

D7.3

BASELINE STUDY ON IHW

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And well-being
In small and medium size ciTies

CORDOBA

RIGA

LUCCA

NITRA

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¹ This deliverable includes also the former D7.6 Report on IHW 1. In fact, with the request of amendment, the baseline study on IHW and former Report on IHW 1 have been merged in a unique deliverable, current D7.3 Baseline study on IHW delivered in month 18.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CMO	Context Mechanism Result
CSIM	Citizen Science Inclusion Mechanism
DIY	Do It Yourself
EC	European Commission
ECRI	European Commission against Racism and Intolerance
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EU	European Union
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency
GDEI	Gender Diversity Equity and Inclusion
IHW	Inclusive Health and well-being
H&W	Health and well-being
ILO	International Labour Organization
K6	Kessler Psychological Distress Scale
LCAs	Local community activators
MESM	Mobile Experience Sampling Method
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
P-PE	Practical Participatory Evaluation
PPPPs	Public-Private-People Partnerships
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SMSCs	Small and Medium size cities
UNDP	United Nations Development
VIS	Visionary and Integrated Solution
WHO	World Health Organization
WHO5	The World Health Organisation- Five Well-Being Index
WHO-QOL	World Health Organization - Quality of Life
WP	Work Package

PARTNERS' SHORT NAMES

AVUE	Neighbourhood Association Union and Hope of Las Palmeras
BOT	Book on a Tree
BSC	Baltic Studies Center
B4B	Bridge for Billions
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
DFC	Design for Change Spain
HIDE	Hidepark Civic Association Triptych
ISIM	isIMPACT
KQ	Kalniciema Quarter
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
LCREA	Lucca Crea
LUCCA	Comune di Lucca
NITRA	Mesto Nitra
PUJ	Pontificia Universidad Javeriana
RIGA	Riga Planning Region
SUA	Slovak University of Agriculture
TSR	Tesserae
UCO	Universidad de Córdoba
UNIPI	Universita di Pisa
UREAD	University of Reading
WGT	WellnessTechGroup

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the results of the task 7.3 baseline study on Inclusive Health and Well-being (IHW) carried by partner ISIM in collaboration with UREAD and the local partners UCO, UNIPI, RPR, BSC, HIDE and SUA in the four pilot cities of Cordoba, Riga, Lucca and Nitra from June to October 2021.

The report also includes former Deliverable 7.6 Report on IHW-1: the baseline study has been in fact enriched by including the storytelling exercises that were originally planned to be analysed in former D7.6.

The report is structured in two sections and one methodological appendix.

Section one presents, per each pilot city, the analysis of both the context and the baseline concerning Inclusive Health and Well-being (IHW) based, respectively, on the context and impact indicators co-designed in task 7.1. For each city, the analysis will specify any significant difference between intervention groups and control groups and among city target groups regarding the starting condition of health and well-being, also considering the role of Gender Diversity Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) personal characteristics identified in D7.1².

Section two presents the analysis of the effects of COVID 19 pandemic on health and well-being by reporting a comparative analysis across the 4 cities on a set of quantitative indicators detected through the baseline city survey on IHW.

The methodological appendix describes the research methods and tools involved in the baseline study, including the use of the Citizens Science Inclusion Mechanism and the role of local inhabitants in the research.

2 D7.1 Inclusive Impact Assessment Plan is available at this link: https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/WP7_D7.1-INCLUSIVE-IMPACT-ASSESSMENTE-PLAN_May_2021.pdf

INTRODUCTION

For the purpose of assessing the impact of IN-HABIT solutions in terms of changes affecting health and well-being of people in the re-designed city areas, it is necessary to measure and isolate the changes produced by the project compared to a baseline.

A baseline study is an analysis of the current situation to identify the starting points for a programme or project. It looks at what information must be considered and analysed to establish a baseline or starting point, the benchmark against which future progress can be assessed or comparisons made.³

Within the IN-HABIT project the baseline study on inclusive health and well-being (IHW) is coordinated and carried by ISIM under task 7.3 of WP7. The task is performed with the involvement of partner UREAD, which is responsible for the analysis of data on mental health, and with the involvement of the Local Community Activators (LCAs) working within the local research teams of the city partners UCO (Cordoba), RPR and BSC (Riga), UNIPI and LUCCA (Lucca), SUA and HIDE (Nitra). For more details on the role of the LCAs please refer to the Appendix on research methods and tools. **The objective of this baseline study on IHW is to identify and describe the starting point of the condition of local target groups in terms of health and well-being by focusing on the dimensions and sub-dimensions identified in D7.1.**

♦ Table 1 – IHW dimensions and sub-dimensions

Dimension	Sub-dimension
Social well-being	Social cohesion
	Social inclusion
	Civil and social engagement
	Equality
	Discrimination
Spatial and environmental well-being	Sense of safety
	Satisfaction with urban green areas
	Perception of noise and air pollution
	Perception of the neighbourhood and sense of belonging
	Accessibility of resources
Subjective well-being	Mental distress
	Psychological well-being
	Life satisfaction
Healthy lifestyles	Perceived physical health
	Eating habits
	Sports practice
	Social and cultural habits
	Human-animal interaction
	Leisure and free time
Economic well-being	Employment
	Job and skills satisfaction
	Financial situation
	Housing and living conditions

3 Eurostat. Glossary Baseline Study, Statistical concepts. Statistic Explained. European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Baseline_study.

This analysis is based on both qualitative and quantitative Key Impact Indicators⁴ that have been pre-identified and co-designed with the involvement of local partners, citizens and local GDEI organizations in task 7.1.

By presenting this baseline, the proposed study will also:

- reveal any initial differences of the starting IHW condition in the identified intervention groups and control groups for each city;
- detect and describe any significant difference among groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion based on a set of pre-identified personal characteristics, namely: age, gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, citizenship status, residency status, country of birth, religion, disability;
- detect and analyse the effects of Covid-19 in the initial condition of health and well-being of the target groups, in order to consider Covid-19 as a key intervening variable in the evaluation of the changes and progress that the IN-HABIT solutions may produce.

Besides the analysis of the baseline, the study will also present an analysis of the context of IHW concerning the four pilot cities and target groups. This context analysis is based on the measurement of both qualitative and quantitative Context Indicators co-designed in task 7.1. The context analysis aims at capturing those components of health and well-being which are not expected to change due to the projects' solutions but, at the same time, are likely to influence the results of the project.

The study makes use of a four-levels participatory mechanism described in the "Citizen Science Inclusion Mechanism" defined in D7.1, where local inhabitants are engaged in the multiple stages of the impact assessment from the co-design of indicators to the data collection and communication actions. The involvement of local inhabitants in the baseline data collection is described with more detail in the Appendix.

The baseline study is also characterized by the strategic and cross-use of qualitative/quantitative procedures of data collection and analysis, called mixed methodology research⁵ The following **research actions** have been implemented, according to the evaluation plan D7.1:

a. Collection and analysis of secondary data

Administrative data and available statistics on health and well-being at city and regional level have been collected by local partners and analysed by ISIM, on the basis of a specific list of indicators for secondary data collection and guidelines provided in task 7.1 (see D7.1 Annex 1, sheet 2).

b. City survey on Inclusive Health and Well-being

One general survey on IHW has been co-designed by ISIM with the involvement of UREAD and the local research partners UCO, UNIPI, BSC and SUA based on the list of IHW indicators identified in task 7.1 (see D7.1, section 3 "City solutions, expected changes and indicators). In each city, the survey has been administered from 28th of August to 31st of October 2021, with the involvement of local community activators and local observers, by using a combination of context-specific distribution strategies and modalities (for more details on the city distribution strategies please refer to paragraph II.a of the Appendix).

c. Focus groups

One focus group per city has been organised and run in the local language by LCAs with the involvement of five-ten local inhabitants belonging to the city target groups and living (or attending daily) the intervention area. Participants have been selected by LCAs with the help of city partners and local observers. Specific guidelines and training have been provided by ISIM to the LCAs for the implementation of the focus groups, including guiding questions and a selection of IHW indicators to be used in this research action (guidelines available in Annex 3).

d. Data collection through storytelling

Storytelling is used as an assessment tool in WP7, as better described in D7.1. Within the baseline study, per-

4 Key Impact Indicators (KIIs) measure the changes produced by the project compared to a baseline. They can be quantitative (expressed in numbers or rates) or qualitative (expressed in phenomena, general trends, examples, typifications). For the purposes of this analysis, KIIS represent those aspects of IHW which are likely to change due to the intervention.

5 Amaturò E., Punziano G., (2016), Mixed methods in social research, Carocci Editore

sonal stories from local inhabitants are collected and analysed to deepen the change affecting specific aspects (sub-dimensions) of people's socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles after COVID 19.

Five stories per city have been collected by LCAs through the direct engagement of local observers, members of the organized groups or local inhabitants living or attending daily the intervention group. Specific guidelines and training have been provided by ISIM to the LCAs for the collection of the stories, including a storytelling track and a selection of IHW indicators to be used in this research action (Annex 3).

CONTEXT AND BASELINE ANALYSIS

The following sections describe, per each pilot city, the results of both quantitative and qualitative studies carried in task 7.3 by focusing, on one hand, on the analysis of the context and, secondly, on the analysis of the baseline of IHW.

The **analysis of the context** relates to those aspects of IHW that are **not supposed to change** due to the IN-HABIT solutions (although any unexpected change that may occur will be detected and reported in the ex-post study). These aspects have been pre-identified during the co-design of the Context Indicators in task 7.1 (more detail is provided in D7.1).

The context analysis is presented by grouping the context indicators within sub-dimensions of IHW that are supposed to act as **external influencing factors**: although not directly involved in the causal chain, these factors may influence the results of the project on IHW. One of these influencing factors across the four cities, for instance, is represented by the Covid-19 pandemic.

The data sources for the context analysis in each city are: the secondary data, the city survey, the focus group and the stories from local inhabitants.

On the other hand, per each city, the present report provides the **analysis of the baseline concerning IHW**. It is presented for each of the dimensions of IHW under investigation, namely social well-being, mental health, healthy lifestyles and economic well-being. By following the theory-based evaluation approach⁶ (Weiss, 2007), the analysis is based on the **assumptions regarding the expected changes** that the IN-HABIT project is likely to produce in the intervention group of inhabitants, namely those living or attending the intervention neighbourhoods identified by city partners, compared to those who do not (more detail on the methodology of the baseline study is provided in the Appendix). The identification of the research assumptions derives from the participative co-design of the expected changes and related Key Impact Indicators carried in task 7.1. For a full description of the city specific assumptions, expected changes and indicators involved in the baseline analysis, please refer to Annex 4.

For each city, the baseline analysis specifies: an overview of the current situation regarding each IHW sub-dimension; any relevant differences between intervention groups and control groups as well as between city target groups. The data sources for the baseline analysis in each city are: the city survey, the focus group and the storytelling sessions.

6 A theory-based impact evaluation focuses on programme theories, i.e. the assumptions of policy makers and stakeholders on the preconditions, mechanism and context for an intervention to work. Theory-based impact evaluations test these assumptions against the observed results following the different steps of the intervention logic and examine other influencing factors. They are thus able to explain why and how results have occurred and to appraise the contribution of the programme and of other factors. European Commission - Impact evaluation center. Theory-based impact evaluation FAQs. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/evaluations/guidance/impact_faq_theor#2.

1. CORDOBA

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1. CORDOBA

1.1 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE BASELINE STUDY IN CORDOBA

The specific objective of the baseline study in Cordoba is to identify the starting health and well-being condition of the local intervention group and make a comparison with the starting condition of a control group in the city regarding the following aspects of H&W:

◆ **Table n.2** – Aspects of H&W involved in the baseline study of Cordoba

Dimension	Sub-dimension
Social well-being	Social cohesion
	Social inclusion
	Discrimination
	Equality in the access to culture and leisure
Spatial and environmental well-being	Perception of security
	Accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood
	Satisfaction with the neighbourhood and urban green areas
Healthy lifestyles	Perceived physical health
	Eating habits
	Sports practice
	Cultural participation and culture-related well-being
	Free time and leisure
Economic well-being	Employment
	Job and skills satisfaction
	Financial situation
Subjective well-being	Psychological well-being
	Mental distress
	Life satisfaction

The project quantitative impacts will be assessed by comparing the average difference over time among respondents from the intervention group to the average difference among respondents in the control group. Both intervention and control groups were identified by local research partner UCO with the aim of isolating as much as possible the direct beneficiaries of the project solutions. The intervention group is composed by adults (18+) residents of Cordoba who live or who attend in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week) the intervention areas, while the control group is composed by adults residents of Cordoba who do not live nor attend such areas.

◆ **Table n.3** – The intervention and control groups in Cordoba

City	
Cordoba	Intervention Group (IG) Adults (18+) residents of Cordoba who live in Las Palmeras OR who attend this neighbourhood in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week)
	Control Group (CG) Adults (18+) residents of Cordoba who do not live in Las Palmeras OR who do not attend this neighbourhood in a relevant way

Within each group, the proposed baseline study will assess the initial condition of IHW of the following **specific target groups**, among those identified in task 7.1:

◆ **Table n.4** – Cordoba’s specific target groups involved in the baseline study

Specific Target Groups in Cordoba
Young people aged 18 – 30
Persons with disabilities
Women
LGBTQI+ People
Elderly aged 65+
Ethnic minorities
Religious minorities

1.2 THE BASELINE STUDY IN CORDOBA – KEY FEATURES

The key features of the baseline study in Cordoba are described in the table below.

◆ **Table n.5** – Key features of the baseline study in Cordoba

1 city survey	Answers collected	470
	valid answers analysed	449
	Distribution modalities	Online, computer assisted interview
1 focus group	Number of participants	6
	Gender distribution	All women
	Selection process	Direct contact upon invitation through personal relationships established by the LCAs and the local observers
	Inclusion of persons at risk of discrimination and exclusion	1 Person belonging to the Roma minority 1 Person with disability
5 Stories	Number of participants	5
	Gender distribution	3 Women and 2 Men
	Selection process	Direct contact upon invitation through personal relationships established by the LCAs and the local observers
	Participants’ profile	A Roma women residing in Las Palmeras A man residing in Las Palmeras A woman residing in Las Palmeras An elderly man residing in Las Palmeras A young women residing in Las Palmeras

1.3 THE CONTEXT OF CORDOBA

Cordoba is located in Andalusia, the southernmost autonomous community of continental Spain. The city is also the administrative capital of the province of Cordoba and the eleventh largest city in the country. Eurostat reports that in 2019 the population of Cordoba counted 121 thousand private households for a total population living in private households of 320 thousand inhabitants⁷. Despite its impressive historical and cultural heritage, the city scores poorly in most of the socio-economic rankings at country level. For 2018, Eurostat estimates the activity rate of residents in Cordoba (i.e., in employment or looking for employment) at 57%. The activity rate is higher among men than among women (64% males vs 50% females). The unemployment rate for the same year was estimated at 28%, about 13 percentage points higher in women than in men (35% female vs 22% males)⁸.

The project will focus on the neighbourhood of Las Palmeras, one of the most marginal areas in Spain, whose in-habitants include people from different ethnic groups (including Roma).

The quarter is characterised by segregation and disconnection; high dependence of social subsidies (low rent social housing, social canteens), unstructured families and gender violence; robberies, drug trafficking and raids are common problems. Health and well-being levels are well below the city's standards. Well-being is limited by the lack of employment, the low quality of social houses, the absence of incomes to satisfy basic needs, the lack of green areas and public spaces and low education standards. Being born in the quarter is a stigma that makes many people hide their origins or the place where they live and to leave the neighbourhood once they are better off. The health status is characterised by unhealthy diets and lifestyles. Obesity problems, unwanted pregnancies and drug consumption from early ages are common problems.

1.3.1 Psycho-social data on the perception of health and well-being reported from local inhabitants

Local communities are characterised by segregation, discrimination and stigma; high dependence of social subsidies (low rent social housing, social canteens), unstructured families and gender violence; robberies, drug trafficking and raids are common problems.

Health and well-being levels are well below the city's standards. Well-being is limited by the lack of employment, the low quality of social houses, the absence of incomes to satisfy basic needs, the lack of green areas and public spaces and low education standards.

Well-being is limited by the lack of employment, the low quality of social houses, the absence of incomes to afford minimum welfare, the lack of green areas and public spaces, the low educational standards and the insecurity and even fear due to the violent behaviour of those involved in illegal activities. People do not have a feeling of belonging nor identity. Collective and community actions are almost non-existent. Disputes between families and clans are rather common and might lead to the reallocation of extended families (up to 12-15 families) in another district.

Being born in the quarter is a stigma that makes many people hide their origins or the place where they live and to leave the neighbourhood once they are better off.

The health status is characterized by unhealthy diets and lifestyles. Obesity problems, unwanted pregnancies and drug consumption from early ages are common problems.

Local inhabitants consulted during the co-design activities expressed their view of well-being and health to the research partners. The risks factors that emerged from this consultation were:

- difficulties in having the basics needs covered (a stable source of income, a job, "a roof", food). This aspect was highlighted as closely related to psychological well-being (the level of stress), as well as with dignity and social relationships;
- low sense of security, both at home and in the neighbourhood. The safety dimension as well was mentioned as risk factors in relation to psychological well-being (feeling calm, living with tranquility);
- low quality of the public environment ("silent", "well kept", "pleasant and safe for all age groups") that was

⁷ Eurostat (2022). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_LIVCON. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en>

⁸ Eurostat (2022). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_CLMA. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en>

connected to personal satisfaction ("feeling good about what surrounds me") and health. In particular, the lack of a silent environment negatively affected inhabitants' sleep, good mood and school attendance;

- poor quality of the housing, which implied living in an adequate space (several generations were sharing small rooms with clear negative consequences for personal development), but also having good habits like house cleaning and care;
- loss/absence of healthy habits like regular contact with nature, regular physical activity, good sleep, adequate personal care and hygiene, access to healthy food;
- self stigmatization and equality, feeling valued/loved, having motivation and goals, feeling with equal opportunities: these critical aspects of social/relational and psychological well-being were mentioned in relation
- personal growth/academic/career success (wealth , education, employment).

Other psycho-social risk factors and emerged during the work run by Local Community Activator for the establishment of the IN-HUB in Las Palmeras. They are described in D1.1 and summarized below:

- lack of social cohesion and mistrust among neighbours. They are not used to work together nor cooperate. The people living in each patio, and even each block might be an isolated unit;
- low income, unemployment and uncovered basic needs: living from day to day and urgent needs make difficult to think on changes with long-term benefits.
- mistrust in public administration and institutional projects;
- illegal activities that benefit from the isolation and degradation of the neighbourhood and create insecurity.

On the other hand, some positive elements identified by the interviewed inhabitants were: a significant sense of solidarity and belonging within the community ("like a small town"); presence of several associations and service networks to help vulnerable children and families; motivation and willingness to change the neighbourhood (from young people, in particular).

1.3.2 Relationship between external factors and the lifestyle of the target communities

Within this general context, some specific aspects of health and well-being have been measured and analysed in the baseline study as possible external factors that might influence the short to medium term impact of the IN-HABIT project in Cordoba. On one hand we have some environmental factors like equality and discrimination in society, the economic situation and the Covid 19 pandemic. On the other hand we have analysed some subjective factors like perceived physical health, physical activity and eating habits, cultural consumption, time devoted to family, leisure and pets care. These aspects of people lifestyles are measured through context indicators and help understand and reconstruct the lifestyle of the local communities and target groups to better assess the possible external factors that might have an influence on the project's expected impacts.

The impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on the lifestyles of the local communities is analysed in a dedicated section (section 6), that also presents a comparative analysis across the four cities on this aspect.

EQUALITY – External influencing factor 1 for Cordoba

The qualitative study revealed a deep **sense of inequality** which is perceived by the participants from the intervention neighbourhood of Las Palmeras. Inequality lies in the way they are treated by local institutions: "We are crossed out from the institutions because we are a neighbourhood at risk of social exclusion, we are the marginalized of Córdoba"⁹ as well as in the way they are treated by people who live outside the neighbourhood.

"Being from this neighbourhood, many opportunities are closed to you. You feel there is no future for your children at Las Palmeras".

The main obstacles that emerged from the qualitative study were the **obstacles to education and training opportunities** on one hand and to **social care services** on the other hand.

⁹ All the quotes are extracted from the Focus Group Reports as well as from the Storytelling Reports drafted by the local research teams in each city as a result of the qualitative fieldwork research. The full version of these reports is available in Annex 5.

Also with reference to **access to internet from home**, the survey revealed a statistically significant difference between respondents from the intervention group who are less likely to report access to internet from home than respondents from the control group (70% vs 98%).

A majority of respondents from Cordoba, instead, **report having no difficulty accessing cultural and leisure opportunities in their neighbourhood (71%)**. Respondents from the intervention area report no difficulties less frequently than respondents from the control group (68% vs 74%). The association is statistically significant, but the effect size of the difference small¹⁰.

In general, participants in the qualitative study complain institutional abandonment (bus stops, access to health services, job placement, etc.). The participants refer that people in Las Palmeras face economic, cultural and mobility obstacles to access education and other services since they have to move outside the neighbourhood, facing all the difficulties linked to stigmatization and discrimination against Las Palmeras inhabitants.

► STORYTELLING - Obstacles in the access to education in Palmeras

The story of a young woman, a social worker from Las Palmeras, helps understanding the issue of the obstacles in the access to education and discrimination suffered by the inhabitants in the intervention area. Her father did not want her and her sister to study in the neighborhood because he wanted them to study with a teacher, not an educator, otherwise the idea was that “here we are criminals and an educator has to come to teach you the basics”.

She had many difficulties in making friends because she was discriminated against because she was from Las Palmeras. “I had to say that I was from Miralbaida”. She comments that one problem is that the neighborhood does not have nearby institutes. Many families also cannot afford to pay for public transportation for their children to go to high school. People were very surprised that she was from Palmeras and was studying: “The teachers said that I was not going to get anywhere, that I would be useless to study”. She found strength as a challenge since others believed her not capable of completing her studies. Despite the difficulties, she continued studying and got a degree in Social Integration.

DISCRIMINATION – External influencing factor 2 for Cordoba

According to the results of the city survey, about one in ten respondents from Cordoba **perceive themselves to be a member of a discriminated group** (12%).

However, with specific reference to the intervention’s area, the qualitative study revealed a widespread **perception of discrimination in the local society** among participants from Las Palmeras. They reported two levels of discrimination: discrimination based on ethnicity, which is perceived against Roma people (“As I looked like a Roma, then I was going to rob him, I was going to pay him, I was going to look for a problem”) and territorial discrimination based on the neighbourhood of origin (“The children from other neighbourhoods were forbidden by parents to play with children from Las Palmeras”).

Roma participants, however, reported to suffer especially from territorial discrimination, although the prejudices against Roma people exist: “Strong discrimination has risen for being from Las Palmeras, not for being a Roma”. According to the results of the focus group, those who live in Las Palmeras know they carry the stigma of being born or living in a neighbourhood considered a “dangerous neighbourhood” and those who do not live there are afraid to approach.

In general, participants to the qualitative study share a **personal condition of discrimination** and reported different examples. It is very common, for instance, that children are discriminated against in school for being from Las Palmeras: “We have double weight, being a good student and being from Las Palmeras, you have to show everyone that you are a good person, you have value, they see you with a stained, glasses full of prejudice, of discrimination”.

¹⁰ In general, the analysis presents the associations that were found statistically significant (p-value of a chi-square less than 0.5) and of non-negligible magnitude (Cramer’s V greater than 0.1). Given the modest sample size, exceptions were made with associations that don’t meet these criteria but are close and of potential interest to the project. More detail on the data analysis are provided in the Appendix.

They also face discrimination when looking for a job, sometimes they try not to put the address on the CV. The stigma is also sustained by self-stigmation: the residents of the neighbourhood said they are responsible for promoting the idea that the neighbourhood is dangerous: “We are guilty of persevering, we ourselves throw mud in the neighborhood”.

PHYSICAL HEALTH, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND EATING HABITS – External influencing factor 3 for Cordoba

People’s general physical health status, physical activity and eating habits have been considered as a possible influencing factor within the proposed impact assessment framework in the pilot of Cordoba.

The regional health survey for 2015-2016 estimated that 75% of adults consume vegetables at least 3 times a week, while 85% of adults consume fresh fruits at least 3 times a week. With regard to risk factors, the same survey places at 25% the prevalence of smoking in Cordoba and estimates that about 58% percent of the population in Cordoba is overweight or obese¹¹. Statistics for the province of Cordoba report 68% of respondents engaged in sports at least once a week, while about 19% almost never in a year.¹²

The results of the baseline survey carried out in Cordoba in September - October 2021 revealed that, regarding the **self reported health status**, a large majority of respondents from Cordoba report satisfaction with the status of their health: 78% rate their physical health to be good, very good, or excellent. Respondents from the intervention area report satisfaction with their physical health slightly less frequently than respondents in the control group (76% vs 80%).

About half of respondents from Cordoba (53%) report **engaging in physical exercise** at least once per week. Respondents from the intervention area report engaging in exercise less frequently than respondents from the control group (44% once a week or more vs 64%). The association is statistically significant and moderate size. Overall, 58% of respondents from Cordoba reported being the main meal preparer at home. No difference was detected between respondents from the intervention and the control group (59% vs 56%).

Among respondents who are responsible for preparing meals, less than a fifth (13%) reported spending more than one hour a day on **meal preparation**.

About a third of respondents from Cordoba (28%) reported consuming at least three portions a day of **fruits or vegetables**. The percentage is lower among respondents from the intervention area compared to those from control group (24% vs 34%). The association is statistically significant and the effect size small.

A majority of respondents from Cordoba report that **access to healthy food** in a typical week is quite or extremely easy for them (71%). Respondents from the intervention find access to healthy food less easy than respondents from the control group (66% easy vs 79%). The association is statistically significant and of modest magnitude. Among those who did not find access to healthy food easy, the top reason is its cost (61%), lack of access to it in the neighbourhood (16%), and lack of time (13%).

TIME DEVOTED TO FAMILY, LEISURE AND PETS CARE – External influencing factor 4 for Cordoba

Overall, 60% of respondents from Cordoba report devoting **one hour or more a day to leisure or personal care**. The proportion is slightly lower among respondents from the intervention area compared to those from the control group (57% vs 63%), but the difference is very small and not statistically significant.

11 Sánchez-Cruz J.J., García Fernández L. , Mayoral Cortés J.M. (2017), La Salud en Andalucía: Adultos, V Encuesta Andaluza de Salud (Adultos) 2015-2016, Encuesta Andaluza del Sud, Escuela Andaluza de Salud Pública, Junta de Andalucía. <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/export/drupaljda/La%20Salud%20en%20Andaluc%C3%ADa-%20Adultos.pdf>

12 Instituto de Estadística y Cartografía de Andalucía (2019). Encuesta Social 2019. Junta de Andalucía. https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/institutodeestadisticaycartografia/badea/operaciones/consulta/anual/37674?CodOper=b3_2234&codConsulta=37674

A majority (70%) of respondents from Cordoba report spending one hour or more a day **caring for their family**. Respondents from the intervention area spend more time on family care than respondents from the control group (76% one h or more vs 62%). The association is statistically significant.

Overall, 38% of respondents from Cordoba report spending one hour or more a day **playing with or caring for their pets**. Respondents from the intervention area report more frequently spending time with pets than respondents from the control group (47% one hour or more a day vs 25%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate strength.

More than half of respondents from Cordoba report being **satisfied with the way they spend their free time** (68% satisfied or more than satisfied). Respondents from the intervention area reported higher satisfaction than respondents from the control group (72% vs 62%), an association that is statistically significant but small.

COVID PANDEMIC – External influencing factor 5 for Cordoba

The qualitative study revealed some effects of Covid-19 pandemic on the local economic situation, as well as on opportunities for socialization, sports and volunteering that further worsened the conditions of the inhabitants of Las Palmeras. Some key effects of Covid in the intervention area have been deepened throughout the use of storytelling for evaluation purposes.

The football coach of the local soccer team in Las Palmeras, for example, reported that due to the Covid, all sports activities in the neighbourhood have had to be suspended: the popular race and the championship. The Club did not have enough money to follow the training sessions on the soccer field, respecting the regulations due to the pandemic. Children have lost the possibility of socializing in a healthy way and doing physical activity with sport. The soccer field has no longer been a safe and healthy reference space for families.

Some participants reported how they had to stop their voluntary and leisure activities in community centers, for instance a woman from Las Palmeras, who found a lot of benefit from her sewing activity in the neighbourhood civic center, said that when COVID arrived, they had to stop because of the restrictions. This was the only year she could not give anything for Christmas to her children and she promised herself this would not happen again.

► STORYTELLING - COVID effects on local economy and the role of social network support

The story of a 70 year old man who has always lived in Las Palmeras gives some key insights regarding the effects of Covid on the economic condition of local inhabitants as well as on how social network support and solidarity played a key role against poverty and material deprivation in the neighbourhood. He tells that the Covid has greatly affected the neighbourhood in all aspects, economic and social cohesion, since the majority of the family lives from black work, collecting scrap metal, manual work of day-to-day arrangements.

The public administration failed to assist these people who could not go out from home. To survive the Covid, a neighbourhood self-organization has been created. The protagonist of the story obtained a special pass from the town hall to be able to travel to all Córdoba and assist people with the necessary resources. He had to go from house to house, for food, medicine, for everything that was needed, including potable water. He found a spirit of help and solidarity from the neighbors in Las Palmeras: “There are those who made a pot for everyone, for the neighbors who did not have them. It has happened in several houses. During the day there are very selfish people, but when there are strong needs they become one. Even families in conflict, they have put conflicts aside”.

► STORYTELLING - COVID effects on employment and mental health

The story of a woman from Las Palmeras helps deepen the effects of Covid on job inclusion and mental health. In her case, the loss of work and the consequences of the disease itself on physical health were the cause of mental disorders such as depression.

The protagonist is a Roma day laborer mother of three children who lives in Las Palmeras. She has dedicated her entire life to working as hard as she can, doing different jobs.

Due to the COVID, the interviewee and her husband have lost their jobs. She spent a few weeks in the hospital without remembering anything. "With COVID, life has changed, I have no strength". She defines herself as a woman who before was very strong, cheerful, who did not need much sleep. Now she does not recognize herself, she feels weak, with depression and sadness. Unable to contribute to the family finances and to take care of her children, she feels worthless.

ECONOMIC SITUATION – External influencing factor 6 for Cordoba

Another influencing factor that characterises the context of Cordoba is the economic situation. The intervention neighbourhood has been for decades excluded from the growth and development path of Cordoba, which results in a high rate of poverty and marginalisation.

According to the results of the qualitative study, participants from the intervention group meet **difficulties to sufficiently satisfy their basic needs** and the economic situation causes a lot of stress to the local inhabitants.

"We are 4 brothers, my mother is the only one who works in a tourism agency, the truth is that things are going badly, the economic situation has caused me a lot of stress".

The participants to the focus group and the storytelling sessions reported a general **dissatisfaction with one's financial situation** and a specific **dissatisfaction with the time and resources to manage personal matters and personal care**. Women participating in the study, in particular, represented their life as totally devoted to satisfying their families' basic needs (food, house, clothes, access to education), with no time and resources for their personal needs "I would get up at 5 to work until night to go to bed".

They reported a very early entry into the world of work and the lack of the right to a childhood and adolescence. A woman from Las Palmeras told that "At the age of 12, she has started to work as a responsible girl should do: she felt she should contribute to the family economy".

Another man reported that at the age of 13 he moved to the neighbourhood and began to work in a construction site "In these times we had neither adolescence nor childhood".

These results were also confirmed by the city survey: about half (47%) of all respondents from Cordoba reported that their financial condition is not enough or just barely sufficient **to satisfy their needs**. In this respect, respondents from the intervention and control group report very different levels of distress (61% not enough or barely sufficient vs 29%). The association is statistically significant and strong.

Respondents from the intervention area reported also slightly less satisfaction than respondents from control group regarding **the time and resources they have to manage personal matters** (55% vs 63%).

Also about being satisfied with their **personal financial situation**, respondents from the intervention area report less satisfaction with their financial situation than respondents from the control group (45% satisfied vs 57%).

1.4 THE BASELINE OF THE EXPECTED IMPACTS IN CORDOBA

The following paragraphs present an analysis of the baseline (starting situation) regarding the selected **aspects of H&W that are expected to change** due to the project solutions in Las Palmeras neighbourhood compared to the control group of participants in Cordoba.

The identification of the research assumptions on the expected impacts on H&W derives from the participative co-design process described in D7.1. In particular, the specific sub-dimensions and impact indicators of interest for the Cordoba’s pilot were identified by partners ISIM and UREAD with the involvement of local research partner UCO during the co-design phase on the basis of the literature review on one hand and on the consultation of project partners, local inhabitants and representatives of local NGOs on the other hand.

This process allowed to establish the causal chains between the city specific solutions (grouped by typology) and the aspects of health and well-being of local target groups that are likely to be affected by these solutions. The identification of these causal chains is based on the validated method of the Theory Based Evaluation (Weiss, 2007) as better described in D7.1.

The following table shows the causal links between Cordoba’s solutions and the selected aspects of H&W that should be improved by the IN-HABIT project (expected impacts). These aspects cover all the IN-HABIT H&W dimensions: social well-being, spatial and environmental well-being, subjective well-being, economic well-being and healthy lifestyles. Each aspect is measured through one or more Impact Indicator on H&W among those selected in T7.1 and described in D7.1.

◆ **Table n.6** – Causal links between project solutions and expected impacts on H&W in Cordoba

VIS CATEGORY A NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS IN PUBLIC SPACES	
SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>A1 Renovation of public squares and patios with the use of nature based solutions, sustainable furniture, green shading structures, social garden/orchards and playgrounds for children</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time spent in nature (<i>Richardson, M., Passmore, H. A., Lumber, R., Thomas, R., & Hunt, A. - 2021</i>) • Environmental and Social connection (<i>Uhlmann, K., Lin, B. B., & Ross, H. - 2018</i>) <hr/> <p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Openness to diversity • Change-making attitude <hr/> <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one’s surrounding – living environment <hr/> <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety at night • Sense of safety in green area • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Perceived air pollution • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY B
SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND SPORTS INFRASTRUCTURES IN PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>B1 Renovation of public squares and patios with sustainable furniture, playgrounds for children, picnic areas</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impacts of play (<i>Gleave, J., & Cole-Hamilton, I. - 2012</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Trust in others • Social Network Support • Collective self-esteem
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with cultural facilities • Participation in cultural activities • Perceived Benefits from culture • Local cultural engagement • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces

	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>
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VIS CATEGORY C
MOBILITY AND LIGHTING SOLUTIONS FOR PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
 C1 Smart and creative lighting solutions	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety (<i>Peña-García, A., Hurtado, A., & Aguilar-Luzón, M. C. - 2016</i>)
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety at night • Sense of safety in green area • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas

VIS CATEGORY D
TRAINING AND SUPPORT FOR SKILLS AND BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
 D1 Business/startup support services	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills

D2
Training workshops on skills development (gardening, masonry, painting, carpentry, ICT)

KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:

- Mastery (*Sirgy, M. J., Uysal, M., & Kruger, S. - 2017*)

ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

- Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills
- Opportunity to find a job in the city
- Expected sector of occupation

HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

- Practice of healthy leisure
- Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas
- Time spent in social and recreational public spaces
- Benefits from social and recreational public spaces

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY E
HEALTHY LIFESTYLES WORKSHOPS, INITIATIVES AND EVENTS

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>E1 Healthy diets and sports events and workshops</p>	KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive food behaviours (<i>Sproesser, G., Klusmann, V., Ruby, M. B., Arbit, N., Rozin, P., Schupp, H. T., & Renner, B. - 2018</i>) • Link between sports/exercise and psychological well-being (<i>Scully, D., Kremer, J., Meade, M. M., Graham, R., & Dudgeon, K. (1998)</i>)
	SOCIAL WELL-BEING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood
	HEALTHY LIFESTYLES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption
	SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself MENTAL DISTRESS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY F
CULTURAL AND ART EVENTS AND INITIATIVES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>F1 Inclusive cultural initiatives, walks and art performances to combat isolation and clash</p>	KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural inclusion (<i>Fancourt, D., & Finn, S. - 2019</i>) • Aesthetics (<i>Mastandrea, S., Fagioli, S., & Biasi, V. - 2019</i>)
	SOCIAL WELL-BEING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Trust in others • Social Network Support
	ECONOMIC WELL-BEING <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surroundings – living environment

	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satisfaction with cultural facilities Participation in cultural activities within public spaces Perceived benefits from culture Local cultural engagement
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeling cheerful and in good spirit Feeling calm and relaxed Feeling active and vigorous Feeling fresh and rested Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeling nervous Feeling hopeless Feeling restless or fidgety Feeling depressed Feeling that everything was an effort Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY G
DIGITAL SERVICES TO BOOST HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>G1 Digital games and services through the INHABIT-APP supporting healthy lifestyles, socialization and cultural participation</p> </div>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positive impacts of play
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessibility of local resources
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satisfaction with cultural facilities Participation in cultural activities within public spaces Perceived benefits from culture Local cultural engagement
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeling cheerful and in good spirit Feeling calm and relaxed Feeling active and vigorous Feeling fresh and rested Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeling nervous Feeling hopeless Feeling restless or fidgety Feeling depressed Feeling that everything was an effort Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

1.4.1 BASELINE OF SOCIAL WELL-BEING IN CORDOBA

SOCIAL COHESION - THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

The first expected change regarding the Cordoba pilot relates to an improvement in the current level of social cohesion. Social cohesion in Cordoba has been investigated through the indicators of satisfaction with personal relationships, trust in others, social network support and self esteem.

Within a generalised climate of insecurity and fear caused by the presence of violence and crime, the qualitative study revealed a good level of social cohesion among the inhabitants from the intervention neighbourhood of Las Palmeras.

Participants to both focus group and storytelling sessions reported that the situation has worsened and the neighbourhood changed due to the influx of new inhabitants, social and ethnic groups as well as for the abandonment by the institutions, causing conflicts and lack of security. "The neighbourhood has been getting worse over the years, as soon as the city council allocates the most problematic, most conflictive families in Las Palmeras". "There are many troubled people from other parts of the city who came and changed the feeling of union and relationship between all".

However, the local community retains the heritage of the neighbourhood's past, when families were very close and lived in harmony "life in common was wonderful, in the neighbourhood the families that had arrived had all suffered so a climate of a great family was created, with the doors open, there was empathy, harmony". "Our parents have given us the ability to respect, coexist not only with people but with the environment".

Despite the conflicts and fears, the **trust in others**, as well as the solidarity among inhabitants and the **social network support** within and among families are still present in the local community of Las Palmeras.

This perception is also confirmed by the results of the baseline survey. In fact over half of respondents from Cordoba are **satisfied with their relationship with people living in their neighbourhood** (66%) and the percentage of satisfied respondents is not different in the intervention and in the control group (65% satisfied vs 68%).

Family is the strongest point of reference and the main social support: "My parents have always been there, always working hard to make a living, in the neighbourhood I have no problem with anyone". "Union between the people, although it does not seem, once happened when my son died. What happened in that moment I believe can still happen".

Regarding **social network support** less than half of respondents agree that there are many associations, neighbourhood committees, and citizen groups that can help (45%). This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than in the control group (52% vs 34%). The association is statistically significant.

The qualitative study showed two main unifying factors that contribute to **social cohesion** in Las Palmeras:

- one is represented by the common struggle for survival: "the families of this neighbourhood are empowered due to the problems they face, knowing the value of sacrifice and of family and neighbourhood union". "They are survivors, they overcome everything, there is a strong spirit of survival".
- a second factor is the closure in oneself as a community, which tends to isolate itself and throw itself away from the rest of the city to avoid confrontation and stigma. The fear of rejection leads people to isolation: "You lock yourself here because you have no problem here, after all, they are your equals and that's it. And it looks normalised and you don't have to be feeling bad or anything".

The qualitative study also revealed a good level of **collective self esteem** as a community. "The neighbourhood is full of good persons of one can be proud... I am proud to say that in this neighbourhood there are people who study". "Despite many conflicts and divisions between families" participants said they are "Proud for the courage, resilience of the people and sad for the degradation, abandonment and lack of resources".

PERCEPTION OF SECURITY - THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

— Chart n.1 – Perception of security in Cordoba

According to the results of the baseline survey in Cordoba, the **perception of safety at night** is lower among respondents from the intervention area compared to respondents from the control group (53% vs 68%). The association is statistically significant but weak.

Most respondents from Cordoba consider **walking alone in public green areas** to be safe (78%). This percentage is lower in respondents from the intervention area than in those from control group (74% vs 84%). The association is statistically significant. According to the results of the qualitative study, there is a widespread **perception of crime and vandalism** related to the living area of the participants, as they report their neighbourhood (Las Palmeras) is characterised by drugs and vandalism. These results were also confirmed by the baseline survey, since more than half of respondents (61%) from Cordoba agree that it often happens to them observing vandalic damages to urban furnishings and private properties. This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than among respondents from the control group (68% vs 51%). The association is statistically significant but of modest magnitude. Moreover, about half of respondents from Cordoba consider leaving a vehicle unattended to be safe (55%). Respondents from the intervention area consider it less safe than respondents from the control group (49% vs 65%). The association is small in magnitude but statistically significant.

According to the opinion of the focus group's participants, a strong fear was reported due to the few people who control the neighbourhood with violence and weapons. This is also reflected in a low **sense of safety in public spaces**: "Many do not spend time outside, in public spaces, because they are afraid of few families: they are afraid of possible fights or of having problems. They comment that there are very few people, but they use weapons, so an acceptance mechanism has been established out of fear.

A young woman participating in the focus group reported that "I am younger, I have seen the ugly part, the beautiful part I have not seen. The part that I couldn't go out on the street because I could fight with anyone, that they could rob you. It happened to me when I was 13 years old and we were playing in the park, they stole my cell phone and they tried to catch me, I started screaming. From this moment I have not left my house if not to go out of the neighbourhood". Participants however believe that with the support of all, a change would be possible: "There are many more normalised people, it would only be necessary to win this fear".

SOCIAL INCLUSION - THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

The third research assumption regarding the pilot of Cordoba is that the envisaged VIS could contribute to enhancing social inclusion of people in the intervention group. The baseline level of social inclusion in Las Palmeras has been investigated through a set of impact indicators (for a detailed description please refer to the Appendix).

The first aspect is the intensity of **social relations in public spaces**. In this respect, a majority of respondents to the city survey report getting together with friends or relatives in a public space once a month or more (69%). This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than among respondents from the control group (71% vs 66%), but the association is not significant.

People participating in the qualitative study reported that **social relations in public spaces** have decreased in the last years, in particular during the Covid 19. People use mainly the courtyards (patios) of the neighbourhood for outdoor socialisation: "The families are very close, they feel like they belong to their patio, but not much to the neighbourhood. There are no socialising spaces, just the benches under their patios".

Other socialisation opportunities/spaces emerging from the qualitative study are the community center (where women meet for social and creative activities like sewing courses) and the soccer field, which involves families and supporters of the local football team who assist to competitions and events.

The lack of security and the presence of crime also negatively affects both social relations in public spaces and the **freedom of personal contact**. The focus group revealed that many people do not spend time outside, in public spaces, because they are afraid of possible fights or of having problems. Participants commented that "there are very few (dangerous) people, but they use weapons, so an acceptance mechanism has been established out of fear".

The qualitative study revealed the existence of situations of **domestic isolation**, especially for women, elderly, persons with disabilities and children, mainly due to the lack of perceived security ("I have not left my house if not to go out of the neighbourhood") and to the effects of the Covid related restrictions. "With the Covid the situation became very complicated because the children stopped going to schools spending a long time at home". "The public administration has not planned to assist people who have not been able to go out, such as the elderly, people with reduced mobility". In addition to this, being the family the cornerstone of social relations in the neighbourhood, the domestic isolation and the closure of people within the family environment is very common. Regarding the **sense of inclusion**, the city survey revealed that over half of respondents in Cordoba report that feeling a sense of community with other people in their neighbourhood is important (57%). The percentage reporting this to be important is 64% among respondents from the intervention group and 46% among respondents from the control group. The association is statistically significant but of modest magnitude.

Regarding **civil engagement** the qualitative study revealed that people from the intervention group feel abandoned by the institutions: "The environment deteriorated due to institutional abandonment, the administration left the houses without control of their use, affecting the new generations, more isolated, more without an occupational future". This negative feeling is also reflected by the results of the city survey regarding the baseline level of civil en-

agement. In this respect, a minority of respondents from Cordoba report engaging in democratic through committees and councils once a month or more (18%). This percentage is 19% among respondents from the intervention area and 17% among respondents from the control group. The association is not statistically significant.

— Chart n.2 – Socio-cultural engagement and relations in public spaces: how often do people engage in the following activities in Cordoba

On the other hand the participants to the qualitative study showed a good level of **change making attitude** since they reported a sense of trust in the possibility to change the reality and to influence the political decisions through the collective action of people: “I believe that there is a way to change the actual situation. People have to be motivated, but they get motivated. If I fight for something that is necessary for me but not for you, one looks from one side and the other from the other”.

The stories collected in Las Palmeras demonstrate the will of some local people to stay in the neighbourhood and work for the improvement of the social conditions of its inhabitants. “There is a part of the neighbourhood that wants a change and invests in that the new generations can study to leave the neighbourhood or try to change Las Palmeras”.

► STORYTELLING - Civil engagement in Palmeras

The story of a 70 year old man from Las Palmeras gives some insights with respect to the civil engagement of local people. In 2007, he started a neighbourhood table with the neighbourhood collectives to create a work schedule to face isolation, neighbourhood improvement, school drop-out, deterioration of the common area. In 2011 they carried out a neighbourhood consultation block by block and then in the patios to create the “comprehensive plan” for the regeneration of the neighbourhood.

After the end of the emergency period due to the Covid 19, neighbourhood participation has been reactivated. He continues fighting for residents to participate but also for institutional abandonment (bus stops, access to health services, job placement, etc).

Regarding **social engagement**, results of the city survey revealed that 32% of respondents from the intervention group report engaging once a month or more in community problem solving when a problem arises. Respondents from the intervention area do so more frequently than respondents from the control group (32% vs 20%). The association is statistically significant and of modest magnitude.

27% of respondents from the intervention group report **taking care of public spaces and green areas of their neighbourhood** as a volunteer once a month or more. Respondents from the intervention area do so more frequently than respondents from the control group (27% vs 11%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate strength.

24% of respondents from the intervention group report **engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activities** once a month or more. The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (24% vs 15%). The association is significant but of modest size.

In addition to this, some of the participants in the qualitative study showed a good level of **satisfaction about their social engagement** in the neighbourhood and to perceive the benefits from voluntary and social engagement for their well-being.

► STORYTELLING - Satisfaction with one's civil engagement

This is the case, for example, of a **young woman from Las Palmeras**. Daughter of a bricklayer and a housewife, she was born and lived in the neighbourhood, has studied social integration and is working in a neighbourhood NGO as a social integrator.

In September 2020, she began looking for work and began as a volunteer in two NGOs in the neighbourhood to grow and gain experience. In a few months she was hired by the neighbourhood NGO “I was very excited because this is also my dream. I want to go to the roots and work in my neighbourhood to be able to help the people in my neighbourhood. So for me it has been a dream to be able to work here”.

Openness to diversity was another aspect of social inclusion that was investigated by the baseline study in Cordoba. Economic difficulties are often attributed to the presence of “new residents, people who come from outside”. According to the perception that emerges from the qualitative analysis, participants from the intervention group believe that relations have worsened a lot and local people are now less open to diversity: “there are many new people, who have not grown up in the neighbourhood, so there is not such a strong bond”. “There are many problematic people from other parts of the city who come and have changed the feeling of union and relationship between all”.

QUALITY IN THE ACCESS TO CULTURE - THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

Based on the results of the city survey, the majority of respondents from Cordoba report having no difficulty accessing cultural and leisure opportunities in their neighbourhood (71%). Respondents from the intervention area report difficulties less frequently than respondents from the control areas (68% vs 74%). The association is statistically significant, but the effect size of the difference small.

With specific regard to the **equal opportunity of access to culture**, no specific reference was made to this topic during the focus group discussion nor during the storytelling exercise. As people participating in the qualitative study were focused on the difficulties in satisfying basic needs like education and job, the equality in the access to culture was not taken into consideration. Equal access to culture appeared to fall outside their aspirations and expectations. In this sense the baseline study shows that there is a wide room for improvement in order to put the attention of local inhabitants on culture and culture-related benefits in the intervention neighbourhood.

SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING - THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

The baseline study detected the current level of spatial well-being of both intervention and control groups in Cordoba by investigating a set of impact indicators.

The first aspect regards the perceived **accessibility of local resources**. The city survey asked how easy is to find some specific resources in the neighbourhood.

— Chart n.3 — Accessibility of local resources in Cordoba: how easy is to find the following resources in the neighbourhood

Not easy (0/1/2) ■ Easy (3/4/5)

According to respondents in Cordoba, some local resources in the neighbourhood are easier to access than others. In addition, all resources mark a distinction between respondents from the intervention and control groups:

- moving on foot is considered easier by the respondents from the control group (78% of respondents from the intervention group consider it easy vs 90% from the control group) as well as moving by bike (74% intervention vs 82% control);
- finding healthy food is easier for respondents from the control group (83%) than for respondents from the intervention group (67%);
- finding playgrounds for children is considered easier in the control group (46% intervention vs 80% control) as well as finding a green space to do sports (46% intervention vs 77% control) or finding safe, accessible, and pleasant green areas (46% intervention vs 76% control)

Resources with no detectable difference between intervention and control areas:

- 67% of respondents from the intervention group consider finding adequate social and health assistance easy vs 72% of respondents from the control group
- 53% of respondents from the intervention group consider finding help from other easy vs 49% of respondents from the control group
- 42% of respondents from the intervention group consider participating in cultural events easy vs 51% of respondent from the control group.

The results of the qualitative study on the **accessibility of local resources in Las Palmeras** show a general perception of lack of resources among participants to the focus group and storytelling. In particular, the resources that were judged as less accessible in the neighbourhood of intervention are: job and training opportunities, education, safe and pleasant green areas. On the other hand, participants highlighted that in Las Palmeras the social capital is accessible (easy to find help from others) as well as the possibility to do sports thanks to the activity of the local football club.

Regarding **satisfaction with urban green areas** where participants spend the majority of their free time, the survey showed that these areas are frequented and appreciated by a majority of respondents from Cordoba, with some notable differences between intervention and control groups.

More specifically, regarding satisfaction about the **inclusiveness and accessibility of the urban green areas**:

- 74% of respondents in Cordoba agree that they are frequented by people of all ages (68% intervention vs 83% control)
- 70% agree that they are frequented by people of all ethnicities (70% intervention vs 71% control)
- 56% agree that they are accessible for persons with disabilities (50% intervention vs 66% control)

Regarding satisfaction about the **beauty and state of maintenance**:

- 65% agree that they are a pleasant and beautiful place to spend their free time (54% intervention vs 80% control)
- 54% agree that they are well maintained (48% intervention vs 63% control)

Additionally, it is worth noting that 40% of respondents from the intervention group report that they do not frequent any public green area (vs 25% control).

— Chart n.4 – Satisfaction with urban green areas in Cordoba

Regarding the **inclusiveness of public squares and green areas**, the qualitative research confirmed the central role of the courtyards as the only outdoor space which is frequented by local inhabitants in the intervention group “there are no socialising spaces, just the benches under their patios”. However, these spaces are not described as pleasant nor well equipped and cannot be considered as a public and inclusive space in all respects, because each patio is mainly frequented by the inhabitants of the buildings that overlook it: “The families are very close, they feel like they belong to their patio, but not much to the neighbourhood”. The challenge for IN-HABIT in this case is to open the patios to other people from the neighbourhood and from the rest of the city.

Regarding the **perception of the neighbourhood**, the participants of the qualitative study agreed that the image of the neighbourhood is negative and it has worsened in the past years due to the abandonment from the institu-

tions. They do not like the neighbourhood as it has become and they reported that most of the local inhabitants try to move elsewhere to study and to find a better life condition for themselves or their children. However, participants to the qualitative study also demonstrate a good sense of belonging since they try to stay in the neighbourhood to change and improve the reality through social and civic engagement.

Finally, regarding their **attachment and sense of belonging to the neighbourhood** they live in, respondents from the intervention group are generally less positive than those in the control group regarding attractiveness for tourists and good image of the neighbourhood, while they express a higher sense of community:

- 38% agree that their neighbourhood is attractive for tourists (vs 53% control)
- 34% agree that the image of the neighbourhood where they live has improved in the past two years (vs 48% control)
- 47% agree that in their neighbourhood no one is left alone (vs 38% control).

1.4.2 BASELINE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLES IN CORDOBA

SPORTS PRACTICE AND CONSUMPTION OF SELF-GROWN FRUIT AND VEGETABLES THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

Healthy lifestyles were also analysed as a dimension of IHW whose components (sub-dimensions) are supposed to change due (at least in part) to the IN-HABIT solutions in Cordoba.

In particular, expected changes in this pilot regard some of the health determinants like: self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption, awareness and motivation toward healthy habits, practice of sports in public green areas and benefits from sports.

The baseline study did not detect any qualitative information about self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption nor awareness and motivation toward healthy habits. These two aspects did not emerge from the discussions of the focus group nor during the storytelling exercise and will be further investigated through the ongoing evaluation.

Regarding **practice of sports in public green areas** the city survey revealed that less than a third (28%) of respondents from Cordoba report using the public green areas of their neighbourhood to do sports once a week or more. This percentage is similar among respondents from the intervention and control areas (27% vs 29%). The qualitative study also shows that the practice of sports in public green areas represents an undervalued resource that may be strengthened by the IN-HABIT project among the inhabitants of the intervention neighbourhood. The current situation described by the participants to the qualitative study is that of a community that does not use public green spaces for doing sports, with the sole exception of the soccer field. The participants to the qualitative study did not report a specific awareness about the **benefits from sports**, which is not mentioned among their main sources of wellbeing and happiness. The only exception is represented by the people involved in the activities of the local soccer club, who get benefits from sports in terms of higher social inclusion, improved health status and better social relations.

The soccer field as well as the activities organised by the local football club represent a point of strong aggregation and involvement of young people and families. The soccer field is presented as the only resource for the practice of healthy habits among the local inhabitants, who in general are described as sedentary.

► **STORYTELLING - The role of sports against discrimination**

The story of a man from Las Plameras who is the coach of the local football team, highlights the role of football as a lever for healthy leisure and physical health on one hand, as well as to combat discrimination, domestic isolation and spatial segregation on the other hand. He tells that the soccer field is still a reference for the neighbourhood, not only for the children who play but for all the families “it gives the neighbourhood a beautiful sports atmosphere, doesn’t it? Opening the gates of the field and people entering with joy”. It has also given the children the possibility through local soccer championships to leave the neighbourhood to play with other teams, socialize with different contexts, to learn as in other environments it is important to respect the rules.

Also thanks to the support of the Club, since 2017 it has been possible to carry out “La Milla”, a popular race within the neighbourhood that draws 600/700 people from Córdoba: an opportunity for people to get to know Las Palmeras with a different look. The race is a very important moment for the neighbourhood, to reinforce a positive identity, a source of pride and cohesion that involves many people from the neighbourhood in the organization.

The Club and related activities such as soccer game and races are a reason for positively reinforcing the neighbourhood’s cohesion and integration with the rest of the city.

He also tells how the social activity around the club contributes to create an atmosphere of celebration, of serenity. The field itself as a well-cared, clean, illuminated green space increases the serenity and the sense of security of the neighbourhood.

CULTURAL PARTICIPATION AND CULTURE-RELATED WELL-BEING
THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

Regarding **participation in cultural activities organised in the neighbourhood**, 13% of respondents from Córdoba reported attending cultural activities organised in public and green spaces of their neighbourhood once a week or more. Respondents from the intervention area attend more frequently than respondents from the control areas (16% vs 9%). The association is statistically significant but weak.

— **Chart n.5 – Frequency of practice of cultural and sports activities in public green areas of the neighbourhood in Cordoba**

Regarding **cultural engagement**, based on the results of the baseline survey, a minority of respondents from Cordoba report engaging in neighborhood cultural or voluntary activities once a month or more (20%). The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (24% vs 15%). The association is significant but of modest size. The qualitative research did not detect specific data on cultural participation as well as on **perceived benefits from culture**, since the topic was not addressed nor in the focus group nor in the storytelling sessions. Probably, as for assumption n.4 “equal access to culture”, in a context in which it is difficult to satisfy basic needs, culture takes a back seat. In this sense the baseline study shows the potential of the IN-HABIT solutions to empower this undervalued resource in the intervention area.

FREE TIME AND LEISURE - THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

Regarding the **practice of healthy leisure**, the participants of the qualitative study underlined the lack of healthy leisure opportunities in the present situation compared to the past in Las Palmeras. The lack of opportunities for sport and healthy entertainment penalises women to a greater extent. In fact, the only example of healthy leisure opportunity within the neighbourhood provided by the participants is the soccer field and the sport events related to soccer.

An interviewee commented how, thanks to soccer, many children were removed from risky behaviours and helped to practice healthy leisure. Soccer has also given the children the possibility to play with other teams, socialise with different contexts and learn the respect for the rules.

Regarding **time spent playing, relaxing, or doing sport in public green areas**, 38% of respondents from Cordoba report spending one hour or more playing, relaxing, or doing sport in public green areas. Respondents from the intervention area are more likely report spending one hour or more a day on this activity (41% intervention vs 33% control), but the association is not statistically significant and small in magnitude.

Regarding **time spent in social and recreational public spaces**, a minority of respondents from Cordoba report spending at least one hour a day in social and recreational public spaces (28%). Respondents from the intervention group report spending more time there than respondents from the control group (31% one h or more vs 24%), but the association is not statistically significant.

Regarding the perception of **benefits from social and recreational public spaces**, according to the participants to the qualitative study, this perception is alive in those inhabitants who have had the opportunity to participate in the activities organized by the neighborhood community center. However, it does not appear to be a general condition of the whole community and represents a factor of potential improvement thanks to the IN-HABIT project.

Finally, with regard to the quality of free time in public space, according to the participants to the focus group, there is much space for improvement in this respect as the current level of **satisfaction with the quality of the time spent in the local public spaces** is very low. The main use of the courtyards reported by the participants is that of sitting on benches to talk to neighbours. A positive exception in this respect is represented again by the experience of the soccer club, that provides good quality free time to the people who attend its events.

1.4.3 BASELINE OF ECONOMIC WELL-BEING IN CORDOBA

EMPLOYMENT, SKILLS AND SATISFACTION WITH ONE'S SURROUNDINGS. THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

The baseline of employability and satisfaction with one's living environment has been investigated by the baseline study through a set of impact indicators as described below. Regarding the **employment situation** of inhabitants in the intervention group, the qualitative study revealed a difficult situation with widespread unemployment, job insecurity and black/grey work: "The majority of the family lives from day to day, collecting scrap metal, manual work of day-to-day arrangements". "There are many families that if one day they cannot go to work the next day they do not eat". The **opportunity to find a job in the city** is described as not credible or not achievable: "Las Palmeras is one of the (four) neighbourhoods in the city with the highest unemployment rate". "Children also see that they have no future: out of 500 children trained in a workshop, only 3 found a job". The common feeling among the participants to the qualitative study is that people have no hope in Las Palmeras and have to leave the neighbourhood to find a decent job or education opportunity.

However, education is perceived by parents as a decisive factor to allow children to have a better future and those who succeeded in completing their studies show a good level of **satisfaction with their skills and competences** and **trust in the possibilities to find a paid job in the city**.

► STORYTELLING - Job and skills satisfaction

Among the people interviewed we also encounter the case of those who, thanks to the support of family and personal commitment, manage to achieve their personal goals. It is the story of a woman, the daughter of a bricklayer and a housewife, who was born and lives in the neighbourhood. She has studied social integration and is working in a neighbourhood NGO as a social integrator: "I was very excited because this is also my dream". "I am what I am for all efforts, sacrifices that my family has made for me: as we know how much it costs, we value much more and we know the value of things".

About satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment, within a general situation of dissatisfaction, the qualitative research has revealed that the opportunity to improve one's economic situation is closely linked to the intervention of external institutions (NGO, Municipality, School, University etc.)

► STORYTELLING - Unemployment

Emblematic is **the story of an adult woman that moved to Las Palmeras when she was 3 years old**. She belonged to a family of 9 sons, moved to Las Palmeras when she was 3 years old.

At the age of 12, P started to work because she felt she should contribute to the family economy. She got pregnant at 18 but did not get married because she felt responsible for continuing to live with her family and contributing to its economy.

Finally, at approximately 25 years old, she married her present husband, but they could not become independent because they could not afford paying for an apartment as none of them had a stable job. Finally, the husband found a job as a security guard, but he had to move to Malaga. She didn't want to follow him because she couldn't stay apart from her parents. In the neighbourhood, she started a sewing course and tried to create a social enterprise, but she had to renounce this plan due to lack of resources. She and her husband had been unemployed for some years: "receiving €215 in social social aid and 164 euros to pay for the apartment".

1.4.4 GDEI ANALYSIS OF THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

This section gives an overview of the key findings regarding the baseline situation of socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles of the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion in Cordoba. This analysis is mainly based on data from the baseline survey, where associations between key impact indicators and membership to city target groups have been explored with the use of statistical tests and standardised effect sizes (for more detail see section II.c of the Appendix). The GDEI analysis of the baseline should be interpreted with caution though, as the number of observations in some of the target groups can be too modest to be reliable. For the very same reason the analysis by target group could be performed at city-level and not at control/intervention group level, where the number of observations per cell would be even smaller.

Women

The analysis of the interviews conducted for the baseline survey in Cordoba revealed gender differences on key impact indicators in the subdimensions leisure/free time and perception of security.

Women were found to be more likely than men:

- to consider walking alone after dark not safe (women 46% not safe vs men 31%)
- to consider walking alone in public green areas not safe (women 24% not safe vs men 16%)

Women were instead found to be less likely than men:

- to spend time playing, relaxing, or doing sports in public green areas (32% on h or more a day vs 46%)

Elderly and young people

The interviews conducted for the baseline in Cordoba revealed differences by age in key impact indicators. Interesting differences were found in the dimensions of leisure/free time, spatial wellbeing, social cohesion, social inclusion.

Compared to mature adults (35-65 years old), young persons (18-34 years old) were found to be:

- more likely to spend time playing, relaxing, or doing sports in public green areas (46% on h or more a day vs 31%)
- more likely to think that no one in their neighborhood is left alone (52% agree vs 38%)
- more likely to think that finding help from others is easy (60% easy vs 45%)
- more likely to engage as volunteers in taking care of public spaces and green areas of the neighborhood (27% once a month or more vs 17%)
- more likely to get together with friends or relatives in public spaces (80% once a month or more vs 64%)

Elderly respondents (65+), compared to mature adults (35-65yo), were found to be:

- less likely to think that there are many association and neighborhood groups that can help them (25% agree vs 43%)
- less likely to think that the image of the neighborhood has improved in the past two years (19% agree vs 40%)
- more likely to feel unsafe walking alone during the day (33% not safe vs 16%)
- more likely to observe vandalic damages to public and private properties (83% agree vs 63%)
- less likely to think that their neighborhood is attractive for tourists (29% agree vs 51%)
- less likely to think finding a green space to do sports is easy (43% easy vs 61%)
- less likely to think public green areas are a pleasant place to spend their time (46% agree vs 69%)

► LGBTQI+ people

Out of 449 interviews collected in Cordoba, only 30 respondents self-identified as not heterosexual. Despite the small number of responses, some tentative differences could be detected on the sub-dimension of spatial wellbeing. Compared to heterosexuals, respondents identifying as LGBTQI+ were found:

- more likely to think finding safe, pleasant, and accessible green areas is easy (79% easy vs 59%)
- more likely to think participating in cultural event is easy in their neighborhood (68% easy vs 46%)
- more likely to think finding a green space to do sports is easy (83% easy vs 61%)
- more likely to think finding healthy food is easy (90% easy vs 76%)
- more likely to agree that the public green areas of their neighborhood are a pleasant and beautiful (86% agree vs 66%)
- more likely to agree that public green areas are attended by people of all ethnicities (93% agree vs 71%).

► Persons with disabilities

Out of 449 interviews collected in Cordoba, 35 respondents reported having a form of disability. Possible differences were detected on key impact indicators on the dimensions of healthy lifestyle and social wellbeing both. People reporting a disability, comparing to those that did not, were found to be:

- more likely to engage in cultural activities organized in public spaces of their neighborhood (23% once a week vs 11%)
- less likely to spend time relaxing or doing sports in public green areas (26% one h a day or more vs 37%)
- more likely to think that there are association in their neighbourhood that can help them (56% agree vs 44%)
- more likely to take care of public spaces of their neighbourhood as volunteers (38% once a month or more vs 19%).

► Ethnic minorities

Out of 449 interviews collected in Cordoba, 42 respondents reported belonging to an ethnic minority. Compared to other respondents, members of an ethnic minority were found to be:

- more likely to feel that leaving a vehicle unattended is safe (73% safe vs 55%)
- less likely to agree that public green areas are frequented by people of all ages (59% agree vs 77%)
- more likely to never frequent a public green area (59% agree vs 33%)
- more likely to informally engage with neighbour about a community problem (60% once a month or more vs 38%).

► Religious minorities

Out of 479 interviews collected in Cordoba, 77 respondents reported being affiliated with a non-Christian religion and 221 to a Christian confession. Possible differences were detected in key impact indicators from the subdimensions of spatial wellbeing, perception of security, and social inclusion.

Respondents from minority religions – compared to Christians – were found:

- less likely to observe vandalic damages to public and private properties in their neighborhood (53% agree vs 70%)
- less likely to think that finding adequate social and health assistance in their neighborhood is easy (56% easy vs 72%)
- more likely to consider feeling a sense of community with other people in the neighborhood something important to them (72% important vs 59%)
- more likely to take care of public and green areas of their neighborhood as volunteers (33% once a month or more vs 20%).

Intervention Group — People living or frequenting Las Palmeras neighbourhood

Control Group — The rest of the inhabitants of Cordoba

> SOCIAL WELL-BEING

> EQUALITY AND DISCRIMINATION

> PERCEPTION OF SECURITY

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

> SOCIAL COHESION

Participants from the intervention group show a **good level of social cohesion** and collective self esteem, trust in others, solidarity among inhabitants and social network support within and among families.

> SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF RESOURCES IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD AND URBAN GREEN AREAS

Participants from the intervention group **report a lower satisfaction for public green areas**, moreover, they believe that the image of their neighbourhood is negative and has worsened in the past years due to the **abandonment from the institutions**.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

People from the intervention group are satisfied with the way they spend their free time. However, they express **dissatisfaction with the quality of the time spent** in the local public spaces and **lack of healthy leisure opportunities**.

> SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

People from the intervention group experience **comparable levels of psychological well-being and higher levels of mental distress.**

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

People from the intervention group experience **widespread unemployment, job insecurity and black/grey work** and describe the opportunity to find a job in the city as not credible or not achievable.

2. RIGA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

2. RIGA

2.1 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE BASELINE STUDY IN RIGA

The specific objective of the baseline study in Riga is to identify the starting health and well-being condition of the local intervention group and make a comparison with the starting condition of a control group in the city regarding the following aspects of H&W:

♦ **Table n.7** – Aspects of H&W involved in the baseline study of Riga

Dimension	Sub-dimension
Social well-being	Social inclusion
	Discrimination
	Equality
Spatial and environmental well-being	Perception of security
	Accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood
	Satisfaction with the neighbourhood and urban green areas
Healthy lifestyles	Perceived physical health
	Eating habits
	Sports practice
	Cultural participation and engagement
	Free time and leisure
Economic well-being	Financial situation
	Employment
	Job and skills satisfaction
	Satisfaction with one's surrounding
Subjective well-being	Psychological well-being,
	Mental distress
	Life satisfaction

The project impacts will be assessed by comparing the average difference over time among respondents from the intervention group to the average difference among respondents in the control group. Both intervention and control groups were identified by local research partner BSC with the aim of isolating as much as possible the direct beneficiaries of the project solutions. The intervention group is composed by adults (18+) residents of Riga who live or who attend in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week) the intervention areas, while the control group is composed by adults residents of Riga who do not live nor attend such areas.

♦ **Table n.8** – The intervention and control groups in Riga

City	
Riga	Intervention Group (IG) Adults (18+) residents of Riga who live in Āgenskalns neighbourhood OR who attend Āgenskalns for at least 4 hours a week
	Control Group (CG) Adults (18+) residents of Riga who live outside Āgenskalns neighbourhood AND who attend Āgenskalns for less than 4 hours a week

Within each group, the proposed baseline study will assess the initial condition of IHW of the following **specific target groups**, among those identified in task 7.1:

◆ **Table n.9** – Riga’s specific target groups involved in the baseline study

Specific Target Groups in Riga
Young people aged 18 – 30
Students
Persons with disabilities
Women
LGBTQI+ People
Elderly aged 65+
Persons living alone
Ethnic minorities
Religious minorities

2.2 THE BASELINE STUDY IN RIGA – KEY FEATURES

The baseline study on IHW in Riga made use of a mix of quali-quantitative research tools, summarized in the following table.

◆ **Table n.10** – Key features of the baseline study in Riga

1 city survey	Answers collected	336
	valid answers analysed	301
	Distribution modalities	Online, computer assisted interview
2 focus groups	Number of participants	7
	Gender distribution	1 Men / 6 Women
	Selection process	Direct contact through an open call for participants and direct contact through local observers and members of local NGOs
	Inclusion of persons at risk of discrimination and exclusion	1 Person with physical disability
5 Stories	Number of participants	5
	Gender distribution	1 Man / 4 Woman
	Selection process	Direct contact through an open call for participants and direct contact through local observers and members of local NGOs
	Participants’ profile	1 Woman living in Āgenskalns 1 Man from Āgenskalns 1 Woman social activist in Āgenskalns 1 Woman from Āgenskalns 1 Elderly woman from Āgenskalns

2.3 THE CONTEXT OF RIGA

The city of Riga has 632.614 inhabitants, with a prevalence of women (351.056 compared to 281.558 men). The proportion of nationalities in Riga is: 47,1% Latvians, 37,4% Russians, 3,7% Belarusians, 3,4% Ukrainians, 1,8% Poles, 0,8% Lithuanians, 6,8% other nationalities¹³.

This population counts a total of 291.000 private households. Households are composed of an average of 2 persons. Eurostat reports¹⁴, for the year 2020, that 44% of households count only one member. The proportion of households with a lone pensioner is 17%, while the proportion of households with a lone parent is 15%. Children aged 0-17 are present in 25% of the households in Riga.

Riga historical centre was included on the UNESCO List of Cultural Heritage. The intervention area of IN-HABIT in Riga is Āgenskalns neighbourhood and, more specifically, its market area and surrounding squares and streets. Open since 1898, Agenskalna market is a historical market in Pardaugava and has a status of a national monument of culture. In January 2018 the market was closed because of poor conditions. Since 2018 the city council and project partner Kalnciema Quarter had started a process of renovation of Agenskalna market, which has continued during the Covid emergency, when the market remained open, hosting also outdoor cultural events, like concerts, workshops, discussions, performances etc.

Agenskalns market gathers local farmers and street food stalls, develops sustainable ideas and contemporary tendencies, collaborates with creative people, civic activists and businesses from the neighbourhood and beyond. Its renovation contributed to the transformation of the neighbourhood as a whole, who is now perceived as a safe, pleasant and familiar place to live by local inhabitants, who particularly appreciate the quality of social relations, the accessibility of healthy food and cultural life, as well as the quality of green spaces and other public spaces as the market area.

2.3.1 Psycho-social data on the perception of health and well-being reported from local inhabitants

While Āgenskalns is well-connected to the city centre, there are limited opportunities for cultural and social life in Āgenskalns itself, particularly for families and young professionals. In addition, the presence of several pawn shops and gambling establishments, and the perception that Āgenskalns is insufficiently safe limits its social desirability. Furthermore, while the local community has been described as cohesive, the influx of students from abroad due to the proximity of Āgenskalns to several university campuses, may be seen as disrupting the social equilibrium. This, in turn, suggests a need for spaces that (i) allow individuals from various different backgrounds to interact without fear of discrimination or discomfort and (ii) are organised around broader considerations related to GDEI¹⁵.

Local inhabitants consulted¹⁶ during the co-design activities expressed their view of well-being and health to the research partners. Local communities are characterise by a variety of ethnic groups and age groups. The social context in the pilot area is characterized by a vital social environment with a good level of social engagement and membership in neighbourhood committees, associations, cultural and environmental movements/organizations. The risks factors that emerged from this consultation of local in-habitants are mainly linked to the consequences of the Covid 19 pandemic and they can be summarized as follows:

- Higher crime rates and fear of crime among local inhabitants
- Loss of income and unemployment especially for students and young people
- Uncertainty about the future
- Limited opportunities for socialization and communication
- Fear of physical contact/presence as a consequence of the social distance measures
- Psychological tensions that can result in violence among people and groups.

13 Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia (2018) People at risk of poverty and social exclusion in Latvia in 2020, in Latvian. Official Statistics of Latvia <https://stat.gov.lv/en/statistics-themes/population/poverty-and-inequality/publications-and-infographics/10941-people-risk?themeCode=NN>

14 Eurostat (2022). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_LIVCON. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en>

15 Inclusive Transformation Plan of Āgenskalns market area in Riga, IN-HABIT project D2.1, 2022, p. 6.

16 For more detail on the methods for local inhabitants' consultation, number and types of persons involved please refer to D7.1

2.3.2 Relationship between external factors and the lifestyle of the target communities

Within this general context, some specific aspects of health and well-being have been measured and analysed in the baseline study as possible external factors that might influence the short to medium term impact of the IN-HABIT project in Riga. On one hand, the following analysis presents the baseline level of some **environmental factors** like discrimination in society; the socio-economic obstacles in the access to culture, leisure and digital services; the economic situation and the Covid 19 pandemic. On the other hand we have analysed some subjective factors like perceived physical health, physical activity and eating habits, time devoted to family, leisure and pets care. These aspects of people lifestyles are measured through context indicators and help understand and reconstruct the lifestyle of the local communities and target groups to better assess the possible external factors that might have an influence on the project's expected impacts. The impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on the lifestyles of the local communities is further analysed in a dedicated section (section 6), that also presents a comparative analysis across the four cities on this aspect.

EQUALITY – External influencing factor 1 for Riga

Equality in the access to culture and digital services as well as the sense of being treated equally have been identified as a possible influencing factors in the assessment of the impact of the IN-HABIT solutions at city level (see D7.1 for a detailed explanation on the rationale of this choice).

Regarding equality in the access to digital services, according to the report “Riga in numbers 2020”¹⁷, Latvia has the fastest internet in the Baltics and the 20th fastest internet in the world.

In Riga, the overwhelming majority of respondents to the baseline survey from the intervention group reports having **access to the internet from home**. No systematic difference was found between respondents from Āgenskalns and those from the rest of the city. Some differences emerged based on age and disability: older respondents report a lower access than adult and younger respondents, but this subgroup is very modest in size. The participants to the qualitative study reported that in general people feel a **sense of equality** in the neighbourhood and even a participant with disabilities (woman) described a welcoming and respectful environment: “She did not expect that security guards and cashiers at shops would help her and double-check if she is ok”¹⁸.

Regarding **equality in the access to culture**, 77% of respondents from the intervention group of the baseline survey report have no difficulty accessing cultural and leisure opportunities in the city, with a similar value in the control group (71%).

DISCRIMINATION – External influencing factor 2 for Riga

The **perception of discrimination in society** has been also analysed as possible characteristic of the context that may influence the impact of the project.

The qualitative study revealed that the perception of discrimination in the local community is not as widespread in the intervention group since participants report to live in an open and welcoming neighbourhood. Participants with disabilities, as well, underline that in general the neighbourhood is open and welcoming.

Participants, however, perceive that some ethnic groups are more exposed to discrimination in the city, such as a people from the Middle East and India who live in Āgenskalns as well as foreign students attending universities: “Ever since international students started attending the medical school, she keeps hearing disparaging remarks directed at the students, so it would be a good idea to talk to them”. “On the other hand, shops that are located

¹⁷ The City Development Department (2020). The economic profile of the city of Riga, Riga in numbers 2020. Riga City Council. <https://www.riga.lv/en/media/3958/download>

¹⁸ All the quotes are extracted from the Focus Group Reports as well as from the Storytelling Reports drafted by the local research teams in each city as a result of the qualitative fieldwork research. The full version of these reports is available in Annex 5.

next to student dormitories have adjusted to this new situation and now carry more products that are familiar to people from Asia and the Middle East”.

According to the opinion of the participants in the focus group, sexism is still quite prominent in Latvia, however it does not characterise the situation in the neighbourhood, where it is mainly related to “isolated incidents” and “occasional remarks from drunks”.

The **personal condition of discrimination** has also been investigated through the survey. Here, although the general perception is quite low, the situation of LGBTQI people and ethnic minorities is worth mentioning. More specifically, 14% of respondents in Riga reported perceiving themselves as discriminated. The percentage reporting a perception of discrimination is not different in intervention and control group (13% discriminated vs 14%). However, LGBTQ+ respondents (n=27) report more perceived discrimination than heterosexual respondents (41% vs 10%), and respondents belonging to ethnic minorities (n=11) more than non-minority respondents (36% vs 13%).

PHYSICAL HEALTH, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND EATING HABITS – External influencing factor 3 for Riga

People’s physical health, physical activity and eating habits have been considered as a possible influencing factor within the proposed impact assessment framework in the pilot of Riga.

The context analysis through the survey revealed that the majority of respondents from Āgenskalns are satisfied with the **status of their physical health**: 61% judge their physical health to be good, very good or excellent. Respondents from the intervention and control group report similar judgements (59% vs 61%).

The **practice of physical activity** is moderately widespread among respondents from the intervention group. About half the respondents (57%) report engaging in physical exercise at least once per week, with a similar distribution in the control group (55%).

Although not comparable from a statistical point of view, it is worth noting that a previous survey research on Riga (Latvija Fakti, 2016¹⁹) found that 65% of respondents from Riga engaged in regular sporting activities.

Regarding **accessibility of healthy food** in Āgenskalns neighbourhood, the qualitative study shows a positive situation. According to the participants, the neighbourhood provides a good offer of healthy food and the situation has even improved due to the Covid 19 pandemic because the offer of the local market and small shops has been complemented by new on-line services and home delivery services.

However, according to the survey, 44% of respondents from Āgenskalns neighbourhood declare that eating healthy food in a typical week is not easy. No difference by intervention and control group is detected. Among those who did not find access to healthy food easy, the top reason was its cost (42%), followed closely by the lack of time (37%), and a preference for fast-food (18%).

19 Latvija Fakti (2016). Latvijas iedzīvotāju sportošanas un fizisko aktivitāšu veikšanas paradumi. Izglītības un zinātnes ministrija, <https://www.izm.gov.lv/lv/media/3985/download>

► STORYTELLING - Accessibility of healthy food

The story of a young woman with three children who lives in Āgenskalns gives some insights in this respect.

She describes Āgenskalns as a family-friendly neighborhood with excellent access to healthy local food in comparison to other Riga districts, thanks to two local markets – Āgenskalns market and Kalnciema Quarter market as well as several “direct food-buying” communities. She describes the citizens of the neighborhood as “probably the luckiest” during the pandemic because of the opportunities to purchase quality local food outdoors in a safe environment (the market). During the start of the pandemic she started choosing supermarkets online orders with a home-delivery option that has changed her food-buying patterns ever since. However, she states that she still buys local products like vegetables and seasonal fruits in the Āgenskalns market when she visits that part of the neighborhood and at the same time visits her favorite zero-waste shop where she chooses mostly grains.

Regarding **consumption of fruit and vegetables**, only 22% of respondents from the intervention group in Riga report eating three or more portions a day of fruits or vegetables. This percentage is higher compared to respondents from the rest of the city (16%). Level of education marks a significant difference: respondents holding a university degree report eating vegetables and fruits more frequently than those without a degree (25% vs 13%).²⁰

Time spent on food preparation is another determinant of health under investigation through the survey. Overall, 65% of respondents in Riga report being the main meal preparer at home. Women report being the main preparer more than men (73% vs 44%). Among the main meal preparers, only 35% overall report spending on average more than one hour a day cooking. Main preparers from the intervention area report spending longer cooking than those from the control group (45% more than 1h vs 27%).

TIME DEVOTED TO FAMILY, LEISURE AND PETS CARE – External influencing factor 4 for Riga

With respect to the dimension of Healthy Lifestyle, the context in Riga was captured with multiple indicators tapping from the sub-dimension of leisure and free time. Respondents to the survey were asked how much time they devote to leisure or personal care, to family care, to playing or caring for pets, and how satisfied they are with the way they spend their free time. While no difference of interest was detected between respondents in the intervention and control group, some differences emerged based on multiple socio-demographic and GDEI factors (see paragraph 2.4.5).

Regarding **time devoted to leisure and personal care** the wide majority of respondents report devoting one hour or more a day to leisure or personal care (71%). The proportion is similar in both the intervention and control group (70% vs 72%).

With regard to **time devoted to family care** 55% of respondents from the intervention group report spending at least one hour a day caring for their family. More women than men report spending at least one hour a day for family care (54% vs 42%) The difference between the intervention and control is not significant.

The **care towards pets** is not as widespread in the pilot area. Among the full sample or respondents from Riga, 30% report spending at least on hour a day playing with or caring for pets. No difference was detected based on intervention or control group (33% vs 28%).

²⁰ The Official Statistics of Latvia found that only 46% of residents in Riga consumed fruits at least once a day and 49% consumed vegetables at least once a day. The same source estimated that 34% of residents in Riga could be classified as overweight and 18% as obese. Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia (2014). Official Statistics of Latvia. <https://www.csp.gov.lv/en>

Regarding **satisfaction with use of free time**, out of the respondents from the intervention group, 50% report to be satisfied with the way they spend their free time and 50% only partly or not satisfied. The distribution in the control group is slightly different (45% satisfied and 55% partly or not satisfied).

COVID PANDEMIC – External influencing factor 5 for Riga

According to the results of the qualitative study, Covid 19 pandemic produced several effects on local situation in the intervention neighbourhood, by affecting mainly the sub-dimensions of social relations, healthy habits and participation to cultural life.

People have changed the frequency of playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas as well as the frequency of attending social and recreational public areas.

The pandemic has increased the awareness of benefits from social and recreational public spaces.

The use of public spaces for socialisation, especially public green areas and the market area, improved due to the social restrictions and fear of personal contact in indoor spaces. Awareness of benefits from urban nature as well as from social public spaces as the market increased thanks to the Covid.

▶ STORYTELLING - The influence of covid on the awareness of the benefits from social public spaces and from nature

The story of a young woman from Āgenskalns neighbourhood helps understand the influence of Covid in this respect. During Covid-19, all her life was happening in Āgenskalns, “and it was a pleasant life”. Attending the market, its events and walking remained her key social activities in the neighbourhood. However, as other places and usual friends became inaccessible, the importance of meeting people at shops, the market and a post-office, and knowing that life was going on outside was a great comfort for someone as her “living now isolated within four walls”. During her walks she observed that much more people had started to frequent and spend their time in the neighbourhood’s public green areas. Now she better appreciated the presence of these green areas nearby as they were easily accessible to refresh her mind after a working day at home.

Local small shops at the market as well as pets and green areas played a key role for maintaining social well-being. The neighbourhood became much more frequented and appreciated for the accessibility of its resources (cultural offer, shops, public spaces and green areas) compared to the city center. Volunteering and social network support also increased. A young woman from the neighbourhood reported to feel “more solidarity among people, for instance, at her residential building elderly people who were hesitant to do shopping themselves were helped by fellowmen. A sense of community was developing”.

Thanks to the pandemic, the awareness of benefits from human-animal relationships among the participants to the focus group has increased. “During the pandemic, dog owners talked to each other in the park – mainly about their dogs and training their dogs. And then they started greeting each other on the street. Small children also communicated, so the parents had to interact”. Cultural offer is still vital in the neighbourhood, although the participation of people has decreased due to the Covid. The market and other green public spaces have replaced the social and cultural events in terms of contribution to social and relational well-being.

► STORYTELLING - The impact of Covid on the perception of benefits from human-animal relationships

The story of a 74 years old woman from the intervention neighbourhood gives some insights on this point. The person has been living in the neighbourhood since 1971, so, for 50 years. She lives just in the corner of Kalnciema Quarter. Before Covid-19 she used to attend concerts and look after the art gallery of the quarter, and it was of high importance to her.

Covid-19 has not affected her leisure time activities and accessibility, since even during the pandemic time Kalnciema Quarter remained open to the public and was safe to attend because of the fresh air and open courtyard. Also, the market on Saturdays was open, although she avoided engaging in the conversations during the market and doing shopping there – rather sits in her favourite place near the gallery.

She stated that nothing else is needed in the neighborhood because the courtyard satisfies all her needs. However, she acknowledged that she misses opportunity to attend concerts and looks forward to do that again.

ECONOMIC SITUATION – External influencing factor 6 for Riga

According to the Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia (CSB), participation in the labour market in Riga is estimated for 2019 at 81% among persons between 15 and 64 years old, while employment rate in the same age group is estimated at 77%²¹.

CSB figures for 2018 place at 21% the prevalence of persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion in Riga²². According to the data provided by the “Riga city numbers 2020” report, the unemployment rate in Riga is lower than the national rate (3,7% vs 5,7%). Also, the average monthly salary of employees is more favourable in the capital than in the rest of the country (1.089 vs 1.222 Euro) as well as the satisfaction with one’s own financial situation (it is 5.7 in Riga vs 5.4 in Latvia, on a scale from 0 to 10).

These data have been complemented by the primary data collection carried in task 7.3. In Riga, the baseline survey on IHW captured the financial context asking respondents to what extent their **financial situation is adequate to satisfy their needs**. While no substantial difference was detected between the intervention and control groups, some associations were identified based on socio-demographic and GDEI indicators (see paragraph 2.4.5).

The results of the survey show that the wide majority of respondents, both in the intervention and in the control group (83% and 82% respectively) feel that their financial situation is in average or above the average than the rest of their neighbourhood.

Among the respondents from Āgenskalns, 17% report that their financial condition is not enough or just barely sufficient to satisfy their basic needs. Respondents from the intervention and control group report similar levels of distress (17% vs 18% not enough or barely sufficient).

According to the participants of the qualitative study, Covid caused negative consequences to the economic situation of families composed by working parents, who had to face new costs and re-arrange the home spaces also for work. The living conditions indoor got worsened, and therefore leisure and socialisation opportunities in the public spaces of the neighbourhood played a greater role for people well-being.

- 21 Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia (2019). Employed and employment rate by age group, sex:. Official Statistics of Latvia <https://stat.gov.lv/en/statistics-themes/labour-market/employment/tables/nbl020c-employed-and-employment-rate-age-group>
- 22 Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia (2018) People at risk of poverty and social exclusion in Latvia in 2020, in Latvian. Official Statistics of Latvia <https://stat.gov.lv/en/statistics-themes/population/poverty-and-inequality/publications-and-infographs/10941-people-risk?themeCode=NN>

2.4 THE BASELINE OF THE EXPECTED IMPACTS IN RIGA

The following paragraphs present an analysis of the baseline (starting situation) regarding the selected **aspects of H&W that are expected to change** due to the project solutions in Agenskalns neighbourhood compared to the control group of participants in Riga.

The identification of the research assumptions on the expected impacts on H&W derives from the participative co-design process described in D7.1. In particular, the specific sub-dimensions and impact indicators of interest for the Riga’s pilot were identified by partners ISIM and UREAD with the involvement of local research partner BSC and RPR during the co-design phase on the basis of the literature review on one hand and on the consultation of project partners, local inhabitants and representatives of local NGOs on the other hand.

This process allowed to establish the causal chains between the city specific solutions (grouped by typology) and the aspects of health and well-being of local target groups that are likely to be affected by these solutions. The identification of these causal chains is based on the validated method of the Theory Based Evaluation (Weiss, 2007) as better described in D7.1.

The following table shows the causal links between Riga’s solutions and the selected aspects of H&W that should be improved by the IN-HABIT project (expected impacts). These aspects cover all the IN-HABIT H&W dimensions: social well-being, spatial and environmental well-being, subjective well-being, economic well-being and healthy lifestyles. Each aspect is measured through one or more Impact Indicator on H&W among those selected in T7.1 and described in D7.1.

◆ **Table n.11** – Causal links between project solutions and expected impacts on H&W in Riga

VIS CATEGORY <u>A</u> NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS IN PUBLIC SPACES	
SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>A1 Renovation of the public square near the market through new green zones</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time spent in nature (Richardson, M., Passmore, H. A., Lumber, R., Thomas, R., & Hunt, A. - 2021) <hr/> <p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion <hr/> <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one’s surrounding – living environment <hr/> <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety in green areas • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY B
SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND SPORTS INFRASTRUCTURES IN PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>B1 New sports facilities, green art installation and playgrounds in the public square near the market</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impacts of play (<i>Gleave, J., & Cole-Hamilton, I. - 2012</i>) • Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing (<i>Scully, D., Kremer, J., Meade, M. M., Graham, R., & Dudgeon, K. - 1998</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety in green areas • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor)

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY C
MOBILITY AND LIGHTING SOLUTIONS FOR PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>C1 New mobility and lighting solutions in the public square near the market</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved perceptions of safety (<i>Peña-García, A., Hurtado, A., & Aguilar-Luzón, M. C. - 2016</i>)
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety at night • Sense of safety in green areas • Fear of road accidents • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

VIS CATEGORY D
TRAINING AND SUPPORT FOR SKILLS AND BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
 D1 Business/startup support services	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills
 D2 Training workshops on cuisine in the community kitchen	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mastery (<i>Sirgy, M. J., Uysal, M., & Kruger, S. - 2017</i>) <p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills <p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits <p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY E
HEALTHY LIFESTYLES WORKSHOPS, INITIATIVES AND EVENTS

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>E1 Educational/social events on food/cuisine, healthy lifestyles and waste reduction</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive food behaviours (<i>Sproesser, G., Klusmann, V., Ruby, M. B., Arbit, N., Rozin, P., Schupp, H. T., & Renner, B. - 2018</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion • Social engagement • change-making attitude
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor)
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY G
DIGITAL SERVICES TO BOOST HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
 G1 Online food purchasing system to promote short supply chains and healthy food habits	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive food behaviours <hr/> <p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits <hr/> <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources
 G2 Digital games and services provided throughout the INHABIT-APP to support healthy diets, sustainable food production/consumption and recycling practices, as well as physical activity and sports (walking and cycling) in the neighbourhood.	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impacts of play • Positive food behaviours • Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing <hr/> <p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion • Social engagement • Change-making attitude <hr/> <p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor) <hr/> <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood <hr/> <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment <hr/> <p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

2.4.1 BASELINE OF SOCIAL WELL-BEING IN RIGA

PERCEPTION OF SECURITY - THE BASELINE IN RIGA

The survey asked respondents in Riga about the safety of walking alone at night, during the day, and in public green spaces. In addition, they were asked if they were concerned by road accidents and if they observed vandalism frequently. Overall participants to the baseline study from Āgenskalns neighbourhood show a good level of **perceived security**, even during the night, as well as a good perception of safety regarding public green areas. Possible areas of improvement regard the condition of women, young people, students and LGBTIQ people.

— Chart n.6 – Perception of security in Riga

About 65% of respondents from the intervention group score **walking alone in the dark** to be safe (scores of 3/4/5 on a scale from 0 very unsafe to 5 very safe). The difference with control group (57%) does not appear to be significant. Large differences instead are found based on gender, sexual orientation and gender identity, education, employment condition and age. Females are less likely than males to consider walking after dark to be safe (54% vs 79% safe). Similarly, young respondents find it less safe than middle aged adults (54% vs 72%). Finally, LGBTQ+ respondent judge it less safe than heterosexual respondents (56% not safe vs 36%).

Regarding the safety of **walking alone during the day**, the large majority of respondents in Riga report a score of safe (92%), with similar values in both intervention and control group. Respondents reporting disabilities re-

port a lower perception of safety for walking alone during the day (77% safe vs 92%), but the sample size for this group is very modest (n=13).

The large majority of those interviewed in Riga score **walking in public green areas** to be safe. No difference is detected between the intervention and control group (89% safe vs 87%). Larger differences are detected instead based on gender and religiosity. Females are more concerned than males (15% not safe vs 4%). Respondents reporting religion to be important for them find it less safe than respondents reporting religion as not important (19% not safe vs 10%).

These positive results have been confirmed also by the qualitative study, which involved participants from the intervention neighbourhood. According to their opinion, the neighbourhood has much improved in terms of safety. “A few years ago, her daughter went to school in Āgenskalns and her daughter was afraid to be outside in the dark – there were drunks and drug addicts. Her daughter knew some of them on sight. This has changed, but there are still homeless people”.

“Āgenskalns is becoming an elite part of Riga, similar to Mežaparks”. “Previously Āgenskalns was a place for gangsters. Things started to change when the Kalnciema neighbourhood was established and the team moved. In the 1990s, this was a place for criminals. It’s much better now”.

A woman with disability also argued that “never thought I would live in Āgenskalns before I moved here. I studied in this area but did not like it. While I am not fully familiar with Āgenskalns, this part of Āgenskalns (near Kalnciema street) is safe for her. There is still room for improvement (in terms of accessibility), but things are getting better”.

On the other hand, possible areas of improvements regard the **perception of crime and vandalism** in the living area and the **fear of road accidents**.

In comparison to previous indicators, 52% of respondents from Āgenskalns neighbourhood would judge unsafe to leave their vehicle, motorbike, or bicycle unattended. This percentage is higher for respondents from the control group (61%). Respondents with disabilities (n=13) consider this to be less safe (69% not safe vs 43%). In addition, students are more concerned than respondents in employment (54% not safe vs 39%).

When asked about **vandalism against private or public properties**, 57% agreed that it often happens to them to observe such damages. No difference was found between intervention and control group (56% agree vs 58%). A significant difference was instead detected based on housing tenure. Landlord agreed more frequently than respondents renting with the statement (65% vs 48%).

Most respondents are concerned by the **risk of road accidents** while walking or cycling on the street. Among respondents from Riga, 58% of those interviewed report this not to be safe. The apparent difference between the intervention and control area (52% not safe vs 61%) is not found to be significant. The same concern about road accidents for bikes and pedestrians raised from the focus group.

“There are more cars now, and noise is becoming a problem; so is traffic. There are too few cycle paths”. “Streets should become more pedestrian-friendly, speed limits should be lowered and additional cycling infrastructure and pedestrian crossing should be built on streets where the traffic moves faster”.

A woman participating in the focus group said that she does not let her daughter ride on the carriageway and many people object to cyclists using the pavement/sidewalk. “If you are on the bicycle with a dog, that is even worse”.

SOCIAL INCLUSION - THE BASELINE IN RIGA

According to the opinion of the participants in the focus group, Āgenskalns is described as an environment characterised by a good level of social cohesion and good social relations.

Participants also highlighted the ease of getting to know when frequenting public spaces, in particular referring to the market as a place of socialisation. The presence of the market as well that of pleasant and accessible green areas are told as deterrents to domestic isolation, even during the Covid pandemic.

“Everything in Āgenskalns is human-sized. People are interested in what you are doing. Everything is accessible. Neighbours are friendly. They come into the shop and you have a chat with them”.

A new resident who has only lived here four months, notes that people are friendly, and many places are wheelchair accessible. Previously had a poor opinion of Āgenskalns and the market. The people there were not nice, and she did not feel comfortable being there. But “the people of Āgenskalns have changed”. She can feel independent and safe in Āgenskalns. “Āgenskalns is cosy. People know you”. The results of the survey confirm only on part this general trends.

— Chart n.7 – **Socio-cultural engagement and relations in public spaces: how often do people engage in the following activities in Riga**

In fact, regarding the **contact with others in public spaces**, about 61% of the respondents to the survey from the intervention group report meeting frequently with friends and relatives in public spaces (once a month or more).

Moreover, during the pandemic, local inhabitants involved in the storytelling session claimed a higher sense of solidarity and **social network support** among people due to the pandemic.

In particular, a woman from Āgenskalns reported that, with the outbreak of the Covid Pandemic, she felt more solidarity among people, for instance, at her residential building elderly people who were hesitant to do shopping themselves were helped by fellowmen. A sense of community was developing.

On the other hand, participants in the survey show a low **sense of inclusion** and a more individualistic attitude. A wide majority (77%) of the respondents from Āgenskalns to the survey disagree with the sentence “In the neighbourhood where I live no one is left alone”. Moreover, feeling a sense of community with people in one’s neighbourhood is important or very important only to a minority of respondents from Āgenskalns (34% vs 18% in the control group).

In addition to this, only 26% of respondents report talking informally with neighbors about a community problem at least once a month. Respondents in the intervention area do so more frequently than those from the control group (38% vs 26%).

Regarding **social engagement**, participants to the focus group and storytelling sessions reported that some people in the intervention group are engaged in the organisation of cultural and leisure activities in the area of Āgenskalns market and Kalnciema Quarter.

► STORYTELLING - Social engagement in Āgenskalns

According to **the story of a young woman with children**: “Āgenskalns is an active place to enjoy various leisure and cultural opportunities, and for those who want to do something and get involved, such an opportunity is” and she predicts that the neighbourhood will continue to be active in this field.

She emphasized that she greatly appreciated the organizations that continued their work at the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and sought to provide a rich range of leisure opportunities, even under severe epidemiological constraints. She thinks it was very courageous, but it is very important for the community that succession continues.

However, the analysis of the quantitative data from the survey show that there is still room for improvement with respect to social engagement.

In fact, only 17% of respondents report **engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activity** at least once a month. On this item, respondents from the intervention area are more likely to engage in these types of neighbourhood activities than those from the control group (24% vs 12%).

When asked how frequently they volunteer to **take care of public spaces and green areas in their neighbourhood**, only about 7% of respondents report doing so at least once per month. This is found to happen more frequently among respondents from the intervention area than the control group (13% vs 3%).

Regarding the baseline level of change making attitude, it has not been detected through the baseline study, since neither the discussion during the focus group nor the personal stories collected refer to this aspect of social well-being. This indicator will be therefore addressed during the on-going evaluation.

SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING - THE BASELINE IN RIGA

Regarding the baseline situation on spacial well-being, the qualitative study revealed a good **sense of belonging to the neighbourhood** of Āgenskalns, as well as a widespread appreciation of the quality of local public spaces both in terms of **accessibility and beauty as well as in terms of inclusiveness** (“in Āgensklans is easy to talk to neighbours and the trees, green areas, and the harmonic combination of old and new architecture are very appealing”). Everyone, historical and new residents alike, say they have had a positive change in the last years and are expecting further improvements in the future.

More specifically, regarding the **satisfaction about the quality and the inclusiveness of urban green areas**, the results of the baseline survey show a high degree of satisfaction among the respondents from Riga and those from Āgensklans in particular.

When asked about the public green areas when they spend the majority of their free time:

- 91% of the respondents from the intervention group agree that green areas are frequented by people of all ages;
- 82% agree that they are frequented by people of all ethnicities;
- 68% agree that they are accessible for persons with disabilities;
- 84% agree that they are please and a beautiful place to spend their free time;
- 80% agree that they are well maintained.

— Chart n.8 – Satisfaction with urban green areas in Riga

Regarding the **sense of belonging and the overall perception of the neighbourhood**, respondents from the intervention group reported an overall good level of attachment to their living area. Respondents from the intervention area are generally more positive than those in the control group:

The baseline survey shows that a large majority agrees that the image of the neighbourhood has improved in the past two years, with respondents from the intervention area agreeing more than those in control group (76% vs 63%).

63% agree that the neighbourhood is attractive for tourists. However, participants to the focus group specified that, although Āgenskalns is attractive for its intrinsic qualities, it is still to be discovered by tourists and the renovation of the market could give a substantial contribution to the influx of tourists.

— Chart n.9 – Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood in Riga

Both qualitative and quantitative studies show that participants from Āgenskalns widely appreciate the great **accessibility of local resources**, particularly shops, healthy food, cultural and leisure opportunities, green areas and services.

“Āgenskalns is like a small town. There are schools, kindergartens, and sports activities. It is ideal in that sense”. Some participants to the focus group, however, highlight the negative effects of urban renovation and gentrification, that penalize mainly families in the access to housing.

“Āgenskalns is becoming an elite part of Riga, similar to Mežaparks”.

“The only real challenge is finding flats suited for families because new projects focus on small flats. Developers probably focus on students, but families would also love to live here”.

— Chart n.10 – Accessibility of local resources: how easy is to find the following resources in the neighbourhood.

According to the participants of the baseline survey, the local resources in the intervention neighbourhood are perceived as very accessible, with some slight exceptions.

- 58% of respondents from Āgensklans report that finding help from others in their neighbourhood is easy;
- 82% consider it easy to find safe, accessible, and pleasant green areas in Āgensklans. Respondents in the intervention area find it easier than respondents in the control group (82% easy vs 72%);
- 74% of respondents from Āgensklans consider participating in cultural events in their neighbourhood to be easy. Again, in the intervention area more than in the control group (74% vs 57%). However, participants in the qualitative study claimed that cultural offer is not adequately advertised and the lack of communication represents an obstacle for full cultural participation;
- 66% judge easy to find adequate social and health assistance in the intervention area.
- 80% judge easy finding a green space to do sports;
- 87% judge easy finding healthy food in Āgensklans;
- 82% judge easy finding playground for children;
- 94% judge easy moving on foot in their neighbourhood, while 79% judge easy moving by bike;

2.4.2 BASELINE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLES IN RIGA

SPORTS PRACTICE AND CONSUMPTION OF SELF-GROWN FRUIT AND VEGETABLES THE BASELINE IN RIGA

The baseline study also investigated some aspects of the healthy habits that are supposed to improve thanks to the IN-HABIT solutions, in particular the consumption of self-grown fruit and vegetables, the awareness and motivation toward healthy habits, the practice of sports in public green areas and the perception of benefits from sport.

Although the access of healthy and local food has been emphasised by the participants to the qualitative study as an accessible resource that characterises the intervention neighbourhood and the consumption habits of the inhabitants, the cultivation and **consumption of self-grown food** has not been mentioned to be as widespread among local people. This is certainly a possible area of improvement that the project may contribute to.

The participants of the focus group and the storytelling sessions also showed a good level of **awareness and motivation toward healthy habits**, especially with regard to the contact with nature, the consumption of healthy food, the use of urban green areas, as well as social and recreational areas for socialization, walking and relaxing.

The **awareness** as well as the **practice of sports in public green areas** did not emerge as relevant factors nor widespread habits among the people from Āgenskalns participating in the qualitative study. This result is confirmed by the answers to the city survey, where, regarding the practice of sports in public green areas, only 18% of respondents from the intervention group report using the green areas of their neighbourhood to practice sport at least once a week. Respondents from the intervention area report a higher frequency than those from the control group, but the difference is not significant and small (18% vs 12%).

CULTURAL PARTICIPATION AND ENAGEMENT - THE BASELINE IN RIGA

Regarding **participation in cultural activities** only 9% of respondents report attending cultural activities organized in public and green spaces of their neighbourhood once a week or more. No difference is detected between respondents from the intervention and control group. On the other hand, **cultural engagement** appears to be high in the intervention area which is described by the participants to the qualitative study as a vibrant **neighbourhood** with many creative people and associations committed to the organization of cultural events, like concerts, workshops, performances etc.

The qualitative study helps clarify the reasons for the low level of **cultural participation** resulting from the

survey. The lie in:

- the effects of Covid 19 and related social restrictions (“re-acustoming people to going to events in person will be difficult and will definitely take time, till the events are as widely attended as before the pandemic”)
- the insufficient and inadequate promotion/communication of the available cultural opportunities (“There are different venues for cultural events. People who live here, as they learn more about the neighbourhood, slowly start to understand that there is a good cultural offer in Āgenskalns. But this is not apparent to everyone, not everyone uses Facebook”. “A lot of events are happening. However, this process of finding an event is found to be cumbersome”)

FREE TIME AND LEISURE - THE BASELINE IN RIGA

The quality of free time in Riga has been detected through two impact indicators.

With regard to the **time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas**, only 31% of respondents in Riga report spending one hour or more a day playing, relaxing, or doing sport in public green areas. Respondents from the intervention area report spending slightly more time relaxing than those from the control group, but the difference is not significant (34% vs 28%).

Although widely appreciated for their quality and accessibility, the use of green areas could be improved by the project solutions.

Regarding **time spent in social and recreational public spaces**, about 28% of respondents report spending at least one hour a day in social and recreational public spaces. Similar reports are offered by respondents from the intervention and control group (28% vs 27%).

Such a relatively low level of use of social and recreational public space can be explained by the qualitative study as well. Participants to the focus group as well as to the storytelling sessions report that Covid 19 reduced the possibilities to meet people in social and recreational public indoor spaces and thus the market and the city squares and green areas somehow compensated for this lack.

2.4.3 BASELINE OF ECONOMIC WELL-BEING IN RIGA

EMPLOYMENT, SKILLS AND SATISFACTION WITH ONE'S SURROUNDINGS THE BASELINE IN RIGA

The baseline study also investigated some aspects of economic well-being that are supposed to improve thanks to the IN-HABIT solutions, in particular employability and satisfaction with one's living environment of the target beneficiaries.

From available statistics²³ we know that the job satisfaction in Riga is in line with the national average in Latvia (5.4 on a scale from 0 to 10). Regarding satisfaction with the living environment, housing costs expressed in percentage in comparison to current income in Riga is 13.5%.

In recent years, Āgenskalns has become an increasingly sought-after area of Riga, as evidenced by the growing interest of people in residential projects implemented in this area. The growing value of Āgenskalns also revealed by the purchase prices of the property. In 2020, apartment prices in new projects ranged from 2,000 to 2,200 euros/m², while in the future they could increase from 2,200 to 2,500 euros/m².

²³ The City Development Department (2020). The economic profile of the city of Riga, Riga in numbers 2020. Riga City Council. <https://www.riga.lv/en/media/3958/download>

The economic well-being in Riga was investigated by the primary data collection through a set of indicators on employability, satisfaction with one's skills and competences and satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment.

Employability and satisfaction with one's skills and competences did not emerge from the discussions of the focus group nor during the storytelling exercise and will be further investigated through the ongoing evaluation.

Regarding **satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment**, the qualitative study revealed some concern and dissatisfaction among the participants from the intervention area with regard to the access to house and affordability of houses. "Price is also important", declared a participant in the focus group and new flats in Āgenskalns are unattainable for most people. The presence of many students in the neighbourhood also means that the houses are designed to be more suitable for that target than for families. "Āgenskalns the only real challenge is finding flats suited for families because new projects focus on small flats" declared a participant during a focus group.

2.4.4 GDEI ANALYSIS OF THE BASELINE IN RIGA

This section gives an overview of the key findings regarding the baseline situation of socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles of the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion in Riga. This analysis is mainly based on data from the baseline survey, where associations between key impact indicators and membership to city target groups have been explored with the use of statistical tests and standardised effect sizes (for more detail see section II.c of the Appendix). The GDEI analysis of the baseline should be interpreted with caution though, as the number of observations in some of the target groups can be too modest to be reliable. For the very same reason the analysis by target group could be performed at city-level and not at control/intervention group level, where the number of observations per cell would be even smaller.

● Women

The quantitative baseline study in Riga has detected interesting differences based on gender on some key impact indicators from the sub-dimensions of leisure/free time, sports practice, perception of security, and spatial wellbeing.

Women were found to be more likely than men

- to attend social and recreational events in public spaces (women 30 % one h or more vs men 18%)
- to feel walking alone after dark is unsafe (46% not safe vs 21%)
- to feel walking alone in public green areas is unsafe (15% not safe vs 4%).

Among respondents, women were instead less likely than men:

- to report not frequenting any public green area (19% agree vs 32%).

Some gender differences emerged also from the analysis of context indicators, on the subdimensions of leisure/free time and determinants of health.

Women were found to be more likely than men

- to spend more time on family care (54% one h or more vs 42%)
- to be the main food preparer (73% yes vs 44%)
- to spend more time preparing meals (38% more than one h vs 21%).

• Elderly and young people

With regard to **age**, a very modest number of elderly respondents completed the survey, but some interesting differences have been detected between young (18-35) and adult (35-65) respondents.

With regard to key impact indicators, differences emerged on the sub-dimensions of cultural participation, leisure/free time, sports practice, perception of security, social inclusion, and spatial wellbeing.

Adults were more likely than young respondents:

- to take part in cultural activities in squares and green areas (14% once a week or more vs 6%);
- to practice sport in public green areas (22% once a week or more vs 11%);
- to feel that walking after dark is safe (72% safe vs 54%);
- to consider important feeling a sense of community in the neighbourhood (34% important vs 18%);
- to informally talk with neighbors about community problems (47% once a week or more vs 23%);
- to find their neighbourhood attractive for tourists (68% agree vs 52%);
- to report finding help from others is easy (62% easy vs 48%).

Adults were instead less likely than young respondents:

- to get together with friends in a public space (49% once a week or more vs 76%).

• LGBTQ+ people

Out of 301 interviews collected in Riga, only 27 respondents self-identified as not heterosexual. Despite the small number of responses, some tentative differences could be detected on the subdimension of perception of security and spatial wellbeing.

Compared to heterosexuals, respondents identifying as LGBTQ+ were found:

- more concerned of walking alone during the day (56% not safe vs 36%)
- less likely to agree that their neighborhood is attractive for tourists (42% agree vs 61%)
- less likely to think that finding a green space to do sport is easy (65% easy vs 82%)
- less likely to think that moving by bike in their neighborhood is easy (65% easy vs 82%).

• Students

Out of 301 interviews collected in Riga, 82 respondents reported being in education or training. Compared to those currently in employment, respondents in education or training were found to be:

- more likely to think that no one is left alone in their neighborhood (38% agree vs 22% do not agree)
- less likely to think that walking alone after dark is safe (40% safe vs 70% unsafe)
- less likely to walk or cycle without the fear of being victims of road accidents (30% safe vs 48% unsafe)
- less likely to think that finding help from others is easy (44% easy vs 53% not easy)
- less likely to think that finding a pleasant, safe, and accessible green area is easy (62% easy vs 82% not easy).
- less likely to engage informally with neighbours about community problems (15% once a month or more vs 37% less than once a month)
- more likely to get together with friends or relatives in a public space (85% once a month or more vs 61% less than once a month).

▶● Persons with disabilities

Out of 301 interviews collected in Riga, only 13 respondents reported having a form of disability. The number of interviews is too small to detect associations reliably, but possible differences were detected on key impact indicators on the sub-dimensions of spatial well-being and social inclusion.

Respondents reporting a disability, compared to those that did not, were found to be:

- less likely to agree that the green areas of their neighbourhood are accessible for persons with disabilities (23% agree vs 69% do not agree)
- less likely to get together with friends or relatives in a public space (38% once a month or more vs 68% less than once a month).

▶● Ethnic minorities

Out of 301 interviews collected in Riga, only 11 respondents reported belonging to an ethnic minority. The number of interviews is too small to detect reliable associations.

▶● Persons living alone

Out of 301 interviews collected in Riga, 83 respondents reported living alone. A difference was detected on the sub-dimension of sports practice.

People living alone, compared to people living with others, were found to be:

- more likely to use the public green areas of their neighbourhood to do sports (22% once a week or more vs 12%)

▶● Religious minorities

Out of 301 interviews collected in Riga, only 30 respondents reported being affiliated with a non-Christian religion and 113 to a Christian confession. No substantive difference was detected comparing Christian to non-Christian respondents on the key impact indicators.

Intervention Group — People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood

Control Group — The rest of the inhabitants of Riga

> SOCIAL WELL-BEING

> EQUALITY AND DISCRIMINATION

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns **feel a sense of equality** in the neighbourhood, which is judged as open and welcoming. However, they perceive that **some ethnic groups are more exposed to discrimination**, such as a people from the Middle East and India as well as foreign students.

> PERCEPTION OF SECURITY

Experience a good sense of safety, with some concerns about walking alone after dark, theft and vandalism, road accidents

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood experience **good and satisfactory social relations and higher social and civic engagement.**

> SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF LOCAL RESOURCES

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood widely **appreciate the great accessibility of local resources**, particularly shops, healthy food, cultural and leisure opportunities, green areas and services.

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD URBAN GREEN AREAS

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood show a **good sense of belonging to the neighbourhood** and **appreciation of the quality of local public spaces and green areas**.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood show a good level of **awareness and motivation toward healthy habits**, especially with regard to contact with nature, consumption of healthy food, use of public spaces for socialization, walking and relaxing.

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

Due to **Covid 19**, people living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood, **have increased the frequency** of playing, relaxing or doing sports in **public green areas** as well as the attendance at the **market as a social and recreational space**.

> SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood experience a **higher level of psychological well-being** and a **lower level of mental distress**.

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood express a comparable satisfaction with their financial situation. However, they are **concerned with the access to house and affordability of houses**.

3. LUCCA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

3. LUCCA

3.1 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE BASELINE STUDY IN LUCCA

The specific objective of the baseline study in Lucca is to identify the starting health and well-being condition of the local intervention group and make a comparison with the starting condition of a control group in the city regarding the following aspects of H&W:

◆ **Table n.12** – Aspects of H&W involved in the baseline study of Lucca

Dimension	Sub-dimension
Social well-being	Social inclusion
	Social cohesion
	Discrimination
	Equality in the access to pets services, culture and leisure
Spatial and environmental well-being	Perception of security
	Accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood
	Satisfaction with the neighbourhood and urban green areas
Healthy lifestyles	Perceived physical health
	Eating habits
	Sports practice
	Cultural participation and culture-related well-being
	Pets' care and pets-related well-being
	Free time and leisure
Economic well-being	Financial situation
	Employment
	Satisfaction with one's surrounding
Subjective well-being	Psychological well-being,
	Mental distress
	Life satisfaction

The project impacts will be assessed by comparing the average difference over time among respondents from the intervention group to the average difference among respondents in the control group. Both intervention and control groups were identified by local research partner UNIFI with the aim of isolating as much as possible the direct beneficiaries of the project solutions. The intervention group is composed by adults (18+) residents of Lucca who live or who attend in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week) the intervention areas, while the control group is composed by adults residents of Lucca who do not live nor attend such areas.

◆ **Table n.13** – The intervention and control groups in Lucca

City	
Lucca	Intervention Group (IG) Adults (18+) residents of Lucca who live in the old city center OR who attend in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week) at least one of the IN-HABIT intervention areas (as listed in question 10.4 of the baseline city survey on IHW).
	Control Group (CG) Adults (18+) residents in Lucca who do not live in the old city center NOR attend in a relevant way (less than 4 hours a week) any of the IN-HABIT intervention areas (as listed in question 10.4 of the baseline city survey on IHW).

Within each group, the proposed baseline study will assess the initial condition of IHW of the following **specific target groups**, among those identified in task 7.1:

◆ **Table n.14** – Lucca’s specific target groups involved in the baseline study

Specific Target Groups in Lucca
Persons Living alone
Pet owners
Persons with disabilities
Women
LGBTQI+ People
Elderly
Ethnic minorities
Religious minorities

3.2 THE BASELINE STUDY IN LUCCA – KEY FEATURES

◆ **Table n.15** – Key features of the baseline study in Lucca

1 city survey	Answers collected	216
	valid answers analysed	208
	Distribution modalities	online, paper distribution, computer assisted interview
1 focus group	Number of participants	10
	Gender distribution	7 Women and 3 Men
	Selection process	direct contact upon invitation through personal relationships established by the LCAs
	Inclusion of persons at risk of discrimination and exclusion	1 person from the Roma community

5 Stories	Number of participants	5
	Gender distribution	4 Women and 1 Man
	Selection process	direct contact upon invitation through personal relationships established by the LCAs
	Participants' profile	1 elderly male with disability, pet owner 1 young women, student 1 women, pet owner from the rural area 1 women working as artisan in the old city center 1 women, social worker, living in the city center

3.3 THE CONTEXT OF LUCCA

The municipality of Lucca is located in the northern part of Tuscany, between central and northern Italy. The city is also the administrative capital of a province with the same name. As of the 2011 Census, the city counted 87.2 thousand inhabitants. About 12% of the population was 75 years old or older, while only 5% was 6 years old or younger²⁴. Lucca is a relatively wealthy city with an average income of 21.895 Euro. Labour market participation (i.e., employment or looking for employment) in Lucca at the 2011 Census was estimated at 52.7%. Participation was higher for men than for women (60.8% males vs 45.6% males). The prevalence of young persons (15-29) not in education and not in employment was 15.2%. The employment rate was estimated at 48.5%, higher for men than for women (56.8% males vs 41.2% females). Employment rate among the youth (15-29) was estimated at 38.4%. The unemployment rate in Lucca at the time of the last Census was 8% overall, higher for women than for men (9.7% females vs 6.5 males). Youth unemployment was estimated at 29.4%²⁵. Tourism, creativity and cultural tourism are cornerstones in the Lucca economy.

3.3.1 Psycho-social data on the perception of health and well-being reported from local inhabitants

The city context Lucca is characterised by the geographic and social separation between those who live inside and those outside the old city walls. The Ageing of the population is contributing to enhancing the geographical divide between the city centre inside the walls, where the aged population live, and the other outside part of the city. Local inhabitants consulted during the co-design activities expressed their view of well-being and health to the research partners. The risks factors that emerged from this consultation were:

- the poor quality of social relations (“freedom of movement... possibility to meet others in person, talk to each other not through a screen”)
- the quality and quantity of free time
- the lack of contact with nature, socialization and relax in the green spaces
- the quality and accessibility of the public green areas, especially for persons with disabilities (“Living and moving in spaces designed with criteria of functionality, accessibility and beauty...walking in neat and clean places... having accessible spaces, on a human scale, not invaded by traffic”)
- the perception of safety in public spaces (“illuminated spaces, living in a place where you feel safe and not exposed to aggression, robbery, ect., ...have the freedom to frequent green areas that are currently not frequented because they are unsafe”).

Some risks factors were expressed by local inhabitants in relation to the Covid 19 pandemic crisis, in particular:

- poor relational well-being, lack of freedom and opportunities for socialization (“habit of free social contact and without mistrust”);
- worse economic / financial situation of households.

24 ISTAT (2011). Una selezione di indicatori per ogni comune d'Italia. Ottomilacensus ISTAT. <https://ottomilacensus.istat.it/comune/046/046017/>

25 ISTAT (2011). Una selezione di indicatori per ogni comune d'Italia. Ottomilacensus ISTAT. <https://ottomilacensus.istat.it/sottotema/046/046017/11/>

3.3.2 Relationship between external factors and the lifestyle of the target communities

Within this general context, some specific aspects of health and well-being have been measured and analysed in the baseline study as possible external factors that might influence the short to medium term impact of the IN-HABIT project in Lucca. On one hand, the following analysis presents the baseline level of some environmental factors like discrimination in society, socio-economic obstacles in the access to culture and digital services, the economic situation and the Covid 19 pandemic. On the other hand we have analysed some subjective factors like perceived physical health, physical activity and eating habits, time devoted to family, leisure and pets care. These aspects of people lifestyles are measured through context indicators and help understand and reconstruct the lifestyle of the local communities and target groups to better assess the possible external factors that might have an influence on the project's expected impacts.

The impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on the lifestyles of the local communities is further analysed in a dedicated section (section 6), that also presents a comparative analysis across the four cities on this aspect.

EQUALITY IN THE ACCESS TO CULTURE AND DIGITAL SERVICES – External influencing factor 1 for Lucca

The first influencing factor that characterises the context of Lucca is equality in the access to culture and digital services.

More than half of respondents from the intervention group to the baseline survey report having difficulty **accessing cultural and leisure opportunities** in their neighbourhood. Respondents from the intervention group report difficulties less frequently than respondents from the control group (58% vs 66%), although the difference is not statistically significant²⁶.

This gap between internal/central and external/peripheral communities emerged also from the qualitative study which revealed various **obstacles to the access to culture**. More specifically, according to participants to the qualitative study, there is a competition between local inhabitants and tourists for the access to culture; obstacles related to mobility (inadequate public transport and parking) as well as to the quality and inclusiveness of the offer (events conceived for tourists or not well advertised by local associations).

According to the participants of the baseline focus group, cultural resources are not distributed equally since they are mainly concentrated in the old city center (“inside the walls”) and organised by and for small groups of people (niches, NGOs) or for tourists. The main obstacles to the equal access to culture are in fact mobility and communication.

“My grandmother, for example, lives in Monte S Quirico where there is no public transport available, she’s aged and when she will no longer be able to drive the car, she will have a problem to go to the city”²⁷.

“There are many cultural events but not all of them are advertised in the same way. Beyond the two or three major events, the other initiatives are varied but restricted to small groups and even information on these activities circulates very little. Once there were some magazines that informed about the cultural offer (both in English and Italian). The problem of how to inform people about the cultural offer is always alive”.

Another aspect of equality that was investigated through the city survey is the **access to internet from home**. In this respect, the overwhelming majority of respondents from Lucca report having access to internet from home. No difference is detected between respondents from the intervention and control group (93% vs 91%).

²⁶ In general, the analysis presents the associations that were found statistically significant (p-value of a chi-square less than 0.5) and of non-negligible magnitude (Cramer’s V greater than 0.1). Given the modest sample size, exceptions were made with associations that don’t meet these criteria but are close and of potential interest to the project. More detail on the data analysis are provided in the Appendix.

²⁷ All the quotes are extracted from the Focus Group Reports as well as from the Storytelling Reports drafted by the local research teams in each city as a result of the qualitative fieldwork research. The full version of these reports is available in Annex 5.

DISCRIMINATION – External influencing factor 2 for Lucca

Discrimination in society has also been identified as a possible influencing factor in the assessment of the impact of the IN-HABIT solutions at city level. The results of the qualitative study show a twofold situation with regards to discrimination.

On one hand the local society is welcoming in terms of reception measures to newly arrived migrants (like language courses, assistance from voluntary associations) as well as intercultural initiatives.

“There are many foreign communities living in Lucca and the number of interventions of the municipality over the years has been conspicuous, they have organized several activities for people who are not native Italian language or initiatives where foreign people were invited to cook the typical food of their countries”.

“Lucca has been called “the European capital of volunteering”, so there is good interaction with foreign communities”. On the other hand, those working with migrants pointed out that prejudices and discrimination in society exists especially against non EU citizens, who face serious difficulties in the access to house.

“There are real estate agencies that claim that their clients do not rent to foreigners. A boy from Senegal had to buy his house in Navacchio because in Lucca no one sold it to him. There are some aspects that remain hurdles, but the hospitality is excellent”.

“I work with foreign people for years, often I felt eyes on me riding with them around the city, in offices etc.. There are serious difficulties to find accommodation for foreigners. In my opinion, it isn't a comfortable city for foreigners. I don't feel like living in a welcoming city”.

The presence of a Roma community in the intervention area, who was identified as the main problem/opportunity in terms of need for inclusion at the time of the proposal, did not emerge from the baseline study as a specific issue regarding discrimination towards Roma people.

Regarding the **perceived personal condition of discrimination**, less than a tenth (6%) of respondents from Lucca perceive themselves to be a member of a discriminated group. No appreciable difference is detected between respondents from the intervention and the control group (4% vs 7%).

The testimony of a participant in the focus group once again highlights the gap between a good reception system and the difficulty to establish good and long lasting social relationships with the “native” inhabitants:

“I belong to Roma community. The inhabitant of Lucca is welcoming but it's hard to open himself to people who are not from Lucca. The groups of friends are hermetics. At the same time friends last one season. It's all very “eat and go” with regard to domestic tourism but also with regard to social relations”.

PHYSICAL HEALTH, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND EATING HABITS – External influencing factor 3 for Lucca

People's physical health, physical activity and eating habits have been considered as a possible influencing factor within the proposed impact assessment framework in the pilot of Lucca.

Regarding the **self reported health status**, over half of respondents from Lucca report satisfaction with the status of their health: 62% rate their physical health to be good, very good, or excellent. Respondents from the intervention area report satisfaction with their physical health slightly less frequently than respondents in the control group (58% vs 65%), but the difference is not statistically significant.

Only a third of respondents from Lucca (30%) report engaging in **physical exercise** at least once per week. No appreciable difference is detected between respondents from the intervention and control group (33% vs 28%). Overall, 70% of respondents from Lucca reported being the main meal preparer at home. No difference was detected between respondents from the intervention and the control group (70% vs 69%).

Among respondents who are responsible for preparing meals, less than a fifth (13%) reported spending more

than one hour a day on **meal preparation at home**. No difference was detected between respondents from the intervention and the control group (13% vs 13%).

Regarding the **consumption of fruit and vegetables**, about a third of respondents from Lucca (33%) reported consuming at least three portions a day of fruits or vegetables. The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area compared to those from the control group (37% vs 30%) but the difference is small and not statistically significant.

TIME DEVOTED TO FAMILY, LEISURE AND PETS CARE – External influencing factor 4 for Lucca

Time devoted to leisure, family and pet's care have been considered as possible elements of the context that may influence the impact of the IN-HABIT solutions in Lucca.

Regarding **time devoted to leisure and personal care**, overall, 63% of respondents from Lucca reported devoting one hour or more a day to leisure or personal care. The proportion is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to those from the control group (68% vs 59%), but the difference is not statistically significant.

The large majority (81%) of respondents from Lucca report spending one hour or more a day **caring for their family**. Respondents from the intervention group spend more time on family care than respondents from the control group (87% one hour or more vs 76%). The association is statistically significant.

Regarding **time devoted to pets**, overall, 57% of respondents from Lucca reported spending one hour or more a day playing with or caring for their pets. No appreciable difference was detected between respondents from the intervention and control group (59% vs 54%).

The baseline city survey in Lucca also detected the current level of **satisfaction with free time use** of local residents. About half of respondents to the survey report being satisfied with the way they spend their free time (47% satisfied or more than satisfied). No differences in this proportion is found between respondents from the intervention and control group (48% vs 46%).

COVID PANDEMIC – External influencing factor 5 for Lucca

The qualitative study helped deepen some effects of the Covid 19 pandemic (first, second and third wave) in the city of Lucca, while a comparative analysis among the four cities is presented in section 5 based on the results of the quantitative study.

As the city of Lucca is characterised by the dichotomy inside-outside the walls, the qualitative study showed increased tensions due to the lack of adequate public transport and connections between the old city center and the periphery. The sense of **fear of social contact** determined further **isolation** of the inhabitants of the areas outside the city center and fewer opportunities to **access social recreational spaces** and events located mainly inside the walls. The study also revealed an **increase of the use of car** compared to other means of transport like bus.

A participant to the baseline focus group, who lives in the countryside quite far from the city center said that, soon after the lockdown:

“I have a feeling of great well-being when I'm at home, but the problem of movement has arisen, the roads are very congested and I can't use the bike, therefore, I use much more the car”.

Covid-19 pandemic produced an impact on the level of **social engagement** of people as well as on the **perceived quality of their free time**. Volunteering represents a key enabling factor for people's well-being in terms of social inclusion and life satisfaction. The restrictions due to the Covid pandemic reduced the time devoted to voluntary activities by producing mobility obstacles and fear/discomfort with respect to personal relationships and

daily activities as attending community centers, social events and using public transports. This penalised in particular the inhabitants of rural and peripheral areas, who suffered from a twofold condition of isolation: domestic isolation and socio-spatial isolation.

► STORYTELLING - The effects of Covid on social engagement

The story of a woman from Lucca helps to deepen these aspects, although in this case the Covid represented a stimulus for the expansion of the social commitment to other local inhabitants. The protagonist is a dog and cat owner who, in her free time, took care of the management of some feline colonies in the historic center of Lucca.

This experience of contact and care of animals has changed the life of the lady who admits that she has always benefited, in terms of well-being, from voluntary activity since she has the feeling of doing a useful and worthy thing.

During the lockdown the lady's habits changed drastically: although she was allowed to move for her voluntary activities, she preferred not to go so often to the city (even for fear of contracting the Covid disease). Due to the emergency, other local inhabitants took her place. In particular, a friend of the protagonist started visiting the feline colony on a daily basis: she found huge benefits from this activity that allowed her to move and observe animals instead of being confined in her house.

The protagonist of the story continues to take care of the colony as regards its organization and goes visiting the cats only for emergencies. She is happy with this new situation, since she can count on the support of other people and improve the management of the colony.

The role of time devoted to work changed during the Covid pandemic, especially during the lockdown periods and in particular for self-employed workers. In some cases, **time devoted to work contributed to people's well-being and resilience.**

► STORYTELLING - The role of work for people's resilience during Covid

The personal story of a woman from Lucca, who is a restorer of ancient textiles, helps understand this dynamic. Although the amount of new work decreased due to the restrictions, she tried to maintain the same working habits and hours as before. This was both to maintain a certain stability on a personal level that allowed her not to lose motivation in her work and because she felt the need to keep busy in order not to focus on what was happening.

The lady is therefore satisfied with her work also because it allowed her to maintain a commitment, even if with a more relaxed pace, constant and daily so as not to let herself be dragged along at an emotional level.

ECONOMIC SITUATION – External influencing factor 6 for Lucca

Most respondents from Lucca report satisfaction with the time and resources they have to manage personal matters (61% satisfied or more). No difference in this proportion is detected between respondents from the intervention and control group (62% vs 61%).

Despite the average per capita income is at a good level (about 26.000 euros in 2018), about a third (30%) of all respondents from Lucca reported that their financial condition is not enough or just barely sufficient to satisfy their needs. Respondents from the intervention and control group report similar levels of distress (31% vs 29%).

The local economy relies very much on the touristic flows and related services for tourists. The social restrictions to fight the Covid-19 pandemic have therefore influenced the baseline economic situation causing repercussions such as uncertainty, lack of income and feelings of fear and stress in the inhabitants.

3.4 THE BASELINE OF THE EXPECTED IMPACTS IN LUCCA

The following paragraphs present an analysis of the baseline (starting situation) regarding the selected aspects of H&W that are expected to change due to the project solutions in the intervention group compared to the control group of participants in Lucca.

The identification of the research assumptions on the expected impacts on H&W derives from the participative co-design process described in D7.1. In particular, the specific sub-dimensions and impact indicators of interest for the Lucca’s pilot were identified by partners ISIM and UREAD with the involvement of local research partner UNIPI during the co-design phase on the basis of the literature review on one hand and on the consultation of project partners, local inhabitants and representatives of local NGOs on the other hand. This process allowed to establish the causal chains between the city specific solutions (grouped by typology) and the aspects of health and well-being of local target groups that are likely to be affected by these solutions. The identification of these causal chains is based on the validated method of the Theory Based Evaluation (Weiss, 2007) as better described in D7.1.

The following table shows the causal links between Lucca’s solutions and the selected aspects of H&W that should be improved by the IN-HABIT project (expected impacts). These aspects cover all the IN-HABIT H&W dimensions: social well-being, spatial and environmental well-being, subjective well-being, economic well-being and healthy lifestyles. Each aspect is measured through one or more Impact Indicator on H&W among those selected in T7.1 and described in D7.1.

♦ **Table n.16** – Causal links between project solutions and expected impacts on H&W in Lucca

VIS CATEGORY A NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS IN PUBLIC SPACES	
SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>A1 Renovation of under-used green areas and therapy gardens</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time spent in nature (<i>Richardson, M., Passmore, H. A., Lumber, R., Thomas, R., & Hunt, A. - 2021</i>) • Environmental and Social connection (<i>Uhlmann, K., Lin, B. B., & Ross, H. - 2018</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one’s surrounding – living environment
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety in green areas • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Satisfaction with green areas devoted to pets • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with sports facilities • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Benefits from urban nature
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY B
SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND SPORTS INFRASTRUCTURES IN PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>B1 Sports and leisure facilities and infrastructures for both people and animals (Animal lines)</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing <i>(Scully, D., Kremer, J., Meade, M. M., Graham, R., & Dudgeon, K. - 1998)</i>
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion • Equal access to pet's care services
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety in green areas • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Satisfaction with green areas devoted to pets • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with sports facilities • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Benefits from human-animal bonds • Benefits from urban nature • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY C
MOBILITY AND LIGHTING SOLUTIONS FOR PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>C1 Renovation of green corridors with new mobility and lighting solutions</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved perceptions of safety <i>(Peña-García, A., Hurtado, A., & Aguilar-Luzón, M. C. - 2016)</i> <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety at night • Sense of safety in green areas • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Satisfaction with green areas devoted to pets • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

VIS CATEGORY D
TRAINING AND SUPPORT FOR SKILLS AND BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>D1 Business/startup support services</p>	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation

VIS CATEGORY E
HEALTHY LIFESTYLES WORKSHOPS, INITIATIVES AND EVENTS

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>E1 Animal assisted interventions in public spaces, schools and other public services</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links between increased human animal relationships, health and wellbeing (<i>Wells, D. L. - 2019</i>) • Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing (<i>Scully, D., Kremer, J., Meade, M. M., Graham, R., & Dudgeon, K. - 1998</i>)
<p>E2 Hum-animal entertainment and sports events</p>	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Social network support • Institutional support • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion • Equal access to pet's care services • Social engagement
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Satisfaction with green areas devoted to pets • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Benefits from human-animal bonds • Benefits from urban nature • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY G
DIGITAL SERVICES TO BOOST HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>G1 Digital games and services through the INHABIT-APP supporting human-animal entertainment, sports and socialization</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impacts of play (<i>Gleave, J., & Cole-Hamilton, I. - 2012</i>) • Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing • Links between increased human animal relationships, health and wellbeing
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic Isolation • Sense of inclusion • Sense of inclusion • Equal access to pet's care services • Equal access to culture and leisure
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources • Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Benefits from human-animal bonds • Benefits from urban nature • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

3.4.1 THE BASELINE OF SOCIAL WELL-BEING IN LUCCA

SOCIAL COHESION - THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The qualitative study revealed a general **dissatisfaction with the personal relationships** in the neighbourhood. People participating in the focus group, for instance, present the local people as “closed” and complain about the difficulty of establishing lasting relationships that go beyond the narrow circle of friends. The image of the dynamics of social relations that emerges from the focus group is that of fragmentation into small closed groups, difficult to integrate with each other.

“There are relationships that are separated entities, also linked to the quality of communication. It’s a characteristic of Lucca to be very closed. As soon as you leave Lucca the mentalities change. The relationship to watertight compartments is something that I live. It is a negative point that can be improved”.

This data has been confirmed by the city survey: just less than half of respondents from Lucca are satisfied of their relationship with people living in their neighbourhood (46%). The percentage of satisfied respondents is not different in the intervention and in the control group (47% satisfied vs 45%).

On the other hand, due to the social restrictions and domestic isolation imposed by the Covid pandemic in the last year, people who participated in the baseline study report a new and greater awareness regarding the benefits from face to face/in person social relationships, especially in the field of work, free time and leisure.

► STORYTELLING - The impact of covid on the perceived benefits from personal relationships

The story of a woman, who is a social worker from Lucca, gives some insights in this sense.

The lady claims to have personally suffered a lot the lockdown phase due to the fact of having to renounce to be personally present in the community, an aspect that she believes to be fundamental for her and for her work (participatory paths) which if carried out remotely never manages to return the gratification and the alchemy that is created in interaction and group work.

In the summer, her group managed to meet in person and enthusiastically explains how to find oneself again doing things that cannot be replaced in any other way has had a completely different meaning.

Currently the lady claims to have returned to a situation that gratifies her and motivates her much more in doing her job.

Secondly, the baseline study shows a general low level of both **social network and institutional support** perceived by target inhabitants. In fact, less than a quarter of respondents agree that there are associations, neighbourhood committees and citizen groups that can help in case of need (21%). This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than in the control group (25% vs 17%) but the association is not statistically significant.

A minority of respondents interviewed in Lucca agree that there are many public care services that can offer help in case of need (26%). Respondent from the intervention area agree more than respondents from the control group (35% vs 18%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate size.

However, according to the participants to the qualitative study, the Covid pandemic has strengthened both social network and institutional support in the intervention area. The same personal story helps understanding how the social services and the volunteering sector in Lucca changed thanks to the Covid emergency, bringing new intersectoral cooperation, innovations and public-private partnerships.

► STORYTELLING - The impact of Covid on social network and institutional support

The office where the lady works was involved, at that time, in the planning of food assistance for families: from the interception of situations of greatest difficulty to practical support through the dissemination of shopping vouchers, which have been realized through the involvement of local shops. This involvement had the specific purpose, through the help of third sector associations, of supporting the local commercial fabric by trying to match families and neighborhood shops also by encouraging practices such as “suspended food shopping” and donations, which have been very well received by the productive sector.

This public-private alliance led to higher social network and institutional support and capacity of the public services to detect and respond to new and emerging social needs.

► STORYTELLING - The impact of Covid on social cohesion

According to the lady, the pandemic led to a generalized impoverishment, which has also affected people who normally have a safe economic situation, and led to greater levels of suffering from all points of view, including the emotional point of view of young people and school-age children. The work on the area was therefore very important to bring out these new situations through the important role of volunteers and the third sector who moved around the area and acted as sentinel, reporting the new needs that were being created to the social services.

PERCEPTION OF SECURITY - THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The qualitative study detected a general **perception of safety in relation to green areas and public spaces**, although some participants remarked that the problem of safety affects mainly women moving at night to reach the city center.

“I can say that Lucca has changed a lot since I was a child. Lucca has improved considerably. When I was a child, safety wasn't taken for granted, kids had to go with their parents to school”.

“As for women, the goal is to keep Lucca a safe city, where a woman can go downtown at midnight to meet a friend”. But a woman also argued that: “It's a matter of general perception, there are people who feel that the city is not safe, I feel safe to walk on the walls at night, there are others of my age who maybe don't”.

This result has been confirmed by the city survey: more than half of respondents in Lucca consider walking alone after dark to be safe (60%). No difference in this percentage is found between respondents from the intervention and the control group (60% v 59%). Most respondents from Lucca consider walking alone in public green areas to be safe (80%). This percentage is not different in among respondents from the intervention and control group (81% vs 78%).

The **perception of crime and vandalism** in the living area has been investigated through the city survey by asking whether people feel safe leaving a vehicle (bike, car) unattended in their neighbourhood and how often they observe vandalic incidents. About half of respondents from Lucca consider leaving a vehicle unattended to be safe (48%). Less respondents from the intervention area consider it safe than respondents from the control group (45% vs 51%), but the difference is not statistically significant. Less than half of respondents (38%) from Lucca agree that it often happens to them observing vandalic damages to urban furnishings and private properties. This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than among respondents from the control group (49% vs 29%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate size.

— Chart n.11 – Perception of security in Lucca

SOCIAL INCLUSION - THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The baseline study detected the current level of social inclusion of both intervention and control groups in Lucca by investigating a set of impact indicators (the full list is available in Annex 4).

Regarding **social relations in public spaces**, about half of respondents from Lucca report getting together with friends or relatives in a public space once a month or more (54%). This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than among respondents from the control group (60% vs 49%). The association is almost significant and of small size.

Regarding the **domestic isolation**, the contact with other in public spaces and the **freedom of personal contact**, in addition to the physiological isolation caused by the lock down, the qualitative baseline study detected again a different situation between old city center and suburbs.

Participants argued that, within a general situation of loss of personal contacts due to the Covid, people living in the city center have more opportunities for social engagement and a greater habit of meeting people in public spaces; on the other hand, people living in the suburbs suffer most from domestic isolation and lack of community centers, associations and opportunities for volunteering.

“There are differences between the old town and the suburbs in associationism, everyone is at its own home, villages are less community than in the past. On the contrary the historical city center still offers opportunities for socializing and being with others”.

For elderly people the domestic isolation and the lack of contact with other in public spaces is quite common and this condition has been worsened by the Covid pandemic.

► STORYTELLING - The role of pets to combat isolation during Covid

The story of a man from Lucca of about seventy years gives some insights in this respect:

He does not usually go out much with his acquaintances, consequently domestic isolation during the lockdown period did not represent a big change for him. However, thanks to the presence of the dog and the farm he owns, he could, with the appropriate attention, go out quite regularly.

The presence of pets represents a compensation for the absence of personal relationships and contributes to the individual well-being of elderly and persons living alone in general.

The seventy year old man from Lucca argues that the presence of his dog represented a great help during the lockdown period. In general, he finds great benefit from the dog's company, since his son lives elsewhere, and his wife is often out.

With respect to the **sense of inclusion**, over half of respondents in Lucca report that feeling a sense of community with other people in their neighbourhood is important (56%). The percentage reporting this to be important is 53% among respondents from the intervention group and 59% among respondents from the control group. The association is not statistically significant. Just less than half of respondents from Lucca (45%) report talking informally with neighbors about a community problem. The percentage is about the same among respondents from the intervention and control group (46% vs 44%).

Another aspect detected by the baseline study was the current level of social and civic engagement. Regarding **civic engagement**, the baseline survey shows that 16% of respondents from Lucca report engaging in democratic life through committees and councils once a month or more. This percentage is 13% among respondents from the intervention area and 19% among respondents from the control group. The association is not statistically significant.

Regarding **social engagement**, in particular, the results of the survey show that a minority of respondents from Lucca report engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activities once a month or more (25%). The percentage is about the same among respondents from the intervention and control group (26% vs 23%).

— Chart n.12 – Socio-cultural engagement and relations in public spaces: how often do people engage in the following activities in Lucca

Less than once a month Once a month or more

However, the participants to the qualitative show a good level of **satisfaction with their level of involvement in their local community life** and **change making attitude**, particularly in relation to the improvement of the spaces (accessibility of green areas), the birth/improvement of services for pets (feline colonies, pet sitting services) as well as the possibility to improve the organization and communication of socio-cultural services thanks to the digital technologies and to the cooperation with local institutions.

Moreover, participants to the qualitative study report that the local context is characterized by a good number of NGOs, civic committees, cultural associations and civic consultation bodies established by the Municipality of Lucca, which encourage democratic participation of local organized groups.

“The picture is very remarkable, there are many associations that are being born, even if then, in the long term,

the life of these associations is very difficult”. “As for associationism, I think that in other cities there isn’t associationism as there is here (referring to the number of associations and their organizations). The associationism in Lucca is in a good state, in my opinion”. “There is also great inclusion among associations, we manage to work together and to break the tendency to work alone”.

However, these positive results of the qualitative study might be in part influenced by the selection of the participants to the focus group and storytelling in Lucca, who were active members of the local IN-HUB, the core group of associations and organizations active for the co-design and the co-management of the project’s solutions.

EQUALITY IN THE ACCESS TO PET'S SERVICES, CULTURE AND LEISURE THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The proposed baseline study has also investigated the current level of **equality in the access to cultural and leisure opportunities**, since they are two key components of IHW that are expected to change thanks to the VIS in Lucca. According to the participants to the focus group, the local cultural offer is substantial but it is not easily accessible by local inhabitants, especially by young people, persons with disability and persons living outside the old city center, who have mobility obstacles.

“There is a problem of connectivity and full participation in the daily life of people who have specific needs”. According to the participants to the focus group, accessibility and inclusiveness of cultural and leisure opportunities is limited by traffic, inadequate public transport services, inadequate pavements but also lack of specific activities and services for young people and persons with disabilities: “I have a disabled person in the family, who is a young worker and has many needs, the paved streets are so uneven that make impossible taking a walk in the historic center”.

“I see great escape of youth from Lucca, which is then tagged as an old town”. “In Lucca you can live well as an adult, as for young people I believe that there are many events, but there are no alternative aggregation points, spaces that can be left in the hands of youths who can self-manage them. Now young people meet at the pub and drink, it would take a different way to experience the city”.

Other limitations regarding the access to culture that emerged from the focus group relate to the quality and communication of the events: participants think that the available events are mainly conceived for tourists and/or not sufficiently communicated.

“Lucca is a beautiful, warm city, but sometimes I felt it a bit empty or built for tourists”.

“There is no communication of events. There are some whatsapp groups that run communications among them, but this is not enough. Sometimes there are very important events, with prominent speakers, but with an audience of 16 people because the event was not advertised adequately”.

SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING - THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The baseline study detected the current level of spatial well-being of both intervention and control groups in Lucca by investigating a set of impact indicators.

The first aspect regards the perceived **accessibility of local resources**.

According to respondents in Lucca, some local resources are easier to access than others. In addition, some differences can be detected between respondents from the intervention and the control group.

Resources marking a distinction between respondents from the intervention and control group are described as follows:

- 82% consider moving on foot easy (89% intervention vs 77% control)
- 72% consider finding playgrounds for children easy (82% intervention vs 64% control)
- 49% consider participating in cultural events easy (65% intervention vs 36% control)
- 45% consider finding adequate social and health assistance easy (54% intervention vs 38% control)

Resources with no detectable difference between intervention and control group:

- 80% consider finding healthy food easy (86% intervention vs 76% control)
- 79% consider moving by bike easy (82% intervention vs 77% control)
- 75% consider finding a green space to do sports easy (79% intervention vs 72% control)
- 70% consider finding safe, accessible, and pleasant green areas to be easy (75% intervention vs 66% control)
- 41% consider finding help from other easy (42% intervention vs 40% control).

— Chart n.13 – Accessibility of local resources in Lucca: how easy is to find the following resources in the neighbourhood

The second aspect of spacial well-being investigated by the baseline study is the satisfaction with urban green areas and with green areas devoted to pets in particular. Regarding **satisfaction with urban green areas**, the survey showed that they are frequented and appreciated by the majority of the respondents from both intervention and control group, although some characteristics of the areas are more appreciated than others.

More specifically, regarding satisfaction about the inclusiveness and accessibility of the urban green areas:

- 83% agree that urban green areas where they spend the majority of their free time are frequented by people of all ages (88% intervention vs 78% control)
- 81% agree that they are frequented by people of all ethnicities (91% intervention vs 72% control)
- 60% agree that they are accessible for persons with disabilities (65% intervention vs 56% control)

Regarding satisfaction about the beauty and state of maintenance:

- 73% agree that they are a pleasant and beautiful place to spend their free time (78% intervention vs 69% control)
- 60% agree that they are well maintained (60% intervention vs 60% control).
- Additionally, a minority of respondents (21%) report that they do not frequent any public green area (12% intervention vs 28% control).

— Chart n.14 – Satisfaction with urban green areas in Lucca

The participants of the qualitative study also confirm this general satisfaction about the urban green areas of intervention. In particular, the circular walls and their parks are considered as “the green vital point that allow people to socialise and feel in a community”.

They report there is some room for improvement in terms of equipment and maintenance: “The "Parco Fluviale" is a very beautiful place and in recent years has been improved, however it lacks an equipment that would make it a flagship of the city: let's improve and equip this space and optimise and make more accessible green spaces”.

Regarding the **satisfaction with green areas devoted to pets**, the situation is not as positive: about half of respondents from Lucca consider finding green areas devoted to dogs and other animals easy (53%). The percentage is similar among respondents from the intervention and the control group (56% vs 50%).

However, only 34% of respondents find that the green areas are adequate and well equipped for dogs. Respondents from the intervention area agree more than respondents from the control group (40 vs 30%), but the association is not statistically significant.

The dissatisfaction with green areas devoted to pets in terms of space, maintenance and equipment was also confirmed by the participants to the qualitative study:

“I'm lucky because I live near the forest, and I have a lot of space to take my dog for a walk. Currently there aren't adequate spaces”.

“In my opinion there is a serious lack of services by the municipality of Lucca concerning animals, in particular dogs. There isn't a real dog park neither in the old town nor in general. Those in San Vito and Sant'Anna are small handkerchiefs of land without maintenance. everything is very dirty, especially on the walls, so that I can't take there the dogs because they are attracted by food residues (unfortunately happened to me that one of my dogs even ingested drug residues, so it was sick for a few days)”.

“I can unleash it in very few places, but I feel a lot the lack of space. I've to search for forest areas or areas where we can stay alone”.

Regarding their attachment and **sense of belonging to the neighbourhood** they live in, respondents from the intervention area are generally more positive than those in the control group:

- 78% agree that their neighbourhood is attractive for tourists (86% intervention vs 72% control)
- 35% agree that the image of the neighbourhood where they live has improved in the past two years (34% intervention vs 35% control)
- 33% agree that no one is left alone (38% intervention vs 29% control)

The qualitative study also confirmed a good sense of belonging and a general good perception of the neighbourhood by the participants (all of them belonging to the intervention group).

The common feeling is that the city has a good image and reputation, especially for tourists, and that it has improved in terms of greenery, beauty and waste management. “I feel like entering a house, because living there is fine, is easily enjoyable and there are accessible services”.

“The urban redevelopment has changed completely the perception because not only it is more beautiful, cleaner but above all it is much more surrounded by greenery (athletic fields, children's park...)”.

However, there is a gap between the external image of the city (how it appears to tourists) and the internal image perceived by local inhabitants: “There is definitely a different perception between residents and tourists: the tourists like the city very much that looks to them like a jewel, but citizens notice the flaws instead”.

3.4.2 THE BASELINE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLES IN LUCCA

The baseline study also investigated those aspects of the dimension “healthy lifestyles” that are supposed to improve thanks to the IN-HABIT solutions in Lucca, in particular the sports practice and satisfaction related to sports; the cultural participation and culture-related well-being; the perceived quality of one's free time.

SPORTS PRACTICE - THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

Within the dimension of “healthy lifestyles” the baseline survey detected the current level of sports practice in public green areas of both intervention and control groups in Lucca.

Only 14% of respondents from Lucca reported using the public green areas of their neighbourhood to do sports once a week or more. This percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention area than among respondents from the control group (21% vs 9%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate size.

CULTURAL PARTICIPATION AND CULTURE-RELATED WELL-BEING THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

Another aspects of “healthy lifestyle” that is supposed to change due to the project’s solutions in Lucca is the cultural participation and culture-related well-being.

Regarding **cultural participation** and **cultural engagement**, the study shows a baseline situation which is influenced by the pandemic since data were collected at the end of Summer 2021 after the third Covid wave, when social and cultural life had just resumed after a period of closure and crisis.

Results from the survey show that only 4% of respondents from Lucca reported **attending cultural activities organised in public green spaces of their neighbourhood** once a week or more. No difference was detected between respondents from the intervention and control group.

According to the participants to the qualitative study, the Covid pandemic produced a general impoverishment of the cultural business sector, with a decrease of both offer and participation of the public due to social restrictions and fear of interpersonal contact.

— Chart n.15 – Frequency of practice of sports and culture in public green spaces of the neighbourhood in Lucca

On the other hand, the pandemic has led to some positive changes, good practices and innovations related to the management of cultural and leisure services in Lucca that could be replicated and further developed in the future. In particular, the qualitative study revealed a good level of offer and participation to cultural and leisure activities in outdoor public spaces, although not comparable with the large numbers of pre-pandemic events.

► STORYTELLING - The effects of Covid on cultural participation and engagement

The testimony of a woman from Lucca who is active in the organization and management of social and cultural events, helps understanding this positive change, that are characterized by: (i) a higher and different use of public spaces for culture and leisure; (ii) a better dissemination and capillarity of the events in the city territory; (iii) the birth of new cultural formats.

The lady tells us that, thanks also to the good weather, it was possible to rearrange the green spaces for events, concerts, etc. and that new forms of entertainment have been born, organized in such a way as to be less concentrated in one place but more “parceled” on the territory, in order to respect the general rules guaranteeing the personal distance. The lady then states that new cultural formats of theater have also been born in the hamlets as well as neighborhood theaters, theaters in the districts (both in the municipality of Lucca and in that of Capannori) and defines these new realities as positive side effects within the pandemic situation of serious general impoverishment. In addition to this aspect, economic activities have also restarted and have required a different use of public spaces. In the opinion of the lady, this represented an improvement that favored the return to aggregation in places where it had been impossible for a long time.

FREE TIME AND LEISURE - THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The baseline study detected the current use of free time of both intervention and control groups in Lucca by investigating a set of impact indicators.

Data on this sub-dimension of IHW show the influence of this post-pandemic period on the baseline situation. Regarding their daily routine, 36% of respondents from Lucca reported spending one hour or more playing, relaxing, or doing sport in public green areas. Respondents from the intervention group were more likely report spending one hour or more a day on this activity (52% intervention vs 23% control). The association is statistically significant and of medium size.

A minority of respondents from Lucca reported spending at least one hour a day in social and recreational public spaces (21%). Respondents from the intervention area report spending more time there than respondents from the control group (25% one h or more vs 18%), but the association is not statistically significant.

Regarding the perception of benefits from leisure, participants to the qualitative study show a good level of awareness of the **benefits from social and recreational public spaces**, as well as **from the contact with nature**. Participants place a lot of value on the time they spend playing, relaxing, doing sports or being with friends in public spaces, as they are regaining possession of these activities and opportunities after the restrictions due to Covid.

Pets owner, in particular, show a high level of **satisfaction with their free time spent with pets** and a good level of awareness of the **benefits from hum-animal bonds**, also thanks to the experience of domestic isolation with pets. The same awareness is not as present among those who do not own a pet/deal with pets.

► STORYTELLING - Effects of Covid on perceived benefits from human-animal bonds

The story of a young woman, who is a student who usually spends her free time in the intervention areas in Lucca, helps understanding the role of Covid in this respect.

The student declares to have been negatively affected by the social isolation due to the pandemic, but having a cat helped her through this period.

During the lockdown, having to stay at home, she had the chance to be more involved in the life of her cat (whose care, before, was entrusted mainly to her family). The girl has been able to interact more with her animal and, moreover, claims to have sought her often for support.

The protagonist believes that hanging out with friends and having the opportunity to go for a walk in the green areas of Lucca has always contributed a lot to her psycho-physical well-being, especially comparing this situation with that of lock down. During the lockdown social relationships decreased and the chance to freely go out got lost. The protagonist, who lives in a town far from Lucca, could not go there and, therefore, every social life activity, as well as the possibility to have fun and to relax in the green areas, was impossible for her.

Regarding the **perceived quality of free time in public spaces**, the qualitative study highlights some negative aspects/room for improvement that relate to the quality of free time for young people.

This aspect is linked to the **need of healthy leisure** as well as with the awareness about healthy habits that has been detected also in the cases of Nitra and Cordoba.

Participants to the focus group in Lucca reported a general perception of dissatisfaction regarding the way young people spend their free time and the practice of unhealthy behaviors like the use of alcoholic.

“In Lucca you can live well as an adult, as for young people I believe that there are many events, but there are no alternative aggregation points, spaces that can be left in the hands of youths who can self-manage them. Now young people meet at the pub and drink, it would take a different way to experience the city”.

“As far as the inclusion of young people is concerned, the problem is not the number of events but the quality of these. There’s the brewer but then there’s nothing else, I wouldn’t want alcohol to be the only way to live the sociability”.

3.4.3 THE BASELINE OF ECONOMIC WELL-BEING IN LUCCA

EMPLOYMENT, SKILLS AND SATISFACTION WITH ONE'S SURROUNDINGS THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

The baseline of economic well-being in Lucca focused in particular on employability and satisfaction of one’s living environment, since these aspects have been considered as subjected to change due to the IN-HABIT solutions at city level.

According to the opinion of the participants in the qualitative study, within highly specialised work sectors which are not strictly dependent on tourist flows or connected to social and recreational activities, Covid effects were less negative even for women. For this type of work, participants reported a good level of satisfaction with the **opportunities offered by the job market at city level** and a general **satisfaction with ones’ living environment**.

► STORYTELLING - The effects of Covid on local economy

The story of a woman who works in the center of Lucca as a restorer of antique textile gives some insights in this respect. She is a self-employed worker whose area of expertise is particular and carried out by a few people. Private customers, including collectors, continued to call the restorer even during the lockdown period, although, of course, the amount of new work was greatly reduced. Now (Autumn 2021) the work of the lady has more or less returned to normality and the activity has been spread at full speed. According to the lady, for her field of work, the post Covid situation could be advantageous: there will probably be an enrichment of a cut of the population that will have more chance to accumulate and buy goods at reduced prices that will then need restoration and maintenance in the various sectors.

3.4.4 GDEI ANALYSIS OF THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

This section gives an overview of the key findings regarding the baseline situation of socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles of the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion in Lucca. This analysis is mainly based on data from the baseline survey, where associations between key impact indicators and membership to city target groups have been explored with the use of statistical tests and standardised effect sizes (for more detail see section II.c of the Appendix). The GDEI analysis of the baseline should be interpreted with caution though, as the number of observations in some of the target groups can be too modest to be reliable. For the very same reason the analysis by target group could be performed at city-level and not at control/intervention group level, where the number of observations per cell would be even smaller.

► Women

The analysis of the interviews conducted for the baseline survey in Lucca revealed gender differences on key impact indicators in the subdimensions perception of security, spatial wellbeing, and social inclusion.

Women were found to be more likely than men:

- to consider walking alone after dark not safe (51% not safe vs 13%)
- to find moving by bike in their neighbourhood not easy (22% vs 8%)

Women were instead found to be less likely than men:

- to engage in community problem solving (10% once a month or more vs 33%)
- to engage in democratic life at city level (14% once a month or more vs 28%)

Moreover findings from the qualitative study show that:

- Women participating in the baseline study show in general a good level of satisfaction with their level of social engagement and free time use, they are engaged in pets' care, in the care of public spaces and in the organization and management of social and cultural services and volunteering. They perceive great benefits from the hum-animal relationships as well as from the contact with nature and the use of public spaces for socialization, also due to the post-pandemic effects.
- Working women also appear satisfied about their job situation but suffered the domestic isolation during the lock down. They appreciate the role of work and social relationships (especially in person face to face relationships) for their well-being and post pandemic resilience.
- Although the perceived sense of safety in the city is in general good, the study revealed the issue of safety for women when moving at night to the old city center.

► Elderly and young people

The interviews conducted for the baseline in Lucca revealed differences by age in key impact indicators. Interesting differences were found in the dimensions of sports practice, perception of security, spatial wellbeing, and social inclusion.

Compared to mature adults (35-65yo), young persons (18-34) were found to be:

- less likely to use public green areas in their neighbourhoods to practice sports (8% once a week or more vs 21%)
- less likely to say that the air of their neighbourhood is unbreathable (12% agree vs 27%)
- less likely to consider feeling a sense of community with other people in their neighbourhood something important to them (39% important vs 63%)
- less likely to informally talk with neighbors about community problems (31% once a month or more vs 46%)
- more likely to get together with friends or relatives in a public space (74% once a month or more vs 48%).

Elderly respondents (65+), compared to mature adults (35-65yo), were found to be:

- less likely to use public green areas to practice sports (3% once a month or more vs 21%)
- more likely to find moving on foot in the neighbourhood easy (97% easy vs 81%)
- more likely to informally talk with neighbors about a community problem (63% once a month or more vs 46%).

In addition to this, according to the participants to the qualitative study:

- elderly people experience domestic isolation and mobility obstacles in the access to the available resources, especially social and cultural activities, that are mainly located in the old city center. The most penalized are the inhabitants of rural and peripheral areas, who suffered from a twofold condition of isolation: domestic isolation and socio-spatial isolation.
- young people do not find adequate and healthy opportunities for leisure since the city lacks good quality cultural events for youth and spaces for socialization.

► LGBTQI+ people

Out of 207 interviews collected in Lucca, only 14 defined themselves as LGBTQI+. While the number reached is too small to detect differences reliably, some tentative differences could be found in the sub-dimensions of sports practice and special wellbeing.

Compared to heterosexuals, respondents identifying as LGBTQ+ were found:

- more likely to use public green areas for sports frequently (33% once a week or more vs 14%)
- more likely to consider finding safe, accessible, and pleasant green areas easy (80% east vs 72%)
- more likely to consider finding green areas for dogs and other animals easy (71% easy vs 55%).

► Students

Differences based on employment conditions were detected on key impact indicators in the sub-dimension of leisure/free time and social inclusion.

More specifically:

- students were found to be more likely than people in employment to play, relax, or do sports in public green areas (47% one h or more a day vs 31%)
- students were found less likely than people in employment to informally talk with neighbors about community problems (32% once a month or more vs 41%)
- retirees and people not in the labour force were found to be more likely than people in employment to informally talk with neighbors about community problems (62% once a month or more vs 41%).

► Persons with disabilities

Regarding the quantitative study, only 4 respondents reported having a form of disability, therefore results from the survey are not meaningful.

According to the participants to the qualitative study, persons with disability suffer from domestic isolation and lack of accessibility and inclusiveness of urban spaces and cultural events.

• Ethnic minorities

According to the participants to the qualitative study, ethnic minorities such as non-EU migrants face problems of social inclusion and discrimination in the access to house. There is no specific issue regarding discrimination towards Roma people, although they suffer dissatisfaction with personal relationships with the “native” inhabitants who are described as closed to diversity.

Regarding the quantitative study, only 6 respondents reported being member of an ethnic minority, therefore results from the survey are not meaningful. Persons living alone

Out of 207 interviews collected in Lucca, only 37 respondents reported living alone. Possible differences were detected on key impact indicators of the sub-dimensions of sports practice, leisure/free time, and social inclusion.

People living alone, compared to people living with others, were found to be:

- more likely to use public green areas of their neighbourhood to do sports (29% once a week or more vs 11%)
- more likely to spend time relaxing or doing sport in public green areas (50% one hour a day or more vs 34%)
- less likely to volunteer to take care of public spaces and green areas (5% once a month or more vs 17%).

• Religious minorities

Out of 207 interviews collected in Lucca, only 20 respondents reported being affiliated with a non-Christian religion. Possible differences were detected in key impact indicators from the sub-dimensions of social cohesion, spatial wellbeing, perception of security, and social inclusion.

Respondents from minority religions were found:

- less likely than Christians to concur that no one is left alone in their neighbourhood (15% agree vs 40%)
- less likely than Christians to think that there are many associations and groups that can help them in their neighbourhood (5% agree vs 30%)
- less likely than Christian to trust the capacity of local authorities to maintain security in their neighbourhood (21% agree vs 38%)
- less likely to think that the neighbourhood where they live has improved in the past two years (15% agree vs 41%)
- less likely than Christians to consider leaving a vehicle unattended safe (25% safe vs 56%)
- less likely than Christians to engage in cultural and voluntary activities in their neighbourhood (21% once a month or more vs 35%).

Intervention Group — People living in the old city center or frequenting one of the areas listed in Q10.4 of the survey

Control Group — The rest of the inhabitants of Lucca

> SOCIAL WELL-BEING

> EQUALITY AND DISCRIMINATION

• The local **cultural offer is substantial but it is not easily accessible** by local inhabitants, especially by young people, persons with disability and persons living outside the old city center, who have mobility obstacles.

• Participants from the intervention group think that the local society is welcoming in terms of reception measures and intercultural initiatives for migrants but **prejudices and discrimination in society exist** especially against non EU citizens, who face serious difficulties in the access to house.

> PERCEPTION OF SECURITY

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

- Participants from the intervention group have more **opportunities for social engagement** and a greater habit of meeting people in public spaces while people living in the suburbs suffer most from domestic isolation and lack of community centers, associations and opportunities for volunteering.
- Participants from the intervention group experience a **loss of freedom of personal contacts and increased domestic isolation due to Covid 19**.
- The presence of **pets represents a compensation for the loss of personal relationships**.

> SOCIAL COHESION

- Participants from the intervention group experience a moderate level of satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood. However, they report **lower levels of both social network and institutional support**.

> SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF RESOURCES IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD

participants from the intervention group **appreciate the accessibility of local resources**, particularly healthy food and green areas.

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD AND URBAN GREEN AREAS

Participants from the intervention group are **satisfied with the quality of urban green areas** in their neighbourhood, but not much with those devoted to pets.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

Participants from the intervention group report dissatisfaction regarding the way young people spend their free time and the practice of **unhealthy behaviors** like the use of alcoholic.

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

People from the intervention group report a good level of **awareness of the benefits from social and recreational public spaces**, as well as from the contact with nature. However, they perceive a general impoverishment of the cultural business sector, with a **decrease of both cultural participation and engagement due to the Covid effects**.

Pets owners show a high level of satisfaction with their free time spent with pets and a good level of awareness of the benefits from human-animal bonds.

> SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

People from the intervention and control groups experience **comparable levels of psychological well-being and mental distress.**

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

Within highly specialised work sectors, which are not strictly dependent on tourist flows or connected to social and recreational activities, participants reported a **good level of satisfaction with the opportunities offered by the job market** at city level and a general satisfaction with ones' living environment. However, the Intervention Group also report uncertainty, **lower income and fear/stress due to the employment situation after Covid 19.**

4. NITRA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

4. NITRA

4.1 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE BASELINE STUDY IN NITRA

The specific objective of the baseline study in Nitra is to identify the starting health and well-being condition of the local intervention group and make a comparison with the starting condition of a control group in the city regarding the following aspects of H&W:

◆ **Table n.17** – Aspects of H&W involved in the baseline study of Nitra

Dimension	Sub-dimension
Social well-being	Social inclusion
	Social cohesion
	Discrimination
	Equality in the access to culture and leisure
Spatial and environmental well-being	Perception of security
	Accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood
	Perception of noise and air pollution
	Satisfaction with the neighbourhood and urban green areas
Healthy lifestyles	Perceived physical health
	Eating habits
	Sports practice
	Free time and leisure
	Free time and leisure
Economic well-being	Financial situation
	Employment
	Job and skills satisfaction
	Satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment
Subjective well-being	Psychological well-being,
	Mental distress
	Life satisfaction

The project impacts will be assessed by comparing the average difference over time among respondents from the intervention group to the average difference among respondents in the control group. Both intervention and control groups were identified by local research partner SUA with the aim of isolating as much as possible the direct beneficiaries of the project solutions. The intervention group is composed by adults (18+) residents of Nitra who live or who attend in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week) the intervention areas, while the control group is composed by adults residents of Nitra who do not live nor attend such areas.

◆ **Table n.18** – The intervention and control groups in Nitra

City	
Nitra	Intervention Group (IG) Adults (18+) residents of Nitra who live in Dražovce neighbourhood OR who attend for at least 4 hours a week one of the areas showed in the map in Q10 of the baseline survey
	Control Group (CG) Adults (18+) residents of Nitra who do not live in Dražovce neighbourhood AND who do not attend for at least 4 hours a week any of the areas showed in the map in Q10 of the baseline survey

Within each group, the proposed baseline study will assess the initial condition of IHW of the following specific target groups, among those identified in task 7.1:

◆ **Table n.19** – Nitra’s specific target groups involved in the baseline study

Specific Target Groups in Nitra
Young students aged 18 – 30
Persons with disabilities
Women
LGBTQI+ People
Elderly aged 65+
Persons living alone
Ethnic minorities
Migrants
Religious minorities

4.2 THE BASELINE STUDY IN NITRA – KEY FEATURES

◆ **Table n.20** – Key features of the baseline study in Nitra

1 city survey	Answers collected	351
	valid answers analysed	282
	Distribution modalities	online, computer assisted interview, paper distribution
2 focus groups	Number of participants	9
	Gender distribution	2 men / 7 women
	Selection process	direct contact upon invitation through the local observers and the members of local organizations
	Inclusion of persons at risk of discrimination and exclusion	1 elderly 2 young people 1 person with physical disability 2 migrants from Serbia
5 Stories	Number of participants	6
	Gender distribution	3 man / 2 woman/ 1 non binary
	Selection process	direct contact upon invitation through personal relationships established by the LCAs and the local observers
	Participants' profile	1 elderly woman a couple (man and woman) of migrants 1 elderly man 1 man with disability 1 young member of the LGBTQI community

4.3 THE CONTEXT OF NITRA

City of Nitra is the fifth largest city of Slovakia. It is the administrative capital of the Region and the District with the same name. As of the most recently available Census (2011) the population of Nitra counted a total of 28 thousand private households, for a total private population of 77 thousand inhabitants²⁸.

The economic base of the city is predominantly industrial and has experienced an increase of foreign immigration. Again, at the time of the 2011 Census 59% of residents in Nitra of working age were active on the labour market (i.e., employed or looking for employment). The activity rate was higher for men than for women (65% males vs 53% females). The unemployment rate was reported at 12%, very similar in both female and male residents of the city²⁹.

Before the Covid-19 pandemic (2019) the city attracted 179 thousand nights spent in tourist accommodations, about 48 thousand from residents of Slovakia and 28 thousand from non-residents³⁰.

28 Eurostat (2022). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_LIVCON. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en>

29 Eurostat (2022). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_CLMA. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en>

30 Eurostat (2022). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_CTOUTR. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/142f62f0-18e8-429c-aca2-1c171f760658?lang=en>

Foreign investments have brought wealth to the city (unemployment rate in Nitra district in 2018 was 2.26%, with net average income 13,116€), but also important challenges linked to health and wellbeing of its inhabitants.

The intervention of the IN-HABIT project focuses on the neighbourhoods that are located along the 8 kilometre-long cycle track that links the Industrial Park and Dražovce district with the main city. This area of intervention involves the residential neighbourhood Dražovce with a sizeable Roma community, industrial park Nitra North with a sizeable community of migrant workers and recreational and cultural spaces along the cyclo road and Nitra river (City Park and Hidepark) frequented by inhabitants from all neighbourhoods of the city. The district of Dražovce is in fact to a large degree disconnected from the main city, having been a separate municipality until 1975. The city is trying to solve the problems of the neighbourhood by promoting alternative modes of transport, mainly bicycle transport.

4.3.1 PSYCHO-SOCIAL DATA ON THE PERCEPTION OF HEALTH AND WELL-BEING REPORTED FROM LOCAL INHABITANTS

The psychosocial context of Nitra is characterised by the following challenges:

- increased pressure on existing facilities, congestion in the central part of the city, air pollutants, permanent noise and degradation;
- Housing and integration for migrant workers represent a great problem and while one of the solutions was to build lodging houses within the industrial park, this led to low living standards and quality of life, isolation (both geographical and socio-economic) and subsequent emergence of a number of socio-pathological behaviours.
- Negative consequences of this situation are further exacerbated by the fact that the majority of workers in the industrial park are men, who are not followed to Nitra by their families. This contributes significantly to their isolation and difficult integration into the community.
- Regarding mobility, although cycling trails are being built, alternative modes of transport are still underused by residents of Nitra and the Dražovce neighbourhood, who consider cycling to be dangerous and ineffective.

Local inhabitants consulted³¹ during the co-design activities expressed their view of well-being and health to the research partners. The risks factors that emerged from this consultation were:

- Social relations in relation to culture and public spaces (“vibrant social and community life, existence of “cultural havens”, small venues with specific atmosphere, plethora of cultural events, opportunities to meet inspiring people, ability to socialize with family and friends in public spaces without the need to “buy”)
- Social cohesion and inclusion, discrimination (“elimination of conflicts with the Roma community, feeling of involvement, tolerance and elimination of negative gender stereotypes”)
- Sense of safety (mostly female participants were putting emphasis on safety in public space)
- Healthy lifestyles and contact with nature (“opportunities to spend time in nature, physical activity and sports as a counterweight to a sedentary job and opportunities to switch off. Access to organic food, fresh fruits, vegetables, vegan food and new gastronomic experiences”. Almost half of participants stressed the importance of environment, namely: “wild nature, bird and nature observation, relaxation zones and green spaces, adequate protection of nature and clean environment, inclusion of animals in city life”)
- Having a peace in the family, good work-life balance
- Accessibility and inclusiveness of local resources for groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion. Not only architectural accessibility but also access to information and educational, cultural opportunities (language barrier for economic migrants, segregation of Roma schools).

4.3.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXTERNAL FACTORS AND THE LIFESTYLE OF THE TARGET COMMUNITIES

Within this general context, some specific aspects of health and well-being have been measured and analysed in the baseline study as possible external factors that might influence the short to medium term impact of the IN-HABIT project in Nitra. On one hand, the following analysis presents the baseline level of some environmental factors like equality and discrimination in society, the economic situation and the Covid 19 pandemic. On the other hand we have analysed some subjective factors like perceived physical health, physical activity and eating

³¹ For more detail on the methods for local inhabitants' consultation, number and types of persons involved please refer to the next paragraph on co-design of IHW indicators

habits, time devoted to family, leisure and pets care. These aspects of people lifestyles are measured through context indicators and help understand and reconstruct the lifestyle of the local communities and target groups to better assess the possible external factors that might have an influence on the project's expected impacts.

The impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on the lifestyles of the local communities is further analysed in a dedicated section (section 6), that also presents a comparative analysis across the four cities on this aspect.

EQUALITY – External influencing factor 1 for Nitra

The first influencing factor that was investigated by the baseline study in Nitra is equality in society.

Regarding the **sense of being treated equally**, participants in the baseline study revealed a sense of inequality based on ethnicity and age. In particular young people and immigrants feel to be treated with less courtesy and respect than other groups. For example, a working immigrant who participated in the focus group said that: "There are different rules for me, I have a working, temporary stay for a year and I can't get to anything.[...] Everything went well in Prague, they are ready for it. There are many foreigners, they are ready. [...] But it's not even worth the money here [...] the money I carry isn't the same as the money of someone who has a permanent residence"³².

A young participant reported that: "Young people are not welcomed here from my point of view. Others feel that we have nothing to tell them. [...] Young people here do not even want to get involved, because no one thinks they have anything suitable, interesting to contribute. So, if there were more interesting projects, more interesting events for young people, it would be nice".

Another aspect of equality that was investigated by the baseline study was the equal access to digital services. In this respect, an overwhelming majority of respondents from Nitra report having **access to internet from home** (96%). Respondents from the intervention area are less likely to report access to internet from home than respondents from the control group (93% vs 99%). The difference is statistically significant³³.

PERCEIVED DISCRIMINATION (PERSONAL CONDITION) – External influencing factor 2 for Nitra

Another aspect of the local context that is supposed to influence the impact of the project in Nitra is the presence of groups of **people that perceive themselves as victims of discrimination**. Data on this variable were collected through the baseline survey, which revealed that 15% of respondents from Nitra perceive themselves to be a member of a discriminated group. In this respect, respondents from the intervention group are more likely to report discrimination than respondents from the control group (21% vs 10%). The association is statistically significant. The condition of discrimination is probably underreported within the quantitative baseline study, since the results might have been influenced by the request of personal data in the survey (see Appendix - lessons learnt from the baseline study).

PHYSICAL HEALTH, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND EATING HABITS – External influencing factor 3 for Nitra

People's general physical health status, physical activity and eating habits have been considered as a possible

- 32 All the quotes are extracted from the Focus Group Reports as well as from the Storytelling Reports drafted by the local research teams in each city as a result of the qualitative fieldwork research. The full version of these reports is available in Annex 5.
- 33 In general, the analysis presents the associations that were found statistically significant (p-value of a chi-square less than 0.5) and of non-negligible magnitude (Cramer's V greater than 0.1). Given the modest sample size, exceptions were made with associations that don't meet these criteria but are close and of potential interest to the project. More detail on the data analysis are provided in the Appendix.

influencing factor within the proposed impact assessment framework in the pilot of Nitra. The context analysis through the survey revealed that a large majority of respondents from Nitra report **satisfaction with the status of their physical health**: 71% rate their physical health to be good, very good, or excellent. Respondents from the intervention area report satisfaction with their physical health slightly more frequently than respondents in the control group (74% vs 68%), but the difference is not statistically significant.

With respect to the **practice of physical activity**, about half of respondents from Nitra (50%) report engaging in physical exercise at least once per week. Respondents from the intervention group report engaging in exercise less frequently than respondents from the control group (44% once a week or more vs 55%). The association is not statistically significant.

Regarding **time spent on food preparation**, 61% of respondents from Nitra reported being the main meal preparer at home. This percentage is lower among respondents from the intervention than among respondents from the control group (55% vs 66%), but the association is not statistically significant.

Among respondents who are responsible for preparing meals, about a third (32%) reported spending more than one hour a day on meal preparation. Respondents from the intervention group report spending more time than respondents from the control group (43% more than one hour a day vs 23%). The association is statistically significant.

Regarding the **consumption of fruit and vegetables**, about a fourth of respondents from Nitra (24%) reported consuming at least three portions a day of fruits or vegetables. The percentage is the same among respondents from the intervention group compared to those from the control group (24% vs 24%).

Finally, a majority of respondents from Nitra report that **access to healthy food** in a typical week is quite or extremely easy for them (66%). Respondents from the intervention group find access to healthy food as easy as respondents from the control group (66% easy vs 66%).

Among those who did not find access to healthy food easy, the top reason was its cost (48%), lack of time (33%), and lack of access to it in the neighbourhood (21%).

TIME DEVOTED TO FAMILY, LEISURE AND PETS CARE – External influencing factor 4 for Nitra

The time devoted to family, leisure and pets' care was also investigated as a possible characteristic of the context that may influence the impact of the IN-HABIT solutions on health and well-being of the target beneficiaries in Nitra.

Overall, 65% of respondents from Nitra reported devoting one hour or more a day to **leisure or personal care**. The proportion is slightly higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to those from the control group (67% vs 63%), but the difference is small and not statistically significant.

Regarding **time devoted to family care**, the majority (71%) of respondents from Nitra report spending one hour or more a day caring for their family. Respondents from the intervention group spend as much time on family care as respondents from the control group (72% one hour or more vs 70%).

Overall, 42% of respondents from Nitra reported spending one hour or more a day **playing with or caring for their pets**. Respondents from the intervention group reported spending as much time with pets as respondents from the control group (43% one hour or more a day vs 41%).

About half of respondents from Nitra report being **satisfied with the way they spend their free time** (52% satisfied or more than satisfied). Respondents from the intervention group report higher satisfaction than respondents from the control group (57% vs 48%), but the association is statistically significant and negligible in size.

COVID PANDEMIC – External influencing factor 5 for Nitra

The qualitative study in Nitra helped deepen some effects of the Covid 19 pandemic on the sub-dimensions of health and well-being under investigation. In particular, the data collection through storytelling focused on the investigation of the effects of the first, second and third pandemic waves on cultural engagement and participation, social inclusion and social engagement, employment, leisure and free time, spatial well-being.

In addition to this, a comparative analysis among the four cities is presented in section 5 based on the results of the quantitative study on a set of indicators on Covid-related effects. Based on the results of the analysis of the stories collected in Nitra, Covid affected negatively all the aspects of social and economic well-being, although in a different way when comparing those frequenting the community center of Hidepark and/or working in the city center and those living and working in the peripheral neighbourhoods like the industrial district of Dražovce.

Participants from the first group reported a deeper change in their daily routine in terms of loss of opportunities and benefits from **cultural participation, social engagement and volunteering, job opportunities related to culture and tourism, satisfaction from social relations, cultural and community life**, which was quite intense and vibrant before the Covid.

Two stories among those collected in Nitra show this type of change in terms of loss of social and cultural resources.

► STORYTELLING - The effects of Covid on the loss of social and cultural resources

A woman who holds an art gallery and a shop in the city center told how she and the local community were very active in terms of organization of cultural and social events before the Covid. All these events were suspended or moved to the online space, with a loss of interest by the protagonist and the citizens. “For example, before the Corona I was planning one project [...] based on people meeting. It was supposed to be Breakfast on the Main Street. I have already taken a few steps before, I have addressed people who run various businesses here, then institutions, whether it is a gallery or a theatre. [...] And as I said, the point was for people to meet out here, and basically to return the centre of the city its previous function of a promenade. [...] Because of the pandemic, I was called upon to do so as part of measures, in some modification, which did not motivate me at all, because it missed the main objective. Because it was supposed to be about meetings, get as many people in the pedestrian zone as possible to find out that its worth going here [...] So, I don't know how to imagine this anymore under these circumstances, what they still are, that I would organize it”.

► STORYTELLING - The effects of Covid on social engagement

The second story is of a **71-year-old retiree** who lives with his brother. Since retiring, he has started volunteering on a daily basis in various organizations and civic associations, including a hospital for persons with disabilities and the community garden in Hidepark.

By telling his story, he recognizes the satisfaction and the benefits he got from this social engagement and the negative effects on his health and well-being caused by the stop of such activities due to the Covid restrictions.

“At first, I was still in contact with them a lot via messenger and video calls, but it started to weaken. I still miss it, even though it’s been a year and a half”. “I have not yet returned to the hospital. It also limited some annual events that we used to do with tourists - spring fires, annual fires, tramp, November’s, they did not take place. So, it affected me a lot. And it remains. For example, our regular Thursdays, which lasted 40 years, are no longer there. They are irregular because pubs are closed or people are afraid to walk among other people, or there are restrictions. People are afraid. They have nowhere to meet, as before. The actions they are used to do not take place nowadays. And it seems as if they are afraid in the family too, among themselves”. I have a bad feeling about the relationships between people, and that it is transmitted to workplaces and families, that is my main feeling. And the second feeling is that I still feel like fighting it or shifting around”.

On the other hand, persons living and working in Dražovce, besides reporting a generalized increase of **domestic isolation** and **fear of personal contacts**, they were mainly affected in their **mobility habits** since they encountered new difficulties in reaching the city centre or to travel outside their living area, which was the main way to enjoy social or familiar relationships, benefits from nature and cultural facilities before the Covid.

► STORYTELLING - Effects of Covid on mobility and social habits

The story of a couple of migrant workers from Dražovce helps understanding these effects of the Covid pandemic on the mobility and social habits. Before the outbreak of the pandemic their social life and their free time took place mainly outside the neighbourhood “We went to the city park, to the pedestrian zone, to the Nitra Castle, [...] once we were on Zobor, on Calvary. [...] We know a couple of Serbs here, for example in Trnava (about 40 km from Nitra) and we have a friend from work, at who’s place we can go to barbecue in the summer. We also have friends in Hidepark, we can come here to talk”. Then, with the pandemic “We spent all our time at home. We were most affected by the rules regarding travel. For 20 months we have not been at home in Serbia, where our parents live, who are of retirement age and need help”. “Everywhere we go, we go in pair, not in a larger group”. “When the measures started to be less strict, we started going to Hidepark again, also to Trnava to see the Serbian community, and they also came to Nitra for us. But it’s not a lot of people, it’s such a small group”.

“This is life, you have good times and you have bad times. How do you know what’s good, if you don’t know what’s bad?”.

Persons living in the peripheral neighbourhoods of the intervention group also increased their **time spent in the neighbourhood** and **in public green areas near home**, moving mainly by foot and by car to avoid social contact on public transports. In this respect, participants to the qualitative study who live in Dražovce also noticed an increase of social tensions with the local Roma community and an impoverishment of social relations between neighbors.

▶ STORYTELLING - Effects of Covid on the use of public green areas and social tensions

The story of a young student from Dražovce helps understanding this change in the use of local resources, especially public green spaces, on one hand and the increase of social tensions and social isolation in this neighbourhood on the other hand

“During the Corona, I had to spend more time in Dražovce, as it was harder to go to the centre of Nitra, and also more time-consuming, as it was not allowed to go out after 9 pm. So, I was left with Dražovce, where I had to find places where to be and where to walk. So, I got to know Dražovce more during the Corona. My mother, who is already a retiree, she made a Facebook account and started to sport during the Corona, she became interested in Nordic walking with mallets that help, so now she also goes for more walks”.

“As for some practical changes, people, for example, are now afraid to take the bus, which is why I bought a car so I wouldn't have to walk the bus. Because our Roma minority refuses to wear a mask and people are afraid that they will become infected. The bus drivers have little to do with it, nor to deal with it in any way. [...] And now that people are afraid to go out and socialize, they don't go out to their neighbours either. So, I'm not even talking to my neighbours anymore. It's even bigger isolation than it was before”.

ECONOMIC SITUATION – External influencing factor 6 for Nitra

The present study also assumes that the economic situation may influence the expected impact of the IN-HABIT project on people's health and well-being. More specifically, the baselines survey asked local inhabitants of Nitra about their current economic situation in terms of capacity to satisfy one's basic needs, satisfaction for time and resources for personal care and satisfaction with one's own personal care.

About half of respondents from Nitra report being **satisfied with their personal financial situation** (53% satisfied or more). Respondents from the intervention and control group report a similar level of satisfaction with their financial situation (52% satisfied vs 53%).

Half of respondents from Nitra report **satisfaction with the time and resources they have to manage personal matters** (55% satisfied or more). Respondents from the intervention area report slightly higher satisfaction than respondents from the control group (57% vs 53%), but the association is not statistically significant and the difference negligible.

About a fifth (21%) of all respondents from Nitra reported that their financial condition is not enough or just barely sufficient to **satisfy their basic needs**. Respondents from the intervention and control group report similar levels of distress (23% not enough or barely sufficient vs 20%).

According to the qualitative study, these data are also influenced by the Covid pandemic, that caused a decrease of the income for those services and enterprises linked to tourism, social and cultural life as well as higher job insecurity for migrant workers in the industrial district.

A woman from Nitra working in the art and cultural sector reported that “I don't think that just a few people will say that it has not affected them. It also affected me quite fundamentally, since I run a shop, this gallery of mine, I had to close it for the first time, for the first time for three months, the second time for four months”.

A couple of migrant workers from Dražovce neighbourhood commented that “And as for other things, (I hope to) find a better job. I hope that my work visas in Slovakia will be extended, that I will still be able to stay here”.

4.4 THE BASELINE OF THE EXPECTED IMPACTS IN NITRA

The following paragraphs present an analysis of the baseline (starting situation) regarding the selected **aspects of H&W that are expected to change** due to the project solutions in the intervention group compared to the control group of participants in Nitra.

The identification of the research assumptions on the expected impacts on H&W derives from the participative co-design process described in D7.1. In particular, the specific sub-dimensions and impact indicators of interest for the Nitra’s pilot were identified by partners ISIM and UREAD with the involvement of local research partners SUA and HIDE during the co-design phase on the basis of the literature review on one hand and on the consultation of project partners, local inhabitants and representatives of local NGOs on the other hand.

This process allowed to establish the causal chains between the city specific solutions (grouped by typology) and the aspects of health and well-being of local target groups that are likely to be affected by these solutions. The identification of these causal chains is based on the validated method of the Theory Based Evaluation (Weiss, 2007) as better described in D7.1.

The following table shows the causal links between Nitra’s solutions and the selected aspects of H&W that should be improved by the IN-HABIT project (expected impacts). These aspects cover all the IN-HABIT H&W dimensions: social well-being, spatial and environmental well-being, subjective well-being, economic well-being and healthy lifestyles. Each aspect is measured through one or more Impact Indicator on H&W among those selected in T7.1 and described in D7.1.

◆ **Table n.21** – Causal links between project solutions and expected impacts on H&W in Nitra

VIS CATEGORY A NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS IN PUBLIC SPACES	
SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>A1 Community and experimental gardens</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time spent in nature (<i>Richardson, M., Passmore, H. A., Lumber, R., Thomas, R., & Hunt, A. - 2021</i>) • Environmental and Social connection (<i>Uhlmann, K., Lin, B. B., & Ross, H. - 2018</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Change-making attitude
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one’s surroundings – living environment
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety in green area • Accessibility of local resources (healthy food) • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Perceived air pollution • Perceived noise pollution • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Benefits from urban nature • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY B
SOCIAL, CULTURAL AND SPORTS INFRASTRUCTURES IN PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>B1 Reversible Multifunctional Open-source Urban Landscape (sustainable furniture for social, cultural and sports practice)</p> </div>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing (Scully, D., Kremer, J., Meade, M. M., Graham, R., & Dudgeon, K. - 1998) • Environmental and Social connection (Eime, R. M., Young, J. A., Harvey, J. T., Charity, M. J., & Payne, W. R. - 2013)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Change-making attitude • Equal access to culture and leisure
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety in green areas • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Accessibility of local resources • Satisfaction with urban green areas • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment

	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with cultural facilities • Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor) • Perceived Benefits from culture • Local cultural engagement • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Benefits from urban nature • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces • Satisfaction with sports facilities • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports <p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>
<p>B2 Community kitchen and DIY café</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive food behaviours (<i>Sproesser, G., Klusmann, V., Ruby, M. B., Arbit, N., Rozin, P., Schupp, H. T., & Renner, B. - 2018</i>) <p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust in others • Social conflicts • Perception of discrimination in society • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Equal access to culture and leisure • Change-making attitude <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood <p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY C
MOBILITY AND LIGHTING SOLUTIONS FOR PUBLIC SPACES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>C1 Renovation of green corridors with new mobility and lighting solutions</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety <i>(Peña-García, A., Hurtado, A., & Aguilar-Luzón, M. C. - 2016)</i>
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense of safety at night • Sense of safety in green area • Fear of road accidents • Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

VIS CATEGORY D
TRAINING AND SUPPORT FOR SKILLS AND BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
 D1 Business/startup support services	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills
 D2 Training courses for urban gardeners	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mastery (Sirgy, M. J., Uysal, M., & Kruger, S. - 2017) • Time spent in nature <p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust in others • Social conflicts • Perception of discrimination in society • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Change-making attitude <p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources (training opportunities) <p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills • Opportunity to find a job in the city • Expected sector of occupation <p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from nature <p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

VIS CATEGORY E
HEALTHY LIFESTYLES WORKSHOPS, INITIATIVES AND EVENTS

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>E1 Culinary events and educational activities on healthy lifestyles</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive food behaviours (<i>Sproesser, G., Klusmann, V., Ruby, M. B., Arbit, N., Rozin, P., Schupp, H. T., & Renner, B. - 2018</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust in others • Social conflicts • Perception of discrimination in society • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Equal access to culture and leisure • Change-making attitude
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources • Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills • Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

E2

Sports and sustainable mobility services (bike and boat rental)

KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:

- Link between sports/exercise and psychological wellbeing

SOCIAL WELL-BEING

- Equal access to culture and leisure

SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING

- Accessibility of local resources
- Satisfaction with sports facilities
- Practice of sports in public green areas
- Benefits from sports
- Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

- Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas
- Benefits from urban nature
- Satisfaction with sports facilities
- Practice of sports in public green areas
- Benefits from sports

ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

- Satisfaction with one's surrounding – living environment

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY **F**
CULTURAL AND ART EVENTS AND INITIATIVES

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>F1 Cultural initiatives and art performances</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural inclusion (<i>Fancourt, D., & Finn, S. - 2019</i>) • Aesthetics (<i>Mastandrea, S., Fagioli, S., & Biasi, V. - 2019</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Perception of discrimination in society • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Freedom of personal contact • Social engagement • Equal access to culture and leisure
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived inclusiveness of public squares and green areas
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with cultural facilities • Participation in cultural activities within public spaces • Perceived benefits from culture • Local cultural engagement
	<p>ECONOMIC WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with one's surroundings – living environment
<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>	

F2
Creative workshops
on self-construction
of urban furniture

KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING:

- Mastery (*Sirgy, M. J., Uysal, M., & Kruger, S. - 2017*)

SOCIAL WELL-BEING

- Trust in others
- Social conflicts
- Perception of discrimination in society
- Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood
- Contact with others in public spaces
- Domestic isolation
- Sense of inclusion
- Freedom of personal contact
- Social engagement
- Equal access to culture and leisure
- Change-making attitude

SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING

- Accessibility of local resources
- Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood

HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

- Practice of healthy leisure
- Time spent in social and recreational public spaces
- Benefits from social and recreational public spaces
- Perceived quality of free time in public spaces

ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

- Satisfaction with one's own competencies and skills
- Opportunity to find a job in the city
- Expected sector of occupation

SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

- Feeling cheerful and in good spirit
- Feeling calm and relaxed
- Feeling active and vigorous
- Feeling fresh and rested
- Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself

MENTAL DISTRESS

- Feeling nervous
- Feeling hopeless
- Feeling restless or fidgety
- Feeling depressed
- Feeling that everything was an effort
- Feeling worthless

LIFE SATISFACTION

VIS CATEGORY **G**
DIGITAL SERVICES TO BOOST HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

SOLUTION APPLIED AT CITY LEVEL	SPECIFIC EXPECTED IMPACTS ON H&W
<p>G1 Digital games and services through the INHABIT-APP supporting healthy lifestyles, socialization and cultural participation</p>	<p>KEY PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPTS LINKED TO IMPROVEMENTS IN WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impacts of play (<i>Gleave, J., & Cole-Hamilton, I. - 2012</i>)
	<p>SOCIAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood • Contact with others in public spaces • Domestic isolation • Sense of inclusion • Social engagement • Equal access to culture and leisure
	<p>SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of local resources
	<p>HEALTHY LIFESTYLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice of healthy leisure • Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas • Time spent in social and recreational public spaces • Benefits from social and recreational public spaces • Perceived quality of free time in public spaces • Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption • Benefits from urban nature • Satisfaction with sports facilities • Practice of sports in public green areas • Benefits from sports • Satisfaction with cultural facilities • Participation in cultural activities within public spaces • Perceived benefits from culture • Local cultural engagement
	<p>SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING</p> <p>PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling cheerful and in good spirit • Feeling calm and relaxed • Feeling active and vigorous • Feeling fresh and rested • Feeling that one's life has been filled with things that interest oneself <p>MENTAL DISTRESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling nervous • Feeling hopeless • Feeling restless or fidgety • Feeling depressed • Feeling that everything was an effort • Feeling worthless <p>LIFE SATISFACTION</p>

4.4.1 THE BASELINE OF SOCIAL WELL-BEING IN NITRA

SOCIAL COHESION - THE BASELINE IN NITRA

The first expected change regarding the Nitra pilot relates to an improvement in the current level of social cohesion. Social cohesion in Nitra has been investigated through the following Key Impact Indicators: satisfaction with personal relationships, trust in others, social conflict and perception of discrimination in society.

Regarding **satisfaction with personal relationships** and **trust in others**, focus groups participants from Drazovce neighbourhood showed a good level of satisfaction and trust, by reporting kindness and solidarity from neighbours “they are simply pleasant, they are smiling, they have a time for me, they listen when I’m talking about nothing related to work also, so I’m...even a gentleman who is cleaning the area which I’m crossing on my way to work is smiling at me”. “People are not afraid to communicate, come to each other and talk. For example, many people remember me from childhood, they often just showed up and talked to me”. During the Covid pandemic “young people, we really had several friends and such more distant ones, immediately offered us to buy you medicine, I will run to pharmacy for you, I will run for food for you”. Also for one of the newest citizen of Nitra the first look of the city “is positive, and it is about that Nitra’s smile”.

These results were also confirmed by the quantitative study: a majority of respondents from Nitra are satisfied with their relationship with people living in their neighbourhood (72% satisfied or more than satisfied). The percentage of satisfied respondents is slightly higher among interviews from the intervention than from the control group (75% satisfied vs 69%), but the difference is modest and not statistically significant.

However, the baseline qualitative study revealed a perception of **social conflicts** based on ethnicity, in particular against the Roma community “There is quite a problem with the Roma community, it is not accepted. Also, the Roma community does not accept the ordinary community that lives there”. “If activities arise, actually one, the most important, which is developed by the civic association for Drazovce, it is primarily focused against Roma people, meaning that the main goal is to get rid of them, somehow like that. Not to cooperate with them, neither to find a possibility of cohabitation, but how to send them away”.

Focus groups participants have also witnessed conflicts between Slovaks and immigrants and **discrimination** against immigrants “the fact that now these Ukrainians and others have come to us, so that’s another part, but these people are divided, unfortunately, it’s because there are the original inhabitants of Drazovce, there are new immigrants” in particular “they cursed at the Ukrainians, just because they drink, have fun, it bothers the neighbour, the people”.

Finally, about half of respondents interviewed in Nitra have **trust in the capacity of local authorities to maintain peace and security** in the neighbourhood where they live (50% agree). Respondents from the intervention group agree with the statement less than respondents from the control group (39% vs 60%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate strength.

PERCEPTION OF SECURITY - THE BASELINE IN NITRA

The second research assumption regarding the pilot of Nitra is that the envisaged VIS could contribute to enhancing the perception of security in the intervention group. Perception of security in Nitra has been investigated through the following Key Impact Indicators: sense of safety at night; sense of safety in green areas; fear of road accidents; perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area.

— Chart n.16 – Perception of security in Nitra

Regarding the **sense of safety at night**, about half of respondents to the survey in Nitra consider walking alone after dark to be safe (47%). However, the perception of safety is lower among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (36% vs 57%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate size. These results have been confirmed by the qualitative study, where participants reported fear of walking at night in the public green areas of intervention, which are considered not sufficiently illuminated, as well as in the streets of Dražovce: “the only thing that could be done in Dražovce was to walk on a few safe alleys where you were not afraid. Even parents do not let their children out much, not only young children, but also teenagers, especially after dark”. A focus group participant admitted that, because of the missing public lighting, in Hidepark when “there is already no sunlight, it is too risky for me that there is not enough light, I just didn’t feel safe”.

The baseline study confirms that there is a correlation between poor lighting and perceived security, since the questions about the sense of safety during the day or within the green areas show better results.

Most respondents in Nitra consider **walking alone during the day** to be safe (78%). Again, the perception of safety is lower among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (66% vs 89%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate strength.

Most respondents from Nitra consider **walking alone in public green areas** to be safe (73%). This percentage is lower in respondents from the intervention area than in those from control group (64% vs 80%). The association is statistically significant.

Regarding the **fear of road accidents**, about half of respondents from Nitra are concerned by the risk of road accidents while walking or cycling in their neighbourhood. Overall, less than half of respondents consider walking or cycling safe (43%). This percentage is lower in among respondents from the intervention area than among those from the control group (31% vs 53%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate magnitude. These results are also confirmed by the qualitative study, that revealed a moderate fear of road accidents among the participants. They reported, for example, that the lane between Nitra and Drazovce has a big problem “because [...] for example if someone on wheelchair with a special bike or just on a wheelchair would like to pass it, there is just no space for it, because he will fall down to trench or creek”. There is the possibility of car accidents or the risk that cyclists and walkers can be hit by cars. It is dangerous also for workers “because those Ukrainians and Poles go to work here, I know, because they keep calling me that we go with flashlights and headlights”. Along the bike path “there is a problem with the lighting [...] and it is also I think dangerous in terms of an accident, now in the winter it will be even worse because it will be dark soon”.

Regarding the **perception of crime and vandalism in the living area**, about half of respondents from Nitra consider leaving a vehicle unattended to be safe (46%). Respondents from the intervention group consider it less safe than respondents from the control group (41% vs 51%), but the association is not statistically significant and negligible in magnitude.

About half of respondents (54%) from Nitra agree that it often happens to them observing vandalic damages to urban furnishings and private properties. This percentage is slightly higher among respondents from the intervention group than among respondents from the control group (56% vs 51%), but the association is not statistically significant and of negligible magnitude.

SOCIAL INCLUSION - THE BASELINE IN NITRA

Social Inclusion has been assessed as a sub-dimension of IHW that is supposed to change due to the IN-HABIT solutions in Nitra. The baseline level of social inclusion has been investigated throughout a set of Key Impact Indicators, as specified in ANNEX 4. The first indicators of social inclusion analysed by the baseline study in Nitra is the **contact with others in public spaces**.

In this respect, a majority of respondents from Nitra report getting together with friends or relatives in a public space once a month or more (65%). This percentage is similar among respondents from the intervention area control groups (66% vs 65%).

The results of the qualitative study also confirmed this positive habits: although reduced by the Covid effects, the contact with friends and acquaintances within public spaces like bars/pubs, public transports, urban parks and community gardens, streets and squares is a widespread habit among local people, both in the historic centre and in the peripheral neighbourhoods. Outdoor public spaces were also the first place of sociality regained immediately after the easing of anti Covid measures: “When the measures started to be less strict, we started going to Hidepark again”. “...Somehow I got more involved here within the garden”. “...I think it was positive in the way that people realized that it is possible to go to nature”.

Domestic isolation has increased during the Covid pandemic, but, according to the participant of the qualitative study, it may represent a temporary condition of the local inhabitants. The same occurs for the current low sense of **freedom of personal contact**, that was greatly affected by the pandemic situation and caused fear of crowded spaces like public transport and pubs, avoidance of social relations and propensity for isolation.

The **sense of inclusion in the local community**, according to the results of the baseline study, positively affects the majority of respondents from the intervention group. In fact, over half of respondents in Nitra report that feeling a sense of community with other people in their neighbourhood is important (57%). The percentage reporting this to be important is 60% among respondents from the intervention group and 55% among respondents from the control group. The association is not statistically significant.

On the other hand, the target group that suffers a stable condition of severe domestic isolation and **social exclusion** is the community of migrant workers in Nitra, with only few exceptions represented by those who attend the community center of Hidepark.

Participants to the focus group reported that: “Many Serbian people who work there at Land Rover, from what I know, these people are not integrating at all, they just come, work, work, work, sleep, sleep and go home, they bring the money and that’s it”. “They have nothing to do here. You know that it is such that they come home and they usually get drunk in those hostels. Participants perceive a **separation among cultural and national communities** “They (Ukrainians) all live in their world, they..They are together, ours are together, there is no connection between them, so I think this project would be good in that there would be such a connection by them living there”. Also with regards to Roma people “There are no conditions created for these people to meet there and to form relationships with each other”.

The few migrant workers who attend social and community centers benefit from higher level of social inclusion. For instance when A. (Ukrainian man) came to the community garden in Hidepark “He didn’t want anything to have in common, nor to talk, nor anything, we had to communicate through his son, after a year we actually started to make friendship, talk, so then he relaxed, he started to get involved in other activities, and not only at his field, he asked questions and came to show us his granddaughter [...] but he is an active member now, which is absolutely great”.

With regards to **civil engagement**, a minority of respondents from Nitra report **engaging in democratic life** at city level through committees and councils once a month or more (10%). This percentage is **14%** among respondents from the intervention group and 7% among respondents from the control group. The association is statistically significant but weak.

These results are also confirmed by the qualitative study. Focus groups participants agree on the fact that they do not trust institutions nor the **possibility to influence local political decisions** “I don’t feel like things can’t be changed, and maybe sometimes the political way of doing it somehow other than often.... the community can work better than through such lines to these political ones” or the feeling that “I can change things in my surroundings, but I don’t have to cooperate with the city for it”.

In general from the focus groups participants emerge a change making attitude witnessed by their social engagement and their commitment towards the community.

According to the results of the qualitative study, local inhabitants experience a moderate level of **social engagement** and **change making attitude** since they believe it is easier to change the life in the neighbourhood from the bottom. For instance, regarding the problem of the rubbish in the forest, a participant to the focus group reported: “I said that we can solve it by taking the children (among them there were also three Roma children) out of school, after school, asking them to do the activity, clean it up, and then make them a barbeque as a reward”.

In this respect, 52% of respondents from the intervention group report **talking informally with neighbors about a community problem** once a month or more. The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to those from the control group (52% vs 38%). The association is statistically significant and of moderate strength.

30% of respondents from the intervention group report **engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activities** once a month or more. The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (30% vs 16%). The association is significant.

Only a minority of respondents from Nitra report **taking care of public spaces and green areas** of their neighbourhood as a volunteer once a month or more (17%). Respondents from the intervention area do so more frequently than respondents from the control group (20% vs 14%), but the association is not statistically significant.

— Chart n.17 – Socio-cultural engagement and relations in public spaces: how often do people engage in the following activities in Nitra

This higher level of social engagement in the intervention group is also confirmed by the qualitative study, where participants reported to be committed in social care services as a volunteer, in the organization of cultural events or in the maintenance of public green spaces and community gardens. This is due, in particular, to the presence of the community center Hidepark in the intervention area and in the selection of the participants to the qualitative study among the local observers.

Participants to the qualitative study also showed **satisfaction with their level of involvement in the local community** life. “I also work with the leader of activators. She helped me a lot there in the beginning, she moved a lot of contacts to me. And I am actually in a regional organization in Nitra through one political party, where I am a member”.

“I have been to all sorts of events as a volunteer, once back. But we are such as family association. We started as a family, mom packs packages, others do this, kids bring things. And by having a son with a mental disability, I involve him in these activities, because I know that he will live in that community”.

However the social engagement does not involve the local ethnic minorities nor the inhabitants of the industrial district, where, according to the inhabitants participating in the study, there are no community centers nor social and recreational activities with the only exception of the elderly center.

EQUALITY IN THE ACCESS TO CULTURE AND LEISURE - THE BASELINE IN NITRA

The proposed baseline study has also investigated the current level of **equality in the access to cultural and leisure opportunities**, since they are two key components of IHW that are expected to change thanks to the VIS in Nitra.

The City of Nitra presents a wide cultural and leisure offer: in 2019 it hosted five theatres, two public swimming pools, and one public library. According to Eurostat, the city's cinemas offered a capacity of 1619 seats, drawing a total annual attendance of 429 thousand visits. Museum attendance is reported by Eurostat at 42 thousand visitors during the same year³⁴.

Regarding the **obstacles for the access to culture and leisure**, a majority of respondents from Nitra to the baseline survey report having no difficulty accessing cultural and leisure opportunities in their neighbourhood (60%). Respondents from the intervention are less likely than respondents from the control group to report no difficulty (51% vs 68%). The association is statistically significant and of medium strength.

According to the participants to the qualitative study, the local cultural offer is substantial, however it is not easily accessible by all the social groups, especially by young people, ethnic minorities and persons living outside the old city center, who have mobility obstacles. Young people and ethnic minorities lack adequate cultural offer for them in terms of quality as well as in terms of inclusive cultural space where they can feel welcome and valued. Mobility obstacles for the access to culture affect mainly the inhabitants of the neighbourhoods that are far from the old city center, especially Dražovce.

While the old city center has a vibrant cultural life with theatres, libraries, cultural associations and galleries that organise several events, the inhabitants of the neighbourhood of Dražovce experience difficulties in accessing cultural and leisure opportunities. The qualitative study also confirmed that people living far from the community center of Hidepark find more difficulties in accessing cultural opportunities due to mobility obstacles, especially persons with disabilities and elderly.

34 Eurostat, URB_CTOUR, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/142f62f0-18e8-429c-aca2-1c171f760658?lang=en>

► STORYTELLING - Accessibility of culture and leisure in Dražovce

The testimony of a young person from Dražovce helps deepening this aspect with respect to equal access to cultural and leisure opportunities for young people in the neighbourhood.

“Here was not much to do in Dražovce, mostly when someone wanted some physical or other activity, they went to Nitra. Community activities in Dražovce were difficult to find. The community centre is intended for the elderly and will remain so. We need to find some middle ground and do interesting projects for all groups, for everyone, and combine them differently and find common things” .

“There is not much here, nor is there anything to do except these few streets for walks and cycling. We still don't have interesting activities and places to go, like teahouses or cafes”.

“I hope things will change in the future. It doesn't take that much, it's enough for someone influential to be interested, and some budget would be enough. Benches, a little colour to restore something, interesting objects, climbing frames, various things like that. A few interesting activities. And people would start communicating more, because what else can be done? Even if families and children met in these places, they could talk, share advice, and so on. Now I know that even in Dražovce you can walk and try to talk to people. I think people will start meeting again and re-establishing neighbourly relations. Maybe even more people are moving here, as there are more and more job offers in the industrial park. And maybe neighbourhood communities, smaller ones, will be built. It may probably be better naturally without any intervention, but it depends on people and their desire to socialize, and this is unpredictable. The mentality here is a bit like everyone is on their own”.

Furthermore the results of the baseline study are influenced by the effects of the Covid pandemic, since data have been collected in September-October 2021, between the third and the fourth pandemic wave in Slovakia. As reported by the participants to the storytelling sessions, the fear of personal contact and the restrictions caused by the pandemic led to an increase in inequalities in access to culture because it has pushed especially the most fragile subjects (people with disabilities, the elderly, people with a precarious state of health) to isolate themselves, it has reduced the propensity to use public transport and therefore the mobility of people, as well as the cultural offer itself.

► STORYTELLING - The effects of covid on the quality of leisure

A young man with a physical disability told its story on how the Covid has affected his access to leisure.

“It affected me mainly by staying at home, as I do not have a very good immunity. So, I really avoided contact with people and so on. I hadn't gone out before very often too, but suddenly it was weird that you would like to, but you can't”. “I spend time at home, with movies, books and video games, or I'm with my girlfriend”. Another young participant who lives in the peripheral district of Dražovce added that “As for some practical changes, people, for example, are now afraid to take the bus, which is why I bought a car so I wouldn't have to walk the bus”.

SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING - THE BASELINE IN NITRA

The baseline study detected the current level of spatial well-being of both intervention and control groups in Nitra by investigating a set of impact indicators.

The first aspect regards the perceived **accessibility of local resources**. The city survey asked how easy it is to find some specific resources in the neighbourhood.

— Chart n.18 – Accessibility of local resources in Nitra: how easy is to find the following resources in the neighbourhood

Not easy (0/1/2) ■ Easy (3/4/5)

According to respondents in Nitra, some local resources in the neighbourhood are easier to access than others. In addition, all resources mark a distinction between respondents from the intervention and control groups:

- moving on foot is considered easier by the respondents from the control group (75% intervention vs 91% control) as well as moving by bike (70% intervention vs 81% control)
- finding help from others is considered easy by the 43% of respondents in the intervention group vs 57% in the control group
- finding a green space to do sports is considered easier by the respondents in the control group (57% intervention vs 76% control) as well as finding safe, accessible and pleasant green areas (57% intervention vs 74% control) and finding playgrounds for children (45% intervention vs 76% control)
- finding healthy food easy is also considered easier by the participants from the control group (50% intervention vs 66% control)
- participating in cultural events marks a similar difference, with 49% of the participants from the intervention group considering it easy vs 64% in the control group
- 39% of the participants from the intervention group consider finding adequate social and health assistance easy vs 64% in the control group.

Regarding **satisfaction with urban green areas** in Nitra, the survey showed that they are frequented and appreciated by most respondents, with some notable differences between intervention and control group, with respondents from the intervention group showing a lower level of satisfaction.

More specifically, regarding satisfaction about the inclusiveness and accessibility of the urban green areas:

- 72% agree that they are frequented by people of all ages (62% intervention vs 81% control)
- 63% agree that they are frequented by people of all ethnicities (61% intervention vs 64% control)
- 50% agree that they are accessible for persons with disabilities (34% intervention vs 64% control).

Regarding satisfaction about the beauty and state of maintenance:

- 64% agree that they are a pleasant and beautiful place to spend their free time (54% intervention vs 74% control)
- 60% agree that they are well maintained (49% intervention vs 70% control).

Additionally, 21% of respondents report that they do not frequent any public green area (27% intervention vs 16% control).

— Chart n.19 – Satisfaction with urban green areas in Nitra

Regarding pollution of their neighbourhood, over half of respondents agree with the statement that there is a lot of trash and litter on the streets of their neighbourhood (59%). The percentage is similar among respondents from the intervention and control group (59% vs 58%).

About one respondent in four from Nitra think that the air is unbreathable (27% agree). The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (32% vs 23%) but the association is not statistically significant.

With regard to noise pollution, a majority of respondents from Nitra agree that the areas they live in are noisy and have heavy traffic (61% agree). The percentage is similar in interviews from the intervention and control group (62% vs 60%).

These results have been in part confirmed by the findings from the qualitative study, where participants from Dražovce reported the lack of adequate social and cultural facilities in the neighbourhood, while appreciating the availability and quality of public green areas in the city.

“Nitra is really great in this, we have a park here, we have forests near it, that when a person needs to clear his head between the green somewhere, it is not an absolute problem, I think”.

In particular, participants reported their appreciation for Hidepark, an independent cultural and community centre in the intervention area, built out of pure volunteer enthusiasm that was indicated by the majority of the participants as their favourite place for sport, culture, art, ecology and sociability: “I think it’s really great, for example when you go to Dražovce along the bike path there are ducks, now we have beavers or muskrats, it’s great, it’s really beautiful there when you go there on that bike because we always cycled with family or acquaintances only in Dražovce to the church and now we actually have the opportunity to go completely different direction”.

Regarding their **attachment and sense of belonging to the neighbourhood** they live in, respondents from the intervention area are generally less positive than those in the control group:

- 48% agree that the image of the neighbourhood where they live has improved in the past two years (43% intervention vs 52% control)
- 41% agree that their neighbourhood is attractive for tourists (44% intervention vs 38% control)
- 35% agree that no one is left alone (29% intervention vs 40% control).

— Chart n.20 – Perception of the neighbourhood in Nitra

Participants from Dražovce that were involved in the qualitative study showed a moderate sense of belonging and a good perception of the neighbourhood, as they think that the image of the neighbourhood has recently improved and it could attract more tourists in the next years. The favourite place where they bring family and friends who come visiting them is Dražovce in general, the Church, Hidepark and all the road to the forest in Zobor (a hill within the city). One of the participants explained that in their neighbourhood there are some “opinion-forming groups” who contribute to give a good image of the district “there are also organizations as gardeners, it is very strong group, which is dedicated to activities related to gardening, they organise exhibitions and so on, ex-

hibition of wine and similar. They seem as a nice people, simple, who are doing nice activity, there is always singing there, accordion is playing, and it is simply one strong group. Then there is a second one, the folk band called Tradition, which organise different performances, also thematically oriented, again they are for sure seen positively in the city, because they are invited everywhere. So, these are two groups and then there is a church choir”.

A young inhabitant of Dražovce also commented that the perception of their neighbourhood has improved after the Covid emergency when they had to spend more time in the neighbourhood “I find Dražovce more interesting now, I find it to be more than a place where I live, but also where you can spend your free time at least a little”.

4.4.2 THE BASELINE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLES IN NITRA

SPORTS PRACTICE AND CONSUMPTION OF SELF-GROWN FRUIT AND VEGETABLES THE BASELINE IN NITRA

Healthy lifestyles were also analysed as a dimension of IHW whose components (sub-dimensions) are supposed to change due (at least in part) to the IN-HABIT solutions in Nitra.

In particular, expected changes in this pilot regard some of the health determinants like: self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption, practice of sports in public green areas and benefits from sports.

Regarding the **consumption of self-grown fruit and vegetables**, the qualitative study revealed that this habit is widespread among the inhabitants who attend the community center of Hidepark and could be extended to other social groups or city areas. Community gardening and cultivation also involved a small group of migrant workers and successfully contributed to their social inclusion in the hosting community.

Regarding the **practice of sports in public green areas**, less than a third (29%) of respondents from Nitra report using the public green areas of their neighbourhood to do sports once a week or more. This percentage is similar among respondents from the intervention and control group (28% vs 30%).

The **benefits from sport** have also been deepened during the qualitative study as one of the components of health and well-being. Participants to the qualitative study report greater awareness of the benefits from sports due to the Covid emergency that forced them into domestic and social isolation.

► STORYTELLING - Perceived benefits from sports

The story of a young man with physical disability gives some relevant insights on the perceived benefits from sport.

The protagonist is a 32-year-old man who lost his entire leg in the fight against cancer, so he is now on a disability pension and has no job. He spends most of his free time at home. He moves with the help of barrels and a car that he can drive. The arrival of the pandemic caused even greater isolation to him “It affected me mainly by staying at home, as I do not have a very good immunity. So, I really avoided contact with people and so on. I hadn’t gone out before very often too, but suddenly it was weird that you would like to, but you can’t.

Before, I used to go somewhere at least 5 times in places that you could swim at opened with a group of friends, but last year, for example, I was only once and this year not at all”.

“Also, it can be seen on my body. I’ve been gaining weight since all this happened. I spend time at home, with movies, books and video games, or I’m with my girlfriend”

CULTURAL PARTICIPATION AND CULTURE-RELATED WELL-BEING THE BASELINE IN NITRA

Overall, the qualitative study revealed a good level of satisfaction with available cultural facilities in the city centre, that is characterized a good offer of cultural events and institutions. Based on the results of the survey, a 49% of the respondents from the intervention group considers participating in local cultural events to be easy vs 64% of respondents in the control group.

People from Dražovce are less satisfied about the cultural facilities in their neighbourhood, as well as young people: they complain about the **lack of recreational and cultural public places** to meet both for Slovaks and immigrants. Immigrants in particular “have nowhere to spend it, there is one bar and one pub”. “The best place for me to meet people was on the bus. It was always the only place where people talked, where they met. It’s sad, but also funny, but the bus was our place where people could socialize”.

Regarding **cultural participation**, overall, 23% of respondents from Nitra reported attending cultural activities organized in public and green spaces of their neighbourhood once a week or more. Respondents from the intervention area attend as frequently as respondents from the control group (24% vs 22%).

With respect to local **cultural engagement**, 30% of respondents from the intervention group report engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activities once a month or more. The percentage is higher among respondents from the intervention group compared to respondents from the control group (30% vs 16%). The association is significant.

This good level of cultural engagement is also confirmed by the qualitative study, that revealed a widespread presence of cultural organizations and association, cultural events and movements, that also led to the proposal of Nitra as European Capital of Culture. However, this cultural vitality is mainly concentrated in the old city center and in Hidepark and has undergone a decrease due to the Covid-related restrictions.

FREE TIME AND LEISURE - THE BASELINE IN NITRA

Another aspect of IHW that is supposed to change due to the IN-HABIT solutions in Nitra is the quality of free time and leisure. This has been considered as a sub-dimension of the “healthy lifestyles” component of IHW (for more detail on the selection of the sub-dimensions and indicators please refer to D7.1).

The first KII under investigation regarding this assumption is the **practice of healthy leisure**. The qualitative study revealed a widespread practice of healthy habits among local inhabitants of the intervention group like walking in nature, cycling, attendance of parks and green areas, sports practice and community gardening. These healthy leisure also involve the participants with disabilities who took part to the study or their care givers (parents or volunteers of social services): “ I motivate those children (with disabilities) so that let’s do something, have fun around it, [...]Because we talk a lot, we walk in nature and they enjoy it. I also do fun activities for them”. “ Also, some sports activities, even with wheelchairs - and especially music therapy”.

Based on the results of the qualitative study in Nitra, the practice of healthy leisure could be improved with respect to the group of local migrant workers (especially those living alone in the industrial park) and for young people who find their main source of leisure in the local pubs and bars. A young participant from Dražovce reported, for instance, that: “The best place for me to meet people was on the bus. It was always the only place where people talked, where they met. It’s sad, but also funny, but the bus was our place where people could socialise”.

People participating in the study in general perceive an impoverishment of the **quality of their free time in public spaces** due to the Covid situation with reduced social and cultural events, limited access to sport centres and swimming pools, reduced gatherings among people and opportunities for social volunteering: “It’s not like before. It’s better than when the pandemic was at its peak, when everything was closed. But it’s not the same and I don’t think it will be. We go outside as before already, it is fine outside. Everywhere we go, we go in pair, not in a larger group”.

However, also thanks to the pandemic, the perception of **benefits from urban nature** is quite high and perceived as potentially increasing in the next future by the participants to the qualitative study. The majority of them reported how the contact with nature has represented one of the few forms of healthy leisure in their neighbourhood both before and during the Covid waves. This awareness of the benefits from urban nature was widespread among the participants to the focus group and storytelling independently from their ethnicity/nationality and other personal characteristics like age, disability, gender identity and neighbourhood of residence.

Data from the quantitative study also confirm the spread of the habit of living in contact with urban nature. In fact, regarding their daily routine, 39% of respondents from Nitra reported **spending one hour or more playing, relaxing, or doing sport in public green areas**. Respondents from the intervention group were more likely to report spending one hour or more a day on this activity (43% intervention vs 35% control), but the association is not statistically significant and of negligible magnitude.

Regarding time spent in social and recreational public spaces, about one third of respondents from Nitra reported spending at least one hour a day in social and recreational public spaces (31%). Respondents from the intervention group report spending as much time there as respondents from the control group (30% one h or more vs 32%).

Among those who **attend social and recreational public spaces**, the qualitative study showed a high level of **perceived benefits** from this practice among adults and elderly, while young people and students are less satisfied. Participants who usually attend the community center of Hidepark reported a higher perception of benefits from social and recreational public space due to the variety of activities offered and to the familiar and inclusive culture of this place also for groups at risk of discrimination as elderly, LGBTQI+ people and migrants. An elderly participant reported, for instance: “My second community is Hidepark. Basically, I started coming here in 2013, when my friend Zuza persuaded me how amazing it is here. At first, just come let us play sometimes. I came, I got a pickaxe in my hand and she immediately told me that I was going to plant. A year later, we established a garden and I was here basically every day, and I still am”.

4.4.3 THE BASELINE OF ECONOMIC WELL-BEING IN NITRA

EMPLOYMENT, SKILLS AND SATISFACTION WITH ONE'S SURROUNDINGS THE BASELINE IN NITRA

The baseline of economic well-being in Nitra focused in particular on employability and satisfaction of one's living environment, since these aspects have been considered as subjected to change due to the IN-HABIT solutions at city level. A specific set of Key Impact Indicators were measured and analysed in the baseline study to detect the starting level for these aspects of the economic well-being. The analysis of the indicators involved is presented as follows.

Unemployment and **employability** is not the main concern of the local inhabitants who took part to the baseline study. The job situation did not emerge as a central topic during the discussion of the focus group not during the storytelling sessions. People participating in the qualitative study did not report any specific dissatisfaction about their **skills and competences** nor about the possibility to find a paid job that corresponds to their competences. An artisan woman working in the art sector has a positive view in this respect: “I feel that it happens that people think qualitatively differently. That maybe not be so many unnecessary things, but if so, something valuable. We mainly support this by offering works of art, craftsmen and jewelers. These are all originals that can be bought from us. And it will help not only us, but also those artists and craftsmen when people want these things that we are offering them”.

However, regarding the perceived **opportunity to find a job in the city**, the qualitative study showed a perception of reduced opportunities and a sense of uncertainty for workers in the art and culture sector, for social and recreational services and for economic immigrants living and working in the city.

An elderly volunteer gave a picture of the social services sector: “I have started volunteering at the Klokanček Mother Center. They called me because of my jewelry making workshop and it lasted for 5 years. One of my acquaintances also worked there, telling me to come and have a look at their work, because at that time she was

setting up a hospital for the severely disabled. So, I came there once to see it and I stayed there for exactly 10 years. The Corona interrupted it”.

An immigrant worker from the industrial district reported that: “It would be good if everything was as it was before the Corona, especially when it comes to travel. In order to travel better, go see other countries, and especially so that they are no longer red countries. So that we can also travel home to Serbia more easily. And as for other things, find a better job”.

4.4.4 GDEI ANALYSIS OF THE BASELINE IN NITRA

This section gives an overview of the key findings regarding the baseline situation of socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles of the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion in Nitra. This analysis is mainly based on data from the baseline survey, where associations between key impact indicators and membership to city target groups have been explored with the use of statistical tests and standardised effect sizes (for more detail see section II.c of the Appendix). The GDEI analysis of the baseline should be interpreted with caution though, as the number of observations in some of the target groups can be too modest to be reliable. For the very same reason the analysis by target group could be performed at city-level and not at control/intervention group level, where the number of observations per cell would be even smaller.

• Women

The analysis of the interviews conducted for the baseline survey in Nitra revealed gender differences on key impact indicators in the sub-dimensions cultural participation, perception of security, and spatial well-being.

Women were found to be more likely than men:

- to consider walking alone after dark not safe (63% not safe vs 36%)
- to find moving by bike easy (81% easy vs 70%).

Women were instead found to be less likely than men:

- to take part in cultural activities organized in public squares and green areas of their neighbourhood (16% once a week or more vs 34%).

• Young and Elderly

The interviews conducted for the baseline in Nitra revealed differences by age in key impact indicators. Interesting differences were found in the dimensions of perception of security, spatial wellbeing, and social inclusion. As only 11 respondents out of 282 collected in Nitra reported being 65 years old or more, only comparison of young persons and adults are reported.

Compared to mature adults (35-65yo), young persons (18-34) were found to be:

- more likely to think that walking alone during the day is safe (85% safe vs 75%)
- more likely to think that walking alone in public green areas is safe (81% safe vs 68%)
- more likely to think that finding adequate social a health assistance in their neighbourhood is easy (64% easy vs 45%)
- more likely to think that finding playgrounds for children is easy (70% easy v 56%)
- less likely to informal talk with neighbors about community problems (38% once a month or more vs 48%)
- more likely to get together with friends and relatives in a public space (73% once a month or more vs 56%).

► LGBTQI+ people

Out of 282 interviews collected in Nitra, only 16 respondents self-identified as not heterosexual. Despite the small number of responses, some tentative differences could be detected on the subdimension of spatial well-being.

Compared to heterosexuals, respondents identifying as LGBTQI+ were found:

- more concerned of walking alone during the day (38% not safe vs 17%)
- more concerned of walking alone in public green areas (50% not safe vs 22%)
- less likely to think finding help from others is easy (31% easy vs 55%)
- less likely to think participating in cultural events in their neighbourhood is easy (44% easy vs 62%)
- less likely to think that the green areas of their neighbourhood are well maintained (44% agree vs 65%)
- more likely to believe that feeling a sense of community with other people in their neighbourhood is important (56% important vs 39%)
- less likely to talk with neighbors about a community problem (19% once a month or more vs 47%)
- less likely to get together with friends or relatives in a public space (56% once a month or more vs 69%).

► Students

Out of 282 interviews collected in Nitra, only 17 respondents reported being in education or training. Compared to those currently in employment, respondents in education or training were found to be:

- more likely to attend social and recreational public spaces (47% on hour or more a day vs 28%)
- less likely to think that moving on foot is easy in their neighbourhood (76% easy vs 88%)
- less likely to think the public green areas are well maintained (53% agree vs 65%)
- less likely to informally talk with their neighbors about a community problem (18% once a month or more vs 44%).

► Persons with Disabilities

Out of 282 interviews collected in Nitra, 20 respondents reported having a form of disability. Possible differences were detected on key impact indicators on the dimensions of healthy lifestyle and social wellbeing both. People reporting a disability, compares to those that did not, were found to be:

- less likely to think that walking alone during the day is safe (50% safe vs 82%)
- more likely to think that their neighbourhood is attractive for tourists (70% agree vs 40%)
- less likely to think that participating in cultural events is easy (30% easy vs 60%)
- less likely to think that finding a green space to do sports is easy (50% easy vs 69%)
- less likely to think that finding healthy food is easy (40% easy vs 61%)
- less likely to think that moving on foot in their area is easy (55% easy vs 87%)
- more likely to think that a sense of community with other people in the neighbourhood is important (80% important vs 57%)
- less likely to get together with friends or relatives in a public space (55% once a month or more vs 67%).

► Ethnic minorities

Out of 282 interviews collected in Nitra, only 18 respondents reported belonging to an ethnic minority. Compared to other respondents, members of an ethnic minority were found to be:

- more likely to feel that leaving a vehicle unattended is safe (78% safe vs 44%)
- less likely to often observe vandalic damages to public and private properties (39% agree vs 56%)
- more likely to agree that public green areas in their neighbourhood are frequented by people of all ethnicities (83% agree vs 60%).

► Persons living alone

Out of 282 interviews collected in Nitra, 62 respondents reported living alone. A difference was detected on key impact indicators of the subdimension of social inclusion.

People living alone, compared to people living with others, were found to be:

- less likely to informally talk with neighbors about a community problem (32% once a month or more vs 48)
- less likely to engage in cultural and social activities in the neighbourhood as volunteer (15% once a month or more vs 25%).

► Religious minorities

Out of 282 interviews collected in Nitra, 46 respondents reported being affiliated with a non-Christian religion and 132 to a Christian confession. Possible differences were detected in key impact indicators from the subdimensions of leisure/free time, social cohesion, spatial wellbeing, perception of security, and social inclusion.

Respondents from minority religions – compared to Christians – were found:

- less likely to attend recreation and public spaces of their neighbourhood (15% one hour a day or more vs 34%)
- less likely to trust the capacity of local authorities to maintain security in the neighbourhood where they live (33% agree vs 51%)
- more likely to think that walking alone after dark is safe (52% safe vs 37%)
- more likely to think that walking alone during the day is safe (84% safe vs 67%)
- more likely to think that walking alone in public green areas is safe (76% safe vs 63%)
- less likely to think that their neighbourhood is attractive for tourists (39% agree vs 53%)
- more likely to think that finding a safe, accessible, and pleasant green area in their neighbourhood is easy (72% easy vs 53%)
- more likely to think that finding a green space to do sports is easy (74% easy vs 52%)
- more likely to think that finding a playground for children is easy (65% easy vs 49%)
- more likely to agree that green areas in their neighbourhood are frequented by people of all ages (87% agree vs 63%)
- less likely to engage in social and cultural activities as volunteers (15% once a month or more vs 30%).

Intervention Group — People living in Dražovce neighbourhood or frequenting one of the green areas along the cycle road connecting Dražovce with the old city centre.

Control Group — The rest of the inhabitants of Nitra

> SOCIAL WELL-BEING

> EQUALITY AND DISCRIMINATION

Participants from the intervention group reported higher perception of discrimination and inequality, in particular based on ethnicity and age.

> PERCEPTION OF SECURITY

Participants from the intervention group experience a lower sense of safety at night and greater fear of road accidents.

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

Participants from the intervention group experience a good sense of community, social engagement and change making attitude. On the other hand, they report low levels of civic engagement and trust in the institutions and the group of migrant workers suffers a condition of severe domestic isolation.

> SOCIAL COHESION

Participants from the intervention group experience **satisfaction with personal relationships and trust in others**, by reporting kindness and solidarity from neighbours.

Perceive **social conflicts** between Slovaks and migrants as well as with the Roma community.

> SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF RESOURCES IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD

Participants from the control group report a better accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood.

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD AND URBAN GREEN AREAS

Participants from the intervention group report **lower satisfaction with the urban green areas** where they spend the majority of their free time.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

- The habit of **consuming self-grown fruit and vegetables is widespread** among the inhabitants who attend the community center of Hydepark and could be extended to other social groups or city areas.
- Participants from the intervention group are **aware of benefits from urban nature** and perceive these benefits as potentially increasing in the next future.

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

- People from the intervention group experience **healthy leisure practices** like walking in nature, cycling, attendance of parks and green areas, sports practice and community gardening. However, they perceive an **impoverishment of the quality of their free time in public spaces due to the Covid effects**.
- The practice of healthy leisure could be improved with respect to the group of local migrant workers.

> SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

People from the intervention group experience **comparable levels of psychological well-being and mental distress.**

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

People from the intervention group express concern with the **access to house and affordability of houses.**

Covid pandemic caused a decrease of the income in the tourist and cultural sector as well as higher job insecurity for migrant workers in the industrial district.

5. THE BASELINE OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN THE FOUR PILOT CITIES

This section presents the analysis of the baseline data on subjective well-being carried by the School of Psychology of the University of Reading. The data source used for this section was part B of the baseline city surveys that included a battery of questions corresponding to the WHO5 scales, the K6 scales and one question on overall life satisfaction.

Within the proposed assessment framework, subjective well-being of the target beneficiaries has been considered as a transversal dimension of IHW that is expected to change due to the IN-HABIT solutions in the 4 pilot cities.

Subjective well-being indicators have been selected by UREAD based on available and already validated psychometric scales, namely:

- the WHO-5 scale³⁵ includes 5 indicators of positive emotions that detect the overall psychological well-being. To detect the baseline level of overall psychological well-being, respondents were asked how often, during the past two weeks they have been feeling cheerful and in good spirit; feeling calm and relaxed; feeling active and vigorous; woke up feeling fresh and rested; they have been thinking that their daily life has been filled with things that interest them. The baseline level of overall psychological well-being is presented through the mean (M) and standardised distribution (SD) of the values obtained in the responses to these five questions;
- the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6)³⁶ includes 6 indicators of psychological distress. participants were asked how often, during the past 30 days, they have been feeling nervous; hopeless; restless or fidgety; so depressed that nothing could cheer them up; that everything was an effort; worthless. The baseline level of mental distress is presented through the mean (M) and standardised distribution (SD) of the values obtained in the responses to these six questions;
- the Ryff's scale: to detect the baseline level of overall life satisfaction, respondents were asked to what extent they are satisfied with their life at the moment (for more detail see part B of the questionnaire in Annex 2).

5.1 THE BASELINE OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN CORDOBA

A total of 449 individuals completed the WHO5 questionnaire, which measures overall wellbeing, at baseline in Cordoba (overall mean = 63.74, SD = 22.15), of which 262 individuals were in the intervention group and 187 individuals were in the control group. There was not a significant difference in mean WHO5 scores between the intervention group (M = 64.24, SD = 24.56) and the control group, (M = 63.03, SD = 18.30) at baseline, $t(446.19) = 0.60$, $p = .551$, which indicates that well-being was approximately comparable between the two groups.

A total of 459 individuals completed the K6 questionnaire, which is a measure of mental distress, at baseline in Cordoba (overall mean = 14.98, SD = 5.91), of which 267 individuals were in the intervention group and 192 individuals were in the control group. There was a significant difference in K6 scores between the intervention group and the control group, $t(446.17) = 4.14$, $p < .001$. The mean K6 score was significantly greater for the intervention group (M = 15.91, SD = 6.21) compared to the control group (M = 13.69, SD = 5.21) indicating that participants in the intervention group were experiencing higher levels of distress.

In Cordoba, 459 individuals completed the life satisfaction item at baseline (N = 267 in intervention group, N = 192 in control group). Life satisfaction scores were associated with group (intervention versus control) at baseline in Cordoba, $X^2(4, 459) = 24.61$, $p < .001$.

35 WHO (1998). The World Health Organisation- Five Well-Being Index (WHO-5). Outcome & experience measures. CORC. <https://www.corc.uk.net/outcome-experience-measures/the-world-health-organisation-five-well-being-index-who-5/>.

36 Kessler et al. (2002) K6+ Self Reported Measure. National Comorbidity Survey. Health Care Policy. Harvard Medical School. <https://www.hcp.med.harvard.edu/hcs/ftpd/ir/k6/K6+self%20admin-3-05-%20FINAL.pdf>.

5.1.1 THE GDEI ANALYSIS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AT THE BASELINE IN CORDOBA

Women

- There was not a significant difference in WHO5 scores between males ($n = 174$, $M = 64.32$, $SD = 20.61$) and females ($n = 272$, $M = 63.18$, $SD = 23.11$) in Cordoba, indicating that overall well-being was comparable between males and females at baseline.
- There was a marginal difference in K6 scores between males and females in Cordoba at baseline, $t(454) = 1.927$, $p = .054$. Females ($N = 276$, $M = 15.38$, $SD = 5.89$) reported higher K6 scores compared to males ($N = 180$, $M = 14.29$, $SD = 5.82$), suggesting that women experienced increased levels of distress compared to men in Cordoba at baseline.
- There was not a significant difference in life satisfaction scores between males ($N = 180$, $M = 2.28$, $SD = 1.18$) and females ($N = 276$, $M = 2.27$, $SD = 1.21$) in Cordoba at baseline, indicating that overall life satisfaction was comparable between males and females at this time point.

Elderly and young people

- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36-64) and older adults (65+)) on WHO5 scores in Cordoba at baseline. There was a significant effect of age group on K6 scores in Cordoba at baseline, $F(2, 228) = 3.513$, $p = .031$. Individuals in the mid age group demonstrated significantly higher K6 scores ($N = 210$, $M = 15.38$) compared to adults in the older age group ($N = 36$, $M = 12.58$), $p = .023$, suggesting that mid aged adults experienced greater distress compared to older adults at baseline.
- There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between younger adults ($N = 203$, $M = 14.86$) and adults in the mid age group, $p = .636$, or older adults, $p = .083$.
- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+)) on life satisfaction scores in Cordoba at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and life satisfaction.

LGBTQI+ people

- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on WHO5 scores in Cordoba at baseline, $t(121.15) = -.143$, $p = .886$, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified at LGBTQI+ ($N = 94$, $M = 63.48$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 353$, $M = 63.92$).
- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on K6 scores in Cordoba at baseline, $t(135.44) = 1.88$, $p = .062$, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified at LGBTQI+ ($N = 97$, $M = 16.03$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 360$, $M = 14.64$).
- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on life satisfaction scores in Cordoba at baseline, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified at LGBTQI+ ($N = 97$, $M = 2.20$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 360$, $M = 2.30$).

●● Persons with disabilities

- There was an effect of disability status on WHO5 scores in Cordoba at baseline, $F(2, 448) = 3.196$, $p = .042$. Individuals that reported that they had a disability ($N = 35$, $M = 55.40$, $SD = 23.23$) reported lower overall well-being (i.e., lower WHO5 scores) compared to individuals who reported that they did not have a disability ($N = 404$, $M = 64.27$, $SD = 21.67$), $p = .059$. There were no significant differences in WHO5 scores between individuals that reported that they would rather not disclose their disability status ($N = 10$, $M = 71.20$, $SD = 31.82$) and individuals that reported that they did have a disability, $p = .114$, and individuals that reported that they did not have a disability, $p = .589$.
- There was an effect of disability status on K6 scores in Cordoba at baseline, $F(2, 458) = 6.895$, $p = .001$. Individuals that reported that they had a disability ($N = 35$, $M = 17.80$, $SD = 5.09$) reported significantly increased levels of distress (i.e., higher K6 scores) compared to individuals that reported that they did not have a disability ($N = 414$, $M = 14.65$, $SD = 5.86$), $p = .006$. There were no significant differences in K6 scores between individuals that reported that they would rather not disclose their disability status ($N = 10$, $M = 18.80$, $SD = 7.11$) and individuals that reported that they did have a disability, $p = .882$, and individuals that reported that they did not have a disability in Cordoba at baseline, $p = .068$.
- There was an effect of disability status on life satisfaction responses in Cordoba at baseline, $F(2, 458) = 3.420$, $p = .034$. Individuals that reported that they had a disability ($N = 35$, $M = 1.80$, $SD = 1.02$) reported significantly decreased life satisfaction compared to individuals that reported that they did not have a disability ($N = 414$, $M = 2.32$, $SD = 1.18$), $p = .033$. There were no significant differences in life satisfaction responses in Cordoba at baseline between individuals that reported that they would rather not disclose their disability status ($N = 10$, $M = 2.00$, $SD = 1.89$) and individuals that reported that they did have a disability, $p = .885$, and individuals that reported that they did not have a disability, $p = .671$.

●● Ethnic minorities

- There was a significant effect of ethnic group on WHO5 scores in Cordoba at baseline, $F(2, 448) = 4.80$, $p = .009$. Individuals that reported that they were part of an ethnic minority group reported increased WHO5 scores ($N = 41$, $M = 73.66$) compared to individuals who reported that they were part of the ethnic majority ($N = 389$, $M = 62.59$), $p = .006$, suggesting increased overall wellbeing in individual who reported as being part of the ethnic minority compared to the ethnic majority at baseline.
- There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic majority ($N = 395$, $M = 14.83$) compared to individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic minority ($N = 44$, $M = 14.93$) and individuals that declared that they did not wish to disclose their ethnicity ($N = 20$, $M = 18.05$).
- There was not a significant difference in life satisfaction responses at baselines between individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic majority ($N = 395$, $M = 2.27$), individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic minority ($N = 44$, $M = 2.45$), and individuals that did not wish to disclose their ethnicity ($N = 20$, $M = 2.10$). There was not a significant difference in life satisfaction responses at baselines between individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic majority ($N = 395$, $M = 2.27$), individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic minority ($N = 44$, $M = 2.45$), and individuals that did not wish to disclose their ethnicity ($N = 20$, $M = 2.10$).

5.2 THE BASELINE OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN RIGA

A total of 308 individuals completed the WHO5 questionnaire, which measures overall wellbeing, at baseline in Riga (overall mean = 53.14, $SD = 17.96$), of which 127 individuals were in the intervention group and 181 individuals were in the control group. There was a significant difference in mean WHO5 scores between the intervention group and the control group at baseline, $t(306) = 2.10$, $p = .037$. The mean WHO5 score was significantly greater for the intervention group ($M = 55.69$, $SD = 18.76$), compared to the control group ($M = 51.35$, $SD = 17.20$). This indicates that participants in the intervention group had better well-being than the control group at this initial stage.

A total of 308 individuals that completed the K6 questionnaire, which measures mental distress, at baseline in Riga (overall mean = 15.64, SD = 5.21), of which 127 individuals were in the intervention group and 181 individuals were in the control group. There was a significant difference in K6 scores between the intervention group and the control group, $t(296.08) = -2.96$, $p = .003$. The mean K6 score was significantly greater for the control group ($M = 16.35$, $SD = 5.49$) compared to the intervention group ($M = 14.64$, $SD = 4.61$) indicating greater levels of distress in the control group.

In Riga, 308 individuals completed the life satisfaction item at baseline ($N = 127$ in the intervention group, $N = 181$ in the control group). Life satisfaction responses were not associated with group (intervention versus control) at baseline in Riga, $X^2(4, 308) = 4.09$, $p = .394$. This indicates that participants in the control and intervention groups were approximately comparable on life satisfaction.

5.2.1 THE GDEI ANALYSIS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AT THE BASELINE IN RIGA

● Women

- There was not a significant difference in WHO5 scores between males ($N = 77$, $M = 55.95$, $SD = 17.44$) and females ($N = 228$, $M = 52.36$, $SD = 17.98$) in Riga.
- There was a significant difference in K6 scores, $t(136.06) = 2.80$, $p = .006$. Females ($N = 228$, $M = 16.09$, $SD = 5.19$) reported higher K6 scores compared to males ($N = 77$, $M = 14.23$, $SD = 4.98$), suggesting that females experienced increased levels of distress compared to males at baseline.
- There was a significant difference between males and females in life satisfaction scores in Riga at baseline, $t(117.07) = -2.125$, $p = .036$. Males ($N = 77$, $M = 2.14$, $SD = 1.11$), compared to females ($N = 228$, $M = 1.84$, $SD = 0.96$), reported greater life satisfaction.

● Elderly and young people

- There was a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36-64) and older adults (65+)) on WHO5 scores in Riga at baseline, $F(2, 300) = 7.515$, $p = .001$. Younger adults ($N = 206$, $M = 50.27$) demonstrated significantly lower WHO5 scores compared to adults in the mid age group ($N = 86$, $M = 58.87$), $p < .001$, suggesting that younger adults experienced lower overall well being compared to mid aged adults at baseline. There was not a significant difference in WHO5 scores between older adults ($N = 9$, $M = 56.44$) and younger adults, $p = .555$, and adults in the mid aged group, $p = .917$.
- There was a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36-64) and older adults (65+)) on K6 scores in Riga at baseline, $F(2, 300) = 17.503$, $p < .001$. Younger adults ($N = 206$, $M = 16.84$) demonstrated significantly higher K6 scores compared to adults in the mid age group ($N = 86$, $M = 13.13$), $p < .001$, suggesting that younger adults experienced higher distress compared to mid aged adults at baseline. There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between older adults ($N = 9$, $M = 14.56$) and younger adults, $p = .362$, and adults in the mid aged group, $p = .686$.
- There was a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36-64) and older adults (65+)) on life satisfaction scores in Riga at baseline, $F(2, 300) = 3.897$, $p < .001$. Younger adults ($N = 206$, $M = 1.83$) demonstrated significantly lower life satisfaction scores compared to adults in the mid age group ($N = 86$, $M = 2.14$), $p = .044$, suggesting that younger adults experienced lower life satisfaction compared to mid aged adults at baseline. There was not a significant difference in life satisfaction scores between older adults ($N = 9$, $M = 1.44$) and younger adults, $p = .497$, and adults in the mid aged group, $p = .119$.

● LGBTIQ+ people

- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on WHO5 scores in Riga at baseline, $t(72.94) = -1.425$, $p = .158$, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified as LGBTIQ+ ($N = 58$, $M = 49.93$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 247$, $M = 54.30$).
- There was a significant effect of sexual orientation on K6 scores in Riga at baseline, $t(76.44) = 2.706$, $p = .008$. Individuals that identified as LGBTIQ+ reported significantly higher K6 scores ($N = 58$, $M = 17.41$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 247$, $M = 14.15$), suggesting that individuals that identified as LGBTIQ+ experienced greater levels of distress compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual at baseline.
- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on life satisfaction scores in Riga at baseline, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified as LGBTIQ+ ($N = 58$, $M = 1.69$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 247$, $M = 1.98$).

● Persons with disabilities

- There was no effect of disability status on WHO5 scores at this initial time point in Riga, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable across reported disability status at baseline.
- There was not an effect of disability status on K6 scores, suggesting that reported distress was comparable across reported disability status at baseline.
- There was not a significant effect of disability status on life satisfaction responses, suggesting that life satisfaction responses were comparable across disability status in Riga at baseline.

5.3 THE BASELINE OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN LUCCA

A total of 208 individuals completed the WHO5 questionnaire, which measures overall wellbeing, at baseline in Lucca (overall mean = 52.13, SD = 19.45), of which 92 individuals were in the intervention group and 116 individuals were in the control group. There was not a significant difference in mean WHO5 scores between the intervention group ($M = 54.43$, $SD = 18.62$) and the control group, ($M = 50.31$, $SD = 19.98$) at baseline, $t(206) = 1.52$, $p = .129$, indicating that the two groups were approximately comparable on well-being.

A total of 209 individuals completed the K6 questionnaire, which measures mental distress, at baseline in Lucca (overall mean = 13.30, SD = 5.26), of which 92 individuals were in the intervention group and 117 individuals were in the control group. There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between the intervention group ($M = 13.29$, $SD = 5.52$), and the control group ($M = 13.30$, $SD = 5.06$) at baseline, $t(207) = -0.19$, $p = .99$, indicating that the two groups were relatively comparable on the level of distress they reported.

In Lucca, 209 individuals completed the life satisfaction item at baseline ($N = 92$ in the intervention group, $N = 117$ in the control group). Life satisfaction responses were not associated with group (intervention versus control) at baseline in Lucca, $X^2(4, 209) = 2.56$, $p = .635$ indicating that the groups were relatively comparable on level of life satisfaction.

5.3.1 THE GDEI ANALYSIS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AT THE BASELINE IN LUCCA

● Women

- There was not a significant difference in WHO5 scores between males ($N = 59$, $M = 54.71$, $SD = 19.28$) and females ($N = 148$, $M = 51.14$, $SD = 19.56$) in Lucca, indicating that overall well-being was comparable between males and females at this initial time point.
- There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between males and females in Lucca at baseline, $t(99.08) = -.096$, $p = .924$, indicating that levels of mental distress were comparable between males and females at baseline.
- There was not a significant difference in life satisfaction responses between males ($N = 59$, $M = 1.88$, $SD = 1.05$) and females ($N = 159$, $M = 1.99$, $SD = 1.01$), suggesting that life satisfaction responses were approximately comparable between males and females at this initial time point.

● Elderly and young people

- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+)) on WHO5 scores in Lucca at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and overall wellbeing at baseline.
- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+)) on K6 scores in Lucca at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and overall distress at baseline.
- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+)) on life satisfaction scores in Lucca at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and overall life satisfaction at baseline.

● LGBTQI+ people

- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on WHO5 scores in Lucca at baseline, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ (N = 24, M = 48.67) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual (N = 183, M = 52.68).
- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on K6 scores in Lucca at baseline, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ (N = 24, M = 13.88) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual (N = 184, M = 13.23).
- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on life satisfaction scores in Lucca at baseline, suggesting that overall wellbeing was comparable between individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ (N = 24, M = 1.63) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual (N = 184, M = 2.00).

● Persons with disabilities

Only 4 respondents reported having a form of disability, therefore results from the survey are not meaningful.

- There was not a significant effect of disability status on WHO5 scores in Lucca at baseline, suggesting that wellbeing was comparable across disability status in Lucca.
- There was not an effect of disability status on K6 scores, suggesting that reported distress was comparable across reported disability status at baseline.
- There was not an effect of disability status on life satisfaction responses, demonstrating that life satisfaction was approximately comparable across disability status in Lucca at baseline.

5.4 THE BASELINE OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN NITRA

A total of 316 individuals completed the WHO5 questionnaire, which measures overall wellbeing, at baseline in Nitra (overall mean = 55.83, SD = 22.09), of which 167 individuals were in the intervention group and 149 individuals were in the control group. There was not a significant difference in mean WHO5 scores between the intervention group (M = 56.11, SD = 23.84) and the control group, (M = 55.50, SD = 20.03) at baseline, $t(312.9) = .247$, $p = .805$, which indicates that participants in the two groups reported comparable levels of well-being.

A total of 321 individuals completed the K6 questionnaire, which measures mental distress, at baseline in Nitra (overall mean = 14.43, SD = 5.39), of which 169 individuals were in the intervention group and 152 individuals were in the control group. There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between the intervention group (M = 13.92, SD = 5.44), and the control group (M = 14.99, SD = 5.30) at baseline, $t(319) = -1.79$, $p = .074$, indicating that the two groups reported similar levels of mental distress.

In Nitra, 321 individuals completed the life satisfaction item at baseline (N = 169 in intervention group, N = 152 in control group). Life satisfaction responses were associated with group (intervention versus control) at baseline in Nitra, $X^2(4, 321) = 13.79$, $p = .008$.

5.4.1 THE GDEI ANALYSIS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AT THE BASELINE IN NITRA

• Women

- There was not a significant difference in WHO5 scores between males ($n = 116$, $M = 55.13$, $SD = 22.61$) and females ($n = 195$, $M = 56.38$, $SD = 21.38$) in Nitra, indicating that overall wellbeing was comparable between males and females at baseline.
- There was not a significant difference in K6 scores between males ($n = 118$, $M = 14.03$, $SD = 5.52$) and females ($n = 198$, $M = 14.67$, $SD = 5.24$) in Nitra, indicating that levels of mental distress were comparable between males and females at baseline.
- There was not a significant difference in life satisfaction scores between males ($n = 118$, $M = 1.94$, $SD = 1.08$) and females ($n = 198$, $M = 2.05$, $SD = 1.08$) in Nitra at baseline, indicating that overall life satisfaction was comparable between males and females.

• Young and Elderly

- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+) on WHO5 scores in Nitra at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and overall wellbeing at baseline.
- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+) on K6 scores in Nitra at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and overall distress at baseline.
- There was not a significant effect of age group (i.e., younger adults (18-35), mid aged adults (36 – 64) and older adults (65+) on life satisfaction scores in Nitra at baseline, indicating that there was not a relationship between age and overall life satisfaction at baseline.

• LGBTQI+ people

- There was a significant effect of sexual orientation on WHO5 scores in Nitra at baseline, $t(92.17) = -2.075$, $p = .041$. Individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ reported significantly lower WHO5 scores ($N = 62$, $M = 50.71$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 249$, $M = 57.20$), suggesting that individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ experienced lower overall wellbeing compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual at baseline in Nitra.
- There was not a significant effect of sexual orientation on K6 scores in Nitra at baseline, suggesting that overall mental distress was comparable between individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ ($N = 63$, $M = 14.95$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 252$, $M = 14.20$).
- There was a significant effect of sexual orientation on life satisfaction scores in Nitra at baseline, $t(96.57) = -2.996$, $p = .003$. Individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ reported significantly lower life satisfaction scores ($N = 63$, $M = 1.65$) compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual ($N = 252$, $M = 2.10$), suggesting that individuals that identified as LGBTQI+ experienced lower overall life satisfaction compared to individuals that identified as heterosexual at baseline in Nitra.

• Persons with Disabilities

- There was not a significant difference in WHO5 scores between participants that responded that they would prefer not to disclose their disability status ($M = 46.67$, $SD = 13.56$) compared to respondents that reported that they had a disability, and respondents that reported that they did not have a disability.
- There was not an effect of disability status on K6 scores in Nitra, suggesting that levels of mental distress were approximately comparable disability status at baseline.
- There was an effect of disability status on life satisfaction responses in Nitra at baseline, $F(2, 320) = 4.85$, $p = .008$. Respondents that reported that they would rather not disclose their disability status reported significantly lower life satisfaction ($N = 9$, $M = 1.11$, $SD = 1.05$), compared to respondents that reported that they did not have a disability ($N = 282$, $M = 2.07$, $SD = 1.05$), $p = .023$. There was no significant difference in life satisfaction scores between respondents that reported that they did have a disability ($n = 30$, $M = 1.70$, $SD = 1.26$) and respondents that reported that they did not have a disability, and respondents that reported that they would rather not disclose their disability status.

• Ethnic minorities

- There was not a significant effect of ethnicity on WHO5 scores in Nitra at baseline between individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic majority (N = 287, M = 56.01), individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic minority (N = 19, M = 55.37) and individuals that declared that they did not wish to disclose their ethnicity (N = 10, M = 51.50).
- There was not a significant effect of ethnicity on K6 scores in Nitra at baseline, between individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic majority (N = 291, M = 14.48), individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic minority (N = 20, M = 13.50) and individuals that declared that they did not wish to disclose their ethnicity (N = 10, M = 14.60).
- There was not a significant effect of ethnicity on life satisfaction scores in Nitra at baseline, between individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic majority (N = 291, M = 2.03), individuals that reported that they were part of the ethnic minority (N = 20, M = 1.70) and individuals that declared that they did not wish to disclose their ethnicity (N = 10, M = 1.90).

6. THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON PEOPLE'S LIFESTYLES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The Covid-19 epidemic had from the outset the potential to severely affect how persons spend their time and their health and lifestyle behaviour. The baseline survey of the IN-HABIT project took place between the third and the fourth wave of the pandemic, raising the question of whether and how it impacted the lifestyle of respondents in the four target cities.

While answering this question would be outside the scope of the project and the possibilities offered by the current baseline survey, the questionnaire was revised to include a set of questions to capture how Covid-19 affected the daily routine of respondents spent with regard of a list of social, cultural, and health activities.

Specifically, respondents were asked "Since Covid-19 restrictions have been in place, has the frequency with which you perform the following activities changed?". For each activity, respondents could report that the frequency "has decreased", "remained the same", or "has increased". The following activities were rated: reading a book for pleasure; doing physical activity; caring for family members: engaging in cultural activities; cooking; sleeping; listening to music; eating; taking care of your body and appearance; taking care of your home; attending social and recreational public spaces; and playing, relaxing, or doing sports in public green areas. The list spans a range of activities that goes from personal to social, from indoor to outdoor, from cognitive to physical.

The present section reports on the answers collected on these survey items in the four cities involved in the project. First results are reported focusing on a comparison of responses from the intervention areas in the four cities. Then a comparison between intervention and control areas within each city is presented.

— Chart n.21 – The impact of Covid 19 on people's lifestyles: general overview in the 4 pilot cities

The overall picture suggests that despite occasional differences, the frequency of engagement with the activities listed has been affected in a comparable way among respondents from the intervention areas in the four cities. Three notable patterns emerge from [Chart n.21].

First, a large proportion of respondents reported a change in the structure of their activities (i.e., either increased or decreased frequency because of Covid-19 restrictions), but for most of the activities an important plurality of respondents reported engaging in the activity with the same frequency it did before restrictions were in place.

Second, it appears that activities where the proportion of respondents reporting a decreased frequency is higher, are also activities where the proportion of respondents reporting increased frequency is lower. This suggests that the impact of restrictions has induced a consistent change across individuals, primarily related to the type of activity. Third, reports from the intervention areas suggest the activities have been affected by restrictions in a comparable way across the four cities. For example, the activities where respondents were most likely to report a decreased frequency were the most social and outdoor-oriented: engaging in cultural activities; attending social and recreational public spaces; playing, relaxing, or doing sports in public green areas. On the opposite end, the activities where respondents were more likely to report an increased frequency were family or personal indoor-oriented activities: caring for family members; taking care of the home; eating; cooking. In the next four paragraphs we briefly list the main differences detected between intervention and control areas within each city with respect to the self-reported impact of Covid-19 restriction on daily activities. Only activities where the association was found to be statistically significant (p -value less than 0.05) and of non-negligible magnitude (Cramer's V greater than 0.1).

— Chart n.22 – The differential impact of Covid 19 on the lifestyles of participants in the intervention and control groups in Riga

Comparing respondents from the intervention and control areas in Riga, possible differences were detected on the following activities: reading a book for pleasure; playing, relaxing, or doing sports in public green areas; caring for family members; listening to music.

Respondents from the intervention area when compared to respondent from the control areas were found to be:

- less likely to report reading a book less frequently (14% decreased vs 26%)
- less likely to report playing or relaxing in public green areas less frequently (34% decreased vs 50%)
- more likely to report dedicating more time to caring for family members (30% increased vs 17%)
- less likely to report a decreased frequency of listening to music (35% decreased vs 47%).

— Chart n.23 – The differential impact of Covid 19 on the lifestyles of participants in the intervention and control groups in Nitra

Increased Same Decreased

In Nitra the comparison of respondents from the intervention and control areas regarding the effect of Covid-19 restrictions detected possible differences on the following three activities: attending social and recreational public spaces; doing physical activity; taking care of your body and appearance.

Respondents from the intervention areas, compared to those from the control areas, were found:

- more likely to report a decreased frequency of attending social and recreational events in public spaces (50% decreased vs 67%)
- less likely to report spending less time taking care of their body and appearance (13% decreased vs 28%)
- less likely to report both engaging in physical activity more frequently (18% increased vs 26%) and less frequently (27% decreased vs 33%).

— Chart n.24 – The differential impact of Covid 19 on the lifestyles of participants in the intervention and control groups in Cordoba

The comparison of respondents from the intervention and control areas in Cordoba detected possible differences on several activities: reading a book for pleasure; attending social and recreational public spaces; engaging in cultural activities; sleeping; eating.

Respondents from the intervention areas, compared to respondents from the control areas, were found:

- more likely to report decreased frequency of reading a book for pleasure (32% decreased vs 20%) and less likely to report increased frequency (11% increased vs 25%)
- less likely to report decreased frequency of attending social events in public spaces (38% decreased vs 57%)
- less likely to report decreased engagement in cultural activities (40% decreased vs 52%)
- more likely to report both sleeping less frequently (21% decreased vs 15%) and sleeping more frequently (27% increased vs 18%)
- more likely to report both eating less frequently (12% decreased vs 7%) and more frequently (35% increased vs 22%).

— Chart n.24 – The differential impact of Covid 19 on the lifestyles of participants in the intervention and control groups in Lucca

In Lucca, comparing the self-reported impact of Covid-19 restrictions on daily activities between intervention and control areas led to the detection of a possible difference on a single activity: cooking. Specifically, respondents from the intervention areas compared to those from the control areas were found less likely to report both cooking more frequently (29% increased vs 40%) and cooking less frequently (1% decreased vs 11%).

7. APPENDIX ON RESEARCH METHODS AND TOOLS

This section presents the research methods applied, the research tools and the phases of the baseline study.

I. THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present baseline study makes use of a blended approach to evaluation (defined as “bricolage” approach, Nicholls 2009) that is articulated on the appropriate combination of the following types of evaluation:

- the **Theory Based Evaluation**³⁷ (Weiss, 2007), since the study aims at assessing and isolating the short to medium terms impacts of the project through the reconstruction of the causal chains (called “value chains”) linking city specific solutions, objectives and expected changes (see D7.1 part A). The definition of the value chains and related assumptions on the expected changes are the result of a participatory work that involved the researchers (project partners) and the representatives of local stakeholders in task 7.1. The resulting Key Impact Indicators on IHW used in this study were also co-designed with local stakeholders and they represent the joint vision of local people and researches on the expected changes on health and well-being in each pilot city.
- the strategic and cross-use of qualitative/quantitative procedures of data collection and analysis, called **Mixed Methodology Research** (Amaturo, Punziano, 2016). The baseline study, in fact, is based on the use of surveys, focus groups, storytelling sessions and analysis of secondary data.
- the **Practical Participatory Evaluation (P-PE)** methodology (J. Bradley Cousins and Elizabeth Whitmore, 1998), which is characterized by the stakeholders’ participation in the evaluation process.

More specifically, the baseline study has made wide use of the involvement of local inhabitants in both intervention and control group, based on the **Citizen Science Inclusion Mechanism (CSIM)** described in D7.1. Within the baseline study, the CSIM was tested in the 4 cities by the local research teams with the coordination and guidance of ISIM.

More specifically, local inhabitants have been involved in participatory assessment actions like storytelling, surveys and focus groups. Moreover, by testing the CSIM, **some groups of inhabitants played an active role in the research**. In particular:

- the local community activators (**LCAs**), namely local researchers who share some key cultural resources with the local inhabitants, like the language (they speak both English and the local language), the city culture and the knowledge of the local context played a key role in the data collection. Besides administering interviews and facilitating focus groups in the local language, they have acted as activators of local inhabitants, identifying, involving, motivating and keeping contact with local observers and organized groups. LCAs supported the distribution strategy and the snowball sampling of the survey by spreading the on-line questionnaire to specific groups and social network pages as well as mailing lists; by organizing local events with specific target audiences and by interviewing people in their usual meeting/living places, especially inhabitants at risk of discrimination and exclusion.
- **local observers**, who are individual inhabitants and/or representatives of local organizations and groups with a high level of interest in the project, have been involved in the focus groups and storytelling as well as in the recruitment of additional participants to the research actions. They acted as “gatekeepers” and intermediaries between the LCAs and the member of the city specific target groups, since they supported the

37 A theory-based impact evaluation focuses on programme theories, i.e. the assumptions of policy makers and stakeholders on the preconditions, mechanism and context for an intervention to work. Theory-based impact evaluations test these assumptions against the observed results following the different steps of the intervention logic and examine other influencing factors. They are thus able to explain why and how results have occurred and to appraise the contribution of the programme and of other factors. European Commission Impact Evaluation Center
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/evaluations/guidance/impact_faqs_theor#2.

personal contact and involvement of inhabitants in the selected city areas or people with specific personal profiles, thus limiting as much as possible the self-selection bias in the sampling, while ensuring inclusiveness of the research and diversity of the participants.

- members of local **institutions and organized groups** of inhabitants (for example school teachers and students, social workers and volunteers of local NGOs/social care services, members of local neighbourhood committees ect.) have been involved by LCAs and local observers to participate in the survey as well as in the focus group and storytelling. They also acted as multipliers of the research activities by involving the general public of inhabitants in the research actions. In particular, during the baseline study they contributed to spreading the survey, arranging interviews and events for the distribution of the questionnaire, identifying participants with specific personal characteristics.

The participation of local inhabitants in the baseline study was also supported by the use of non monetary **incentives**, which have been designed by local research partners with a context- and target-based approach.

Among the incentives tested during the baseline study:

- the personal relationship (bond of trust) between the various levels of the CSIM, namely between the LCAs, the local observers and the members of local institutions and organized groups, as well as with local inhabitants (Nitra, Cordoba, Lucca, Riga)
- bus tickets (Cordoba)
- training and university credits for students (Riga and Nitra)
- role recognition and space for participation by the local municipality (Lucca)

The proposed baseline study is also characterised by an **inclusive approach**, since:

- **GDEI personal characteristics** which may affect the project's impact on health and well-being are included in the research framework and quantitative data are disaggregated accordingly. On the other hand, expected results and IHW Indicators which may be influenced by GDEI characteristics are included in the research framework as GDEI indicators, which were selected with the involvement of the representatives of the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion (local NGOs in the 4 cities);
- people at risk of discrimination and exclusion have been involved in the data collection actions (surveys, focus groups and storytelling). Specific attention has been paid to practical and organizational measures to ensure an **equitable participation of persons at risk of discrimination and exclusion** in the research activities. In particular the dissemination of the survey to vulnerable persons (elderly, persons with low literacy level, migrants) has been facilitated by the role of the LCAs and local observers who also acted as linguistic/cultural mediators while administering the questionnaire in Nitra and Cordoba.

Moreover, the organization of the storytelling sessions and the focus group has been adapted to the needs of the participants, especially women, elderly and persons with disabilities. For this reason the in person mode was preferred to the digital one, the venue of the interview was a neutral or familiar place (public square, community center, house, bar) and the time was arranged according to the availability of the participants.

II. CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF THE TARGET GROUPS

In each city, the target groups of the baseline study were identified by local research partners and transversal partners (simpart and University of Reading) on the basis of the following criteria:

- a. selection of those groups of people that are more likely to be affected by the city specific project solutions. This assumptions are based on the results of the consultation of local inhabitants and NGOs described in D7.1 as well as on the stakeholders mapping exercise run by local partners for the design of the Inclusive Transitions Plans (D1.1, D2.1, D3.1 and D4.1)
- b. selection of those groups that are at risk of discrimination by gender, age, disability, ethnic origin, sexual orientation and gender identity, religion. These GDEI target groups were included to meet the requirements of the Call as well as the IN-HABIT general inclusive approach that aims at identify the specific impacts of the solutions on these groups

compared to the rest of the beneficiaries in order to assess the capacity of the project to provide an equitable distribution of the benefits of social, cultural, digital and nature based innovations. These target groups often coincide, at least in part, with those that are more likely to be affected by the city solutions.

Based on these two criteria, the city specific target groups for the baseline study were defined and they are presented in the sections related to the city contexts of this deliverable.

III. QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH TOOLS

Within the proposed baseline study, quantitative research tools include surveys and secondary data collection.

III.a THE CITY SURVEYS ON IHW

• The questionnaire

The baseline city survey on IHW is based on one structured questionnaire per city (4 questionnaires in total, Annex 2). Questions are referring to IHW quantitative indicators which have been co-designed in task 7.1 through the “value chain” exercise. As a consequence, some questions are valid for all the city contexts of the project and included in all the city surveys, while some questions are specific for each city based on the different expected results.

The questions are grouped into four sections:

- Section 1: socio-demographic indicators
- Section 2: mental health indicators
- Section 3: healthy lifestyles indicators
- Section 4: social well-being indicators

Each questionnaire has been designed and distributed both in English and in the main local language selected by the local research partners.

• Control groups

They have been used in the survey distribution and analysis to help isolate the future changes attributable to the IN-HABIT solutions and discount external factors.

Respondents belonging to the control groups have been identified through the setting of specific filter questions (Q2 and Q4) that allow to reconstruct information on the area of residence of the respondents as well as on their frequency of use of the intervention group.

• Distribution period

The questionnaires have been distributed in the period from 28.08.2021 to 31.10.2021. This period coincides with a moment of suspension or relaxation of the social distancing measures due to Covid in the four cities. The analysis of the data takes into account the effects of the distribution period on the results.

• Sampling method used to involve the target groups and criteria used to establish the optimal type and number of participants

– A recruitment both empirically- and theoretically- driven

The recruitment of two stratified, non-probabilistic samples in each city has been adopted to ensure both (a) an adequate number of respondents in each city for each of the two fundamental comparisons described above and (b) to ensure that the saturation of theoretically relevant dimensions to the project – age, gender, target group membership – could be achieved by interviewing a set minimum number in each stratum. The distribution strategy for the baseline city surveys on IHW have been defined by LCAs following the methodological guidelines provided by ISIM (see Annex 3). These guidelines defined the objectives of the distribution strategies of the survey in each city and the optimal number and type of participants.

Regarding the **optimal types of participants**, they reflected the city specific target groups identified by local research

partners following the selection criteria specified above. For this reason the distribution strategies agreed with the local community activators were aimed at reaching adults (18+) residents in the pilot cities by focusing on those belonging to the city specific target groups (including the GDEI groups). The recruitment adopted in the city surveys ensured that all the target groups of the VIS, as identified in the co-design phase, would have a chance to be represented in the study. This implies a qualitative and theoretical, rather than probabilistic, representativeness.

Regarding the **optimal number of participants**, the distribution strategy of the survey aimed at reaching least 150 respondents living or attending in a relevant way (at least 4 hours a week) the intervention areas (experimental group) and at least 150 respondents who do not live nor attend such areas (control group).

Minimum thresholds for the participation of each target group were agreed among Isimpact and Local Community Activators during the training sessions and in the Guidelines for carrying the baseline study in WP7 (Annex 3). In particular it was agreed to involve at least 20 participants belonging to each city target group. These thresholds represented a reference point for the recruitment of the participants to the study, although they could not be numerically representative nor binding due to the lack of data on the composition of the population of reference.

The use of these quota and the snowball recruitment of the participants by other participants belonging to the target groups allowed to include a diverse pool of subjects to capture enough “variation” in respondents’ characteristics.

In order to engender the “snowball effect” and support the distribution of the survey, LCAs could identify a first group of “gatekeepers” among the members of the IN-HUBS, namely local observers and members of organized groups who represented or could be in contact with the target groups. The identification of the gatekeepers took into account the necessity to involve both the intervention and the control group in each pilot city.

Gatekeepers were reached by the LCAs through direct personal contacts (e-mail, face to face, phone contact, social media), only after having received their informed consent regarding participation in the research and use of personal data. Additional sample units (respondents) were engaged with the help of the gatekeepers, who (i) further spread the link of the survey or the paper questionnaire to their primary contacts and/or (ii) provided local community activators with the contacts of other inhabitants and organizations belonging to the target groups. Personal contacts were collected by local community activators only after the informed consent of the interested persons.

– The obtained sample and its qualities

Non-probability samples represent a recruitment solution often encountered in the evaluation literature (Stephenson, 1979; Roll & Cantrill, 1972; Brislin, 1990), often by necessity given the peculiar logistical, ethical, and budgetary constraints posed by the practical implementation of interventions in real settings.

This includes in the context of the H2020 project as well, where both the Re.Cri.RE project suggested as reference by the evaluators (snowball sampling) and the sister project VARCITIES (quota sampling) adopt forms of non-probability samples in their evaluation frameworks.

The baseline city survey on IHW made use of a combination of two non-probability sampling methods, in particular:

- self-selection sampling, that allowed people to choose to take part in the study on their own accord. To this aim the survey has been advertised through the project website and social networks, inviting all the people aged >18 and living in the 4 cities to participate.
- snowball sampling, since research participants (particularly local observers and members of local organized groups and institutions) were asked to assist LCAs in identifying other potential participants among the target groups. The snowballing distribution of the survey was chosen to reduce the risk of self-selection of the respondents which is associated to an uncontrolled dissemination of an online questionnaire.

Non-probability samples are not representative of the population, thus they do not allow for generalizations/inferences. For this reason, **the results of the baseline study have been generalized only to the population of the participants to the study.**

The use of a non-probability sample responds to the following methodological reasons:

- due to the high number of variables under investigations (personal and socio-demographic characteristics), the estimation of the composition of the population based on multiple variables was not possible due to the lack of data at city level regarding the composition by ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, country of birth ect.
- the estimation of the composition of the population considering all the variables of interest was excessively expensive and time-consuming when compared to the possible advantages. In some cases the lack of data on some key target groups makes this process simply non feasible.

- generalizations at city level are not the main research goal or the impact assessment. The main objective of the proposed study is to assess the type of changes affecting IHW of the target beneficiaries of IN-HABIT solutions over time compared to a control group.
- probability sampling may produce biases for the purposes of this research, since it may produce an over-representation of people who, although statistically representative, they are not affected by the project VIS (or vice versa).

The choice of the snowball sampling is also justified for at least three additional reasons:

- it is helpful to reduce the biases deriving from the self-selection sampling (for example only people interested in the project or members of the partner organizations may decide to answer);
- it helps reaching the target beneficiaries of the VIS in each city through the involvement of their representatives (local observers);
- it is helpful to involve the groups who are hidden or difficult to reach because they are not familiar with the digital technologies, because they are exposed to discrimination and stigma, because they are not involved in participatory processes. In this case, the personal bonds of trust among the local activators and the participants are essential.

III.b DISTRIBUTION STRATEGIES AT CITY LEVEL

Given these common objectives, each local research team could adopt specific distribution strategies by adapting the general guidelines to the specificities of the local context and target groups. LCAs could therefore decide to focus on one or more of the following distribution modalities:

1. on-line modality (all the cities) : a web link has been disseminated through the project website and social networks (Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter) and further shared through local partner's profiles, targeting local groups/pages and organizations' profiles on social networks. Community activators and project partners (BOT, local partners) supported the dissemination of the link by contacting the relevant online pages and groups, as well as sending e-mails and messages on chatrooms.

2. In paper mode with subsequent recording of responses (mainly in Nitra, in a residual way in Lucca and Cordoba): in this case, the community activators distributed the paper forms of the survey and, only later, they took care of recording the answers (including the consent form part). This modality helped reaching those target groups who may have difficulties with accessing and/or using digital technologies, and implied the active involvement of local observers and organized groups to reach the participants and arrange the distribution and collection. This modality also helped spreading the survey to the specific target groups and city areas in a short time, by reaching for example the community of migrant workers in Nitra through their peers.

3. Interview mode with immediate recording of responses (Cordoba, Riga): the survey was administered directly by the community activator or by the local observers through a face-to-face interview. In this case, the recording of responses (including the consent form part) will take place simultaneously, via digital support. This modality helped involving inhabitants with low literacy level, elderly or people with low linguistic and/or digital skills. It also helped spreading the survey to the specific target groups and city areas in a short time. In the case of Riga, for instance, university students received specific training to run interviews and select relevant participants in selected target groups and neighbourhoods.

III.c THE ANALYSIS OF THE SURVEY

The baseline survey has been analysed with the aim of offering an exploratory comparison of responses obtained in the intervention and control areas, for all relevant indicators³⁸. Where possible, a comparison by city target groups (including groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion) has also been explored. A similar descrip-

³⁸ The quantitative indicators that have been involved in the data collection through surveys are identified in D7.1 Annex 1.

tion will be offered for the ex-post survey that will be fielded at the end of the project.

Responses from respondents who did not consent to participating in the survey have been removed, as have been removed respondents with less than 18 years of age. Respondents who did not satisfy the conditions to be considered part of the intervention or control groups have also been excluded (i.e respondents who did not live in the pilot cities). The large majority of respondents could be included in either group. Item non-response is very modest, suggesting that drop-out happened mostly through unit non-response – contacted respondents not submitting the questionnaire. Bivariate associations have been computed including all available responses for the variables involved. Where a survey question offered multiple response levels (especially if ordered), these have been combined to obtain a binary comparison wherever possible. This step allowed to surface the key distinctions (e.g., agree vs disagree, easy vs not easy, frequently vs not frequently) and reduced the variability introduced by dividing the responses into many cells with too small a number of responses each.

Associations have been explored with the use of statistical tests and standardized effect sizes. Tests inform us on whether there is an association between variables, while effect sizes inform us how practically strong such an association could be.

Chi-square tests have been computed to detect differences that were least likely to be observed if there was no association between a given indicator and membership in the intervention/control group. In general, the report only comments associations whose Chi-square test produced a p-value lower than 0.05; exceptions were made for indicators considered of particular interest or close to the threshold. The strength of association has been assessed computing Cramer's V coefficient, a standardized index of effect size for categorical variables. The coefficient spans from 0 (no relationship) to 1 (perfect association). Associations with a coefficient smaller than 0.1 can be considered negligible in magnitude and in general have not been commented, even if statistically significant. Associations with a V's coefficient between 0.1 and 0.2 can be described as weak; between .2 and .3 moderate; more than .3 strong.

The procedure above has been applied not only to explore association between project indicators and membership in control/intervention group, but also between project indicators and membership in city target groups, including groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion. The goal of this exercise being the detection of differences by target groups relevant to the project and possibly worth further exploration. Results of this last set of tests and associations should be interpreted with caution though, as the number of observations in some of the target group can be too modest to be reliable. For the very same reason the analysis by target group could be performed at city-level and not at control/ intervention group level, where the number of observations per cell would be even smaller.

By the end of the project, data from both surveys (baseline and ex-post) will be available for analysis. It will be possible to perform an analysis more specifically aimed at detecting differences over time in the intervention areas in each pilot city. As questionnaires include a large set of questions on the context and the condition of respondents, the combined analysis will allow a modelling exercise aimed at separating differences attributable to the project from differences attributable to other factors.

In addition, it will be possible to assess to what extent key impact indicators related to the project can be combined in a summative index of place-based well-being. And the extent to which such a summative index correlates with other external or validated measures of well-being collected in the survey.

IV. QUALITATIVE RESEARCH TOOLS

Within this baseline study, the qualitative research tools included focus groups and data collection through storytelling. More specifically, LCAs have been trained and guided by ISIM to organize one focus group and collect 5 meaningful stories in each city, with the involvement of local observers and/or other local inhabitants who live, work or frequent the intervention group on a daily basis.

These research tools were used to detect qualitative data on three dimensions of IHW, in particular: social well-being, healthy lifestyles and economic well-being.

IV.a THE BASELINE FOCUS GROUPS

For the purpose of this baseline study, each local research team has run one focus group³⁹ in the period July – November 2021.

Specific methodological guidelines, guiding questions and related indicators as well as training were provided by partner ISIM to the LCAs, who organized and run the focus group in their local language, involving from 5 to 10 persons per city. Only people belonging to the intervention group were involved in the focus group, with the aim of

- ensuring heterogeneity of participants in order to balance different points of view as well as GDEI characteristics;
- involving as much as possible a stable group of people across the evaluation stages (ex-ante, ongoing, ex-post).

The management of the group discussion was done by the community activators, following a set of topics (guiding questions) that stimulated the group to reflect in depth on some city specific sub-dimensions and indicators of IHW, actually encouraging direct comparison of different points of view.

The focus group helped detecting in-depth information on some key aspects of IHW concerning both context and impact indicators in each city, by deepening, for instance, the point of view of people belonging to groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion. The qualitative data collected also helped complement the results of the survey and completed the initial picture concerning IHW of the intervention groups.

Last but not least, focus groups and stories also helped detecting unexpected aspects of the context, not initially considered in the research design.

The guidelines for the organization and management of the focus groups were drafted by ISIM and are attached to this report in Annex 3.

IV.b BASELINE DATA COLLECTION THROUGH STORYTELLING

For the purposes of the baseline study, storytelling were used as a data collection method with the aim of detecting the change affecting specific aspects (sub-dimensions) of people's socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles before and after COVID 19.

Storytelling has been tested in the proposed baseline study since it allows to grasp emotional aspects and nuances of individual experiences that other research tools fail to provide.

Compared to semi-structured interviews, storytelling has no rigid interview scheme, but makes use of open dialogue.

Five stories per city have been collected by the LCAs by means of an open interview to local inhabitants, who were selected on the basis of (i) their personal characteristics, (ii) their level of involvement/interest in the project as well as (iii) on their availability to tell a meaningful personal story.

ISIM has developed a five-steps methodology to use storytelling as a means of evaluation and community activators have been trained to use this methodology on field. The five steps, as well as personal data management issues, guiding questions and indicators involved in the storytelling exercises are included in the Guidelines for the LCAs (Annex 3).

³⁹ For a more in depth description of the focus group methodology and their role within the impact assessment plan. Please refer to D7.1 part B.

V. LESSONS LEARNT FROM THE BASELINE STUDY

The baseline study on IHW represented the first joint fieldwork research among partners ISIM, UREAD and the local research teams, including the LCAs hired by local research and/or city partners.

A monitoring and evaluation action was carried by ISIM during and after the fieldwork of the LCAs in order to get information on the progress of the work, the achievements and obstacles encountered by the LCAs and to propose corrective measures, especially with respect to the capacity to reach and involve the expected local target groups and to cover both control and intervention groups.

A final progress report on the fieldwork for the baseline study has been produced by LCAs and analysed by ISIM at the end of the baseline data collection.

The results of this monitoring and evaluation action have been discussed in a meeting organized by ISIM on 9th December 2021, with the involvement of the local research teams.

The main lessons learnt, obstacles and possible countermeasures resulting from this monitoring action are reported as follows.

• Lesson learnt #1

The situation created by the Covid 19 pandemic required flexibility and the ability to adapt research methodologies to the changing conditions of the context

As a result, there is no “one-fits-all” strategy for the distribution of the survey, rather a mixed approach (mostly online + interview mode) seems to be the most suitable depending on the target and context.

• Lessons learnt #2

The baseline study made a sound use of both the snowball sampling and the citizen science inclusion mechanism. In fact:

- local observers have been contacted and played an active role (administrating the survey in Riga, hosting events in Nitra and Cordoba, distributing the paper questionnaire in Nitra, disseminating the link to the survey in Lucca/Cordoba/Riga/Nitra;
- moreover, the baseline study was an opportunity to search and include other organizations belonging to the target groups in all the pilots' IN-HUBS;
- third, local observers and other local inhabitants helped reaching the most vulnerable people and those usually excluded from participatory processes (Nitra, Cordoba), hosting events for the distribution of the survey (Nitra, Cordoba), explaining the survey and helping understanding the questions (Riga, Nitra).

• Lessons learnt #3

Reaching local target groups and people at risk of discrimination and exclusion requires a great effort.

The success factors in this sense were:

- the capacity to intercept people where they usually meet with the help of a local persons/organization: school parents and teachers (Nitra), community centers (Nitra), applicants to benefits from social services (Cordoba), private houses (Cordoba, Nitra),
- meeting people in public spaces in the neighbourhood after having invited them (Riga, Nitra, Cordoba)
- the use of targeted digital channels/social network profiles (Lucca, Cordoba)
- the use of one-to-one / door-to-door approach with individual interviews in familiar/neutral venues (Riga, Nitra, Cordoba)
- the active collaboration of local inhabitants and NGOs in the organization of events (Cordoba, Nitra), in supporting the organization of the door-to-door interviews (Cordoba, Nitra) or in the paper distribution (Nitra)
- the use of incentives

The main obstacles and countermeasures tested during the fieldwork or suggested for future data collection actions are summarised in the following table.

♦ **Table n.22** – Main obstacles and countermeasures related to the baseline study fieldwork

Obstacles encountered	Countermeasures applied/suggested
NGOs are unlikely to meet because of the Covid	Applied: (i) Leverage places and services that people still use/attend, i.e. school, social services, community centers (Nitra, Cordoba)
The questionnaire was long, it included sensitive questions, the consent form required personal data and was too long	Suggested: (i) The questionnaire will remain the same for the ex-post survey, but ISIM will try to improve the consent form and avoid asking personal data for future surveys
People do not understand the need for providing sensitive information, the link with the IN-HABIT project and feel uncomfortable when speaking about themselves or their neighbourhood	Applied: (i) Presentation of the survey during an event or before the one-to-one interview to explain the context (Riga, Lucca; Cordoba, Nitra) (ii) Organisation of the research activities in a place that is familiar to the participant (Cordoba; Nitra) (iii) Separation of the group of participants to the focus group (Nitra)
The questionnaire was difficult to be understood by elderly	Applied: (i) Use of the interview modality to help explaining the questions (Cordoba); (ii) Reach them out in their community/senior centers (Nitra).
Migrants and ethnic minorities were not easy to reach	Suggested: (i) Use of the Russian translation in Riga. Applied: (i) Use of organizations working with this target group, i.e schools, Red Cross, migrant centers (Cordoba, Nitra)
Few time to test the survey	Suggested: (i) Isim will provide the test version in advance at an earlier stage, trying to avoid Summer holidays.

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LIST OF ANNEXES

All the annexes are accessible at the following link:

<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/d7-3-baseline-study-on-iHW-report/>

- **ANNEX 1** Baseline values of the Key Impact Indicators and Context Indicators on IHW
- **ANNEX 2** The baseline city surveys
- **ANNEX 3** Guidelines for the local community activators
- **ANNEX 4** Context and Impact Indicators
- **ANNEX 5** Reports from focus groups and storytelling sessions

